

D2.3 Guidelines, protocols and policy on legal and ethical aspects for fair data handling

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List of abbreviations

Full name	Abbreviation
Deliverable 2.3	D2.3
Local Energy Communities	LECs
Work packages	WPs
General Data Protection Regulation	GDPR
Regulation on a framework for the free flow of non-personal data	FFNPDR
ePrivacy Directive	ePD
ePrivacy Regulation	ePR
Data Governance Act	DGA
Data Act	DA
Open Data Directive	ODD
Web Accessibility Directive	WAD
Regulation on Electronic IDentification, Authentication, and Trust Services	eIDAS
Network and Information Systems Directive	NIS
CyberSecurity Act	CSA
Cyber Resilience Act	CRA
Electricity Market Directive	EMD
Renewable Energy Directive	RED
Implementing Regulation on interoperability requirements and non-discriminatory and transparent procedures for access to metering and consumption data	IR
Article	art.
Small and medium-sized enterprises	SMEs
European Union	EU
Electronic identification	eID
Computer Security Incident Response Team	CSIRT
NIS Cooperation Group	The Group
Computer Security Incident Response Teams	CSIRTs Network
EU Agency for Cybersecurity	ENISA
Member State	MS
Cyber crisis management structure	CyCLONe
Information and communications technology	ICT
Artificial Intelligence	AI
European Cybersecurity Certification Group	ECCG
Stakeholder Cybersecurity Certification Group	SCCG
Renewable energy sources	RES
Demand response	DR
Validation cases	VCs
HLEG Ethical Guidelines on Trustworthy AI	HLEG AI guidelines

Distributed ledger technology	DLT
Distribution system operators	DSOs
Decision Support System	DSS
INTEgrated Energy Management	INTEMA
Virtual intEgrated platfoRm on LCA	VERIFY
Data protection law requirements	PLR
Energy law requirements	ELR
Findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable	FAIR
Data Protection Impact Assessmen	DPIA
Ethical Requirement	ER
Ethical guidelines for trustworthy AI	EGTAI

Executive Summary

This document constitutes Deliverable 2.3 titled ‘Guidelines, protocols and policy on legal and ethical aspects for fair data handling’ (D2.3) in the framework of the DATA CELLAR Project, otherwise known as “Data Hub for the Creation of Energy communities at the Local Level and to Advance Research on them” (Project Acronym: DATA CELLAR; Grant Agreement No.: 101069694).

This Deliverable provides detailed and extensive guidelines on ethical and legal aspects of data handling. In doing so, it points out the main legal and ethical risks that are attributed to the DATA CELLAR project and provides protocols and recommendations on how they can be addressed throughout both the duration of the projects as well as the data cycle.

These guidelines should be adhered to and followed by all project partners during all phases of the DATA CELLAR project. An overview of the project and other relevant information can be found in section 2. The main conclusions and guidelines can be found in sections 5.3, 6.3 and 7.

1 Introduction

This section will provide: a project summary and overview (1.1), an overview of the deliverable’s objective and its structure (1.2), a description of the relationship between this deliverable with other tasks and deliverables (1.3), and the methodology that will be used throughout this deliverable (1.4).

1.1 Project summary and overview

A greener energy system is crucial for the future prosperity and liveability of European citizens. This requirement is at the heart of the DATA CELLAR approach where Local Energy Communities (LECs) have been recognised by the European Commission as playing a pivotal role in driving the EU’s energy transition. At the same time, both the digitisation of the EU energy system and the proper exchange of data between energy actors are crucial to fostering an exchange of best practices and the creation of a knowledge community to tackle one of our society’s most pressing global crises: climate change.

Figure 1: DATA CELLAR Rationale

In this context, DATA CELLAR aims to implement a collaborative platform that will provide an interoperable and secure energy dataspace, capable of delivering access to datasets and AI models, to serve and support the spread of energy communities in the European Union, leveraging on experience gained in the development of other EU projects.

DATA CELLAR will create a decentralized dataspace to store streams of historical data coming from private metering, but it will also provide a data federation, integrating data coming from both external companies and EU federation spaces. The dataspace will be populated by a series of services dedicated to energy utilities, energy communities, private businesses, and citizens. Furthermore, DATA CELLAR will provide a decentralized and open marketplace for energy datasets and pre-trained AI models to serve and support LECs.

To achieve its objectives, DATA CELLAR is divided into 9 work packages (WP) with different objectives, tasks and deliverables. This deliverable is a part of WP which focuses on the value of energy data for energy communities' uptake. This WP strives to analyse data that will populate DATA CELLAR as well as estimate and account for its risks by creating ethical and legal guidelines for data handling. These guidelines will include legal and ethical requirements and policies, guidelines, protocols and recommendations that should be implemented by project partners and DATA CELLAR in all their activities, deliverables and tasks.

1.2 Deliverable's objectives and structure

This deliverable is based on the outcomes of two tasks, namely, T2.5 on data justice in energy communities and T2.6 on ethical aspects of data handling. Together, these tasks seek to identify the main legal and ethical risks that could be encountered by DATA CELLAR during the duration of the project. These tasks also involved proposing relevant guidelines, best practices and protocols that should be employed by the consortium to address the risks.

The results of these tasks are presented in this deliverable, which will be structured in the following way:

- *Chapter 1* articulates the deliverable objectives and displays its links with the pertinent tasks.
- *Chapter 2* includes an introduction to the legal and ethical aspects of data handling, addressing relevant ethical principles as well as data protection, cyber-security and energy-specific laws of the EU.
- *Chapter 3* includes a general overview of the ethical and legal issues,
- *Chapter 4* provides a brief description and classification of the relevant data used by the DATA CELLAR dataspace, explaining the different data roles of data users found in the applicable legislation, and describing DATA CELLAR's functionalities and tools.
- *Chapter 5* focuses on legal and ethical requirements for data handling, addressing legal and ethical risks and proposing guidelines, protocols and recommendations to address them.
- *Chapter 6* relates to legal and ethical requirements on cyber and data security, their implications, challenges and guidelines, and protocols for implementation.
- A *Conclusion Chapter* briefly summarises the main findings of the deliverable.
- References.
- Appendix.

- Annex, including a T2.6 Ethics Workshop Report.

1.3 Relation to other tasks and deliverables

D2.3 is primarily based on the findings of T2.5 and T2.6. Nonetheless, it also builds on outcomes of T1.2, T1.3.1, T1.3, T2.2 and T2.4 as well as D9.2, which can be summarised as follows:

1. T1.2 put forward the data governance and interoperability requirements for the project and was reported in the D1.2.
2. T1.3.1 described the applicable data requirements for relevant energy data and was documented in the Annex to D1.2.
3. T1.3 established preliminary requirements and specifications for the functionalities and tools that will be developed in DATA CELLAR. Its findings were incorporated in D1.3.
4. T2.2 focused on data generation, acquisition and ingestion. The results of this task were used to develop the data requirements created by T1.3.1.
5. T2.4 aimed to develop data anonymisation and aggregation schemes for data that will be available via DATA CELLAR, which main findings were incorporated in D2.2.
6. D9.2 provides guidelines for the project to ensure that all research activities are ethically conducted with respect to privacy, data protection, safety, and general research conduct.

The outcomes of this deliverable will provide guidelines for other WPs such as WP3 on Interoperability and federation of EU energy dataspace, WP4 on DATA CELLAR ICT Architecture, WP5 on DATA CELLAR Data-driven energy services and WP6 on DATA CELLAR Marketplace.

1.4 Methodology

1.4.1 Legal Approach

The legal part of this deliverable is based on desk research, targeted literature review and doctrinal research focused on the legal and regulatory challenges surrounding dataspace, the relationship between and within data-sharing frameworks, and legal aspects of the design of dataspace. The usage of a doctrinal legal research methodology allows us to distil legal issues, legal requirements, guidelines and best practices from primary and secondary law that are of crucial importance for data handling as well as for ensuring that DATA CELLAR will be legally compliant with relevant legislative frameworks. Overall, this analysis will allow us to summarise legal requirements that are binding for DATA CELLAR and pinpoint how legal compliance could be attained. In doing so, this deliverable acknowledges that the legal framework for data-sharing is not yet in force, therefore, it is also included in its scope as a relevant legislative proposal.

The selected literature for this contribution consists of academic literature, and project deliverables such as TwinEnergy (van der Wees et al., 2021), BRIGHT (Iannone et al., 2021), or EU-SysFlex (Kallle, 2019). It also considered reports on dataspace, data ownership, access and processing, and data protection with a focus on AEPD on Approach to the Dataspace from the perspective of GDPR (AEPD, 2023). Additionally, it also considered applicable and upcoming legislative frameworks, for instance:

1. Data protection laws: General Data Protection Regulation,¹ Regulation on a framework for the free flow of non-personal data,² ePrivacy Directive³ and ePrivacy Regulation,⁴ Data Governance Act,⁵ Data Act,⁶ Open Data Directive,⁷ Web Accessibility Directive⁸;
2. Cyber-security laws: Regulation on Electronic IDentification, Authentication, and Trust Services,⁹ Network and Information Systems Directive,¹⁰ CyberSecurity Act,¹¹ Cyber Resilience Act¹²;
3. Energy-specific laws: Electricity Market Directive,¹³ Renewable Energy Directive,¹⁴ Implementing Regulation on interoperability requirements and non-discriminatory and transparent procedures for access to metering and consumption data.¹⁵

This contribution draws on the work performed in different tasks within DATA CELLAR, namely, T2.5, T1.3.1, and T1.3. T2.5 investigated data justice in energy communities, focusing on data rights enjoyed by them and factors that could have a detrimental impact on the examined rights. T.1.3.1 indirectly and directly touched on the challenges related to data access and energy sharing as well

¹ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (GDPR) [2016] OJ 2016 L 119/1.

² Regulation (EU) 2018/1807 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 November 2018 on a framework for the free flow of non-personal data in the European Union (FFNPDR) OJ L303/59.

³ Directive (EU) 2002/58/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 July 2002 concerning the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications sector (ePD) [2009] OJ L 241.

⁴ Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL concerning the respect for private life and the protection of personal data in electronic communications and repealing Directive 2002/58/EC (ePR) [2017] COM/2017/010 final.

⁵ Regulation (EU) 2022/868 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on European data governance and amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1724 (DGA) [2022] OJ L 152/1.

⁶ Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data (DA) [2022] COM/2022/68 final.

⁷ Directive (EU) 2019/1024 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information (ODD) [2019] OJ L 172/56.

⁸ Directive (EU) 2016/2102 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 October 2016 on the accessibility of the websites and mobile applications of public sector bodies (WAD) [2016] OJ L 327/1.

⁹ Regulation (EU) No 910/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 July 2014 on electronic identification and trust services for electronic transactions in the internal market and repealing Directive 1999/93/EC (eIDAS) [2014] OJ L 257/73.

¹⁰ Directive (EU) 2022/2555 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union, amending Regulation (EU) No 910/2014 and Directive (EU) 2018/1972, and repealing Directive (EU) 2016/1148 (NIS2) [2022] OJ L 333/80.

¹¹ Regulation (EU) 2019/881 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on ENISA (the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity) and on information and communications technology cybersecurity certification and repealing Regulation (EU) No 526/2013 (CSA) [2019] OJ L 151/15.

¹² Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on horizontal cybersecurity requirements for products with digital elements and amending Regulation (EU) 2019/1020 (CRA) [2022] COM/2022/454 final.

¹³ Directive (EU) 2019/944 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 June 2019 on common rules for the internal market for electricity and amending Directive 2012/27/EU (recast) (EMD) [2019] OJ L 158.

¹⁴ Directive (EU) 2018/2001 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2018 on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources (recast) (RED) [2018] OJ L 328.

¹⁵ Commission implementing Regulation on interoperability requirements and non-discriminatory and transparent procedures for access to metering and consumption data (Implementing Act) Ares(2022)5456543.

as other important data-related aspects relating to energy communities, such as the nature of energy data, the role of data in activities of energy communities, data ownership and data processing with focus on challenges, and different modes of data access. T1.3 focused on data requirements as well as defining and explaining DATA CELLAR's inputs and outputs.

In general, this deliverable will provide the reader with an overview of legal requirements that need to be complied with, as well as guidelines and best practices that facilitate compliance and which are required if DATA CELLAR's dataspace and its functionalities are to comply with applicable legal frameworks.

1.4.2 Ethical Approach

In its provision of guidelines, protocols, and recommendations for implementation on the ethical aspects of data handling, this deliverable follows the methodology expounded in the SIENNA project for integrating ethics by design into technological development and formulating ethical guidelines. As emerging technologies, by definition, "have not yet fully formed," some of the challenges and implications of the DATA CELLAR functionalities may be unclear or indeterminate. (SIENNA, 2022, p.17) Using a standardised methodology, such as the SIENNA framework, ensures that the ethical guidelines, protocols, and policy recommendations cover ethical challenges and implications as comprehensively as possible.

Ethics by design involves the early integration of ethical values and principles into the design and development process, as well as ensuring that they remain key considerations throughout the project lifecycle. It is utilised within the DATA CELLAR project to publicly demonstrate how the project partners are identifying and addressing ethical challenges and implications, as well as to guide the formulation of guidelines, protocols, and recommendations to project partners on ethically responsible data handling, research, and development. The SIENNA project formulated an ethics by design methodology that can be applied to specific fields of technology, including the energy sector. This ethics by design methodology has been adjusted to fit the DATA CELLAR project and the requirements of this deliverable. Thus, some phases of the methodology are completed simultaneously, rather than being completed chronologically, as illustrated in the diagram below. For example, stages 4 and 5 are completed concurrently within section 5.2.2 pertaining to data processing and section 6.2.2 relating to cyber and data security. Additionally, the SIENNA methodology includes the selection and use of a design methodology, such as CRISP-DM (IBM, 2021), as an analytical tool to structure the development process. Given the infancy of the DATA CELLAR functionalities, this step has been simplified as the 'selection of an analytical framework to frame the risk analysis and provision of guidelines.' Figure 2 exhibits the necessary stages used within the ethics by design methodology, identifying the phases of the DATA CELLAR project which correspond with each step. This includes steps conducted prior to this deliverable as well as steps conducted within this deliverable.

Figure 2: Overview of the ethics by design methodology, in line with the SIENNA methodology

The first stage of the ethics by design methodology detailed above requires the project partners and relevant stakeholders to reach a consensus on the most applicable and significant ethical values which apply to the DATA CELLAR functionalities and the data handling involved in their design, development, and deployment. As per the SIENNA methodology, this phase has been addressed throughout M8-13 of the project through extensive desk-based research, including a literature review of ethics journal articles and books, and grey literature, such as reports, whitepapers, and existing ethics guidelines. Additionally, as part of T2.6, DATA CELLAR project partners and relevant stakeholders collaborated in M10 (April 2023) to identify and discuss the most relevant ethical aspects of data handling within the project through a co-design workshop. The workshop focused on the main functionalities to be developed within DATA CELLAR as well as validation cases wherein the technology is expected to be deployed, identifying ethical values and issues as well as considering potential solutions.

In the DATA CELLAR context, co-design refers to the active involvement of a range of stakeholders throughout the creation, design, and development of new technology. This process involves deliberation between stakeholders and internal experts within the consortium to collaboratively ideate solutions to potential risks or problems as well as to maximise the positive social impact of that technology. Co-design is thus an inclusive and flexible process, involving a range of diverse actors and ideas. In this way, the ethics workshop is an example of one co-creative method utilised within this deliverable’s ethics by design approach. More information and detail regarding the structure and outcomes of this workshop can be found in the T2.6 Ethics Workshop Report found within [Annex 1](#). For this deliverable’s purposes, it is sufficient to state that this activity contributed to the first phase of the ethics by design methodology, obtaining a degree of consensus on the key ethical values to apply to the data handling throughout the project.

Then, in line with the second phase of the methodology, this deliverable uses existing ethics guidelines, such as the HLEG Guidelines on Trustworthy AI (AI HLEG, 2019) as well as mainstream methods of applied ethics to derive “ethical requisites” (SIENNA, 2021, p.55) and specific ethical

norms which emanate from the broader ethical values in phase one. This phase is about defining the conditions that the DATA CELLAR technology must satisfy to achieve its ethical goals (SIENNA, 2021, p.55) as well as ensuring that the final ethical guidelines, formulated in phase four, are operational. Operational guidelines can be contrasted with general and abstract ethical concepts which are difficult to practically integrate into the project's lifecycle and tools' architectures without further specification. For example, broader ethical values such as transparency can be understood in terms of their specific subcomponents such as explainability, explicability, and traceability. These groups of ethical values and their derivative norms can be understood as "value clusters" within this deliverable (Van de Poel, 2020, p.46). Each cluster contains then ethical norms that correspond to similar kinds of 'goodness' or that fall under a broader, overarching ethical value. In order to produce operational guidelines, section 5.2.2 and 6.2.2 of this deliverable provide ethical guidelines, protocols, and recommendations that are in line with the overarching ethical requirements as well as with the specific ethical norms within each value cluster.

As briefly mentioned above, with regard to the third phase of the methodology, this deliverable frames its assessment of ethical risks around the ethical requirements expounded by the HLEG. Yet, the ethical guidelines, protocols, and recommendations for implementation delivered within this deliverable were produced by considering further additions pulled from desk research and partner feedback from the Ethics workshop conducted in M10 (see [Annex 1](#)).

In terms of phase four, the bulk of this deliverable is focused on formulating and presenting general guidelines on the ethical and legal aspects of data handling within the DATA CELLAR project. The ethics guidelines, along with their legal counterparts, will assist with the integration of law and ethics into the design, development, and deployment of the DATA CELLAR functionalities as well as into the data handling processes adopted at each of these phases. Unlike the legal aspects of this deliverable's guidelines, the ethics guidelines are not legally binding. However, as they prescribe how data should be handled throughout the project lifecycle, they retain the "ability to regulate conduct" (SIENNA, 2021, p.49). These guidelines will communicate general ethical standards for data handling within the project as they relate to the relevant ethical values and norms identified within stages one and two of the adopted methodology.

Alongside these generalised guidelines, protocols and recommendations for implementation will be developed. These protocols and recommendations will be attuned to the specific needs of the DATA CELLAR functionalities and specialised in accordance with the validation cases. By outlining why, when, and where the guidelines will be required, including the relevant actors and actions required for their fulfilment, the protocols and recommendations will identify additional tools and methods that can be used by the project partners to maximise the positive ethical impact of the DATA CELLAR functionalities. As envisaged by the final phase of the SIENNA methodology, this part of the deliverable will develop methods, and specialised recommendations to address the specific ethical issues raised by the DATA CELLAR functionalities or their use cases. Moreover, it will assist in operationalising the ethical guidelines by maintaining sight of the validation cases that pertain to the DATA CELLAR functionalities and of key methods to implement the general ethical guidelines. Ethics guidelines can often be both high-level and abstract. Thus, by combining stages four and five of the SIENNA methodology, this deliverable will provide more usable and operational guidelines that directly apply to the particularities of the DATA CELLAR functionalities and their validation cases.

2 Introduction to the legal and ethical aspects of data handling

This section aims to describe the legal and ethical aspects of data handling and the relationship between ethics and law. To do so this section will be structured as follows:

2.1 Legal Aspects

This sub-section will introduce the relevant regulatory frameworks that need to be complied with by the DATA CELLAR dataspace such as the General Data Protection Regulation, Data Governance Act, Electricity Market Directive, Open Directive, Cybersecurity Act etc. They will be briefly described before being summarised in the form of a table.

2.1.1 Data protection laws

The Data Protection package was initially implemented in 2016 and constituted a part of the European digital transition (European Commission, n.d.-b). According to the European Commission (EC), a significant majority of European individuals express their desire for uniform data protection rights throughout the European Union, regardless of the location at which their data is being processed (European Commission, n.d.-b).

In this context, an assortment of regulatory frameworks has been established by the EU with respect to data protection. These laws are thoroughly described below, with the scope of their application specifically discussed within the summary section 2.1.4.

2.1.1.1 General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

The GDPR composes the strictest legislation globally concerning privacy and security (European Council & Council of European Union, 2022). Despite originating in the European Union (EU), its obligations extend to organizations worldwide if they engage in targeting or gathering data pertaining to individuals within the EU (art.3 GDPR; Wolford, n.d.). This regulation, which came into force on May 25th 2018, imposes substantial penalties on those who infringe upon its standards for safeguarding privacy and security (Chapter VIII GDPR; Wolford, n.d.). By implementing the GDPR, Europe is expressing its resolute position on matters of data privacy and security, precisely when individuals are increasingly placing their personal information in the hands of cloud services, and whilst data breaches have become a regular affair (Wolford, n.d.). The regulation itself is extensive, encompassing a wide range of aspects and lacking detailed guidelines, thereby presenting a formidable challenge for businesses, especially small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), to ensure compliance with GDPR requirements (Wolford, n.d.).

2.1.1.2 Regulation on Free flow of non-personal data (FFNPDR)

To enable companies and public institutions to store and handle non-personal data in any preferred location, the EU guarantees the free flow of non-personal data (European Commission, 2022d). The EC fosters collaboration with stakeholders, illustrated by its use of structured dialogues with EU countries and workshops including diverse stakeholders (European Commission, 2022d).

Furthermore, the EC meticulously supervises the development of codes of conduct to facilitate a smooth transition between cloud providers, and monitors the establishment of a comprehensive European cloud security certification scheme, together with other pertinent endeavours (European Commission, 2022d).

The particular regulatory framework ensures: (i) “free movement of non-personal data across borders,” (ii) “the availability of data for regulatory control,” (iii) “easier switching between cloud service providers for professional users,” (iv) “full consistency and synergies with the cybersecurity package, and clarification that any security requirements which already apply to storing and processing data will persist notwithstanding EU cross border storing and/or processing” (European Commission, 2022d).

2.1.1.3 ePrivacy Directive (ePD) and ePrivacy Regulation (ePR)

The ePrivacy Directive (ePD) focuses on data protection and privacy in the context of electronic communications within the digital era (EDPS, n.d.). It serves as a foundational framework rooted in the Data Protection Directive¹⁶ and governs various crucial aspects concerning the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications sector (art. 1 ePD). These services and networks require specific rules and safeguards to ensure the users’ right to privacy and confidentiality such as security of data processing activities (art. 4 ePD).

The ePrivacy Regulation serves as a supplement to the general guidelines for processing personal data set forth by the GDPR (European Commission, 2023f). It brings ahead distinct provisions for electronic communications and takes priority over the GDPR when both legislations are relevant. In comparison with GDPR, ePR extends its scope beyond personal data and encompasses various aspects, including its impact on B2B marketing and other relevant domains. An updated proposal of the EU further empowered the ePR providing improvements in the following areas, as indicated by the regulation description:

- “Privacy rules (...) apply to new players providing electronic communications services such as WhatsApp, Facebook Messenger, and Skype” (European Commission, 2023f).
- “All people and businesses in the EU enjoy the same level of protection of their electronic communications through this directly applicable regulation” (European Commission, 2023f).
- Privacy is safeguarded for communications like the time and the location of a call (European Commission, 2023f).
- “Metadata (...) has a high privacy component and must be anonymised or deleted if users do not give their consent unless the data is needed for billing” (European Commission, 2023f).
- “Once consent is given for communications data to be processed, traditional telecom operators will have more opportunities to provide additional services and to develop their businesses” (European Commission, 2023f).

¹⁶ Directive 95/46/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 October 1995 on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (Data protection Directive) [1995] OJ L 281.

- “The enforcement of the confidentiality rules in the regulation will be the responsibility of data protection authorities already in charge of the rules under the GDPR” (European Commission, 2023f).

2.1.1.4 Data Governance Act (DGA)

The DGA became legally binding in June 2022. DGA aims to increase the availability of data, and remove technical obstacles for reusing data (European Commission, 2022c). In this context, it will foster the creation, operationalisation and development of common European dataspace, involving players from private and public domains, and encompassing a variety of sectors, most importantly health, environment, energy, agriculture, mobility (European Commission, 2022c).

The benefits delivered by the DGA relate to the availability of data and facilitation of data sharing across different sectors and EU countries (European Commission, 2022c). The regulation improves the way data is managed and shared, which stimulates the creation of new and innovative products and services across industries. It also enhances the efficiency and sustainability of economy-related sectors, while supporting the training of AI systems. By making more data accessible, it enables the public sector to develop policies that promote transparent governance and improve the effectiveness of public services. Moreover, data-driven innovation brings advantages to both companies and individuals by offering data relevant to the aforementioned sectors, as indicated by the regulation (European Commission, 2022c):

- Health data: better, tailor-made treatments, improved healthcare, provision of annual savings in the EU health sector, as well as effective response to covid-19.
- Mobility data: annual savings in labour costs and in time of car drivers via real-time navigation.
- Environmental data: used for reducing CO₂ emissions, utilised against environmental crises such as floods and wildfires.
- Agricultural data: precision farming, new products in the agri-food sector and new services in general in rural areas.
- Public administration data: better and more trustworthy official statistics and evidence-based decisions (European Commission, 2022c).

2.1.1.5 Data Act (DA)

DA is a legislative proposal directed at eligibility and availability of data produced within the EU, applicable to the energy sector and industries found in energy markets. (Explanatory memorandum to DA, 2022, p. 2). DA ensures fairness in the digital environment as it safeguards competitive data market stimulation, establishes opportunities for data-driven innovation, and enhances data accessibility for all, enabling creation of new services and ultimately results in more competitive prices (Explanatory memorandum to DA, 2022, p.13; European Commission, 2022a). The Data Act comprises a fundamental building block of the EC’s data strategy towards the continent’s digitalization-by-2030 objective.¹⁷ On top of that, the proposal marks a significant milestone as the second major legislative initiative stemming from the European strategy for data, launched in February 2020, with the ambitious goal of positioning the EU at the forefront of our data-driven

¹⁷ See https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age/europes-digital-decade-digital-targets-2030_en.

society (European Commission, 2022a). Together with DGA, it will promote unified markets which fosters seamless data flow within the EU and across diverse sectors as well as ensuring compliance with EU values and rules (European Commission, 2022a).

DA strives to address the legal, economic, and technical barriers that prevent data from being reused (European Commission, 2023d). As a result, it will give natural and legal persons more control over their data, making it easier for them to engage in data sharing, thereby creating a new framework for data access and portability. In short, DA will support the development of a fair and open data economy by: i) giving data users more control over their data, which gives them the opportunity to make better, more informed and environmentally friendly decisions, ii) enabling data sharing with third parties, which will empower them to offer improved and new energy related-services, iii) introducing appropriate safeguards aiming at the protection of manufacturers such as compensation for the costs associated with data transfer and the prohibition against the utilisation of shared data in the case when it would result in direct competition with manufactures' products or services, and iv) incorporation of measures against unlawful data transfers and facilitation of data portability (European Commission, 2022a, 2023d).

2.1.1.6 Open Data Directive (ODD)

The ODD provides a common European framework for accessibility and re-useability of publicly owned data (art. 1 ODD; European Commission, 2022b). The directive is applicable to data and information held by the public sector, for example, ministries, public authorities, municipalities, and other local level authorities (art. 1 ODD; European Commission, 2022b). ODD is based on the principles of transparency and fair competition (art. 1 ODD; European Commission, 2022b). The rules enshrined in this legal instrument provide:

- Stimulation of the “publishing of dynamic data and the uptake of application programme interfaces (APIs)” (European Commission, 2022b).
- Limitation of “the exceptions which currently allow public bodies to charge more than the marginal costs of dissemination for the re-use of their data” (European Commission, 2022b).
- Enlargement of the scope of the Directive to “the data held by the public undertakings, applying to data that the undertakings make available for re-use” (European Commission, 2022b) and “research data resulting from public funding – Member States will be asked to develop policies for open access to publicly funded research data”, causing new rules to facilitate “re-usability of research data that is already contained in open repositories” (European Commission, 2022b).
- Enhancement of “transparency requirements for public–private agreements involving public sector information, avoiding exclusive arrangements” (European Commission, 2022b).

2.1.1.7 Web Accessibility Directive (WAD)

WAD is a comprehensive piece of legislation that sets the accessibility standards for public sector-owned websites and mobile applications to ensure that they are understandable and user-friendly for all and potential users (including people with disabilities, older people, etc.) (EUR-lex, 2021). It obliges all public sector bodies to employ and enforce all necessary measures to enhance the accessibility of their websites and mobile applications (EUR-lex, 2021). In particular, their content must be easily “perceivable, operable, understandable, and robust” (art. 4 WAD; EUR-lex, 2021).

To ensure compliance with this legal framework, one can use the harmonized European standards, for example 'EN 301 549 - Accessibility requirements for ICT products and services' which puts forward relevant accessibility criteria (European Commission, 2023a). On top of that, public sector bodies are obligated to provide detailed accessibility statements on a regular basis in which they should address any inaccessible elements, provide alternative accessible options, and explain how users can report non-compliance or request excluded information (EUR-lex, 2021).

Lastly, member states are encouraged to extend the accessibility requirements to other types of websites and mobile applications which are covered by their national laws (EUR-lex, 2021). Furthermore, since this Directive is an example of minimum harmonization, member states also have a possibility to adopt stricter and more extensive requirements than those which are outlined in WAD (EUR-lex, 2021).

2.1.2 Cyber-security laws

The complexity of business processes and the variety of assets used within the smart grids' environment requires more than one cyber-security law to be used to address the diverse security requirements, controls, strategies, and technologies. Hence, within the EU, various regulations and guidelines serve distinct purposes. Some emphasize high-level organizational security requirements, while others concentrate on the technical implementation of cybersecurity controls. The classification of the different cyber-security laws and the main guidelines are described in the sub-sections below.

2.1.2.1 Electronic Identification, Authentication, and Trust Services (eIDAS) Regulation

The eIDAS creates a comprehensive European framework for electronic identification (eID), authentication and trust services (European Commission, 2023b). According to EC, this eIDAS regulation, (i) ensures that people and businesses can use their own national electronic identification schemes (eIDs) to access public services available online in other EU countries, and (ii) creates a European internal market for trust services by ensuring that they will work across borders and have the same legal status as their traditional paper-based equivalents (European Commission, 2023b). In addition, eIDAS brings numerous advantages, including:

1. minimization of the administrative workload regarding electronic transactions that involve businesses, customers, and public administrations,
2. ameliorated efficiency in regard of business processes,
3. considerable cost reductions via increased profits, and
4. enhanced security of electronic transactions, increasing consumer trust and broadening the potential consumer pool (European Commission, 2023b).

Businesses of all scales are influenced by eIDAS, simplifying the transactions between businesses and consumers. eIDAS stimulates strong identity verification techniques, reinforcing the validation of both companies and individuals (European Commission, 2023b). Via eIDAS, mutual recognition of foreign eID schemes is established engaging cross-border transactions (European Commission, 2023b). The eIDAS supports further digital/electronic services benefits such as e-signature,¹⁸^[OBJ]

¹⁸ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-building-blocks/wikis/display/DIGITAL/eSignature> - The eSignature from EC

eSeal,^{19[OBJ]} eTimestamp,^{20[OBJ]} Website Authentication Certificates (WACs),^{21[OBJ]} eDelivery^{22[OBJ]} and they are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 3: The eIDAS regulation application benefits for businesses (ENISA, n.d.-a)

The regulation has influence on sectors such as the financial sector, online retail, the transportation sector, and generally on professional services, enabling them to benefit from significant business opportunities and improving services across borders (European Commission, 2023b).

2.1.2.2 Network and Information Systems (NIS) Directive

NIS Directive came into effect in 2016. It bares significant advancements in cybersecurity as it was the first common European approach aiming at the high level of security for network and information systems (Negreiro, 2023, p. 1). NIS Directive was directed towards the protection of Member States' critical infrastructure from cyber-security threats and vulnerabilities and emphasizes key economic sectors (Negreiro, 2023, pp. 2–3).

The scope of NIS extends to operators of essential services and digital service providers, including sectors such as energy, transportation, water, healthcare, online marketplaces, search engines, and Cloud computing services (art. 1 and 5 NIS; European Commission, 2018). This Directive imposes

¹⁹https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/taxonomy/term/http_e_f_fdata_ceuropa_ceu_fdr8_fE-sealVerificationAndValidationService - The eSeal Verification and Validation Service from EC

²⁰https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/taxonomy/term/http_e_f_fdata_ceuropa_ceu_fdr8_fE-timestampCreationService - The e-Timestamp Creation Service from EC

²¹ [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/ATAG/2023/739285/EPRS_ATA\(2023\)739285_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/ATAG/2023/739285/EPRS_ATA(2023)739285_EN.pdf) – Qualified certificates for website authentication from EC

²² <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-building-blocks/wikis/display/DIGITAL/eDelivery> - The eDelivery for exchange documents and data security and reliability

responsibility on these operators to implement appropriate security measures and promptly report incidents with significant impact on the service continuity (art. 14 and 16 NIS; European Commission, 2018). Additionally, digital service providers are obliged to notify the authorities of incidents that notably affect the availability of their services (art. 14 and 16 NIS; European Commission, 2018).

Figure 4: NIS cooperation medians (CCB, 2022)

The NIS Directive is the first example of harmonisation which requires a high degree of cybersecurity in critical infrastructures within Member States’ institutions and systems. The Directive necessitates that Member States be equipped with a minimum set of capabilities (such as a national strategy, national competent authorities, and a national Computer Security Incident Response Team/CSIRT) (ENISA, n.d.-b). Furthermore, it mandates that appropriate security measures be taken, and significant incidents impacting network and information systems be notified to the national authorities by operators in critical sectors and digital service providers. Moreover, the collaborative work of two partnering groups, established by the Directive, namely the NIS Cooperation Group (The Group) and the network of national Computer Security Incident Response Teams (CSIRTs Network), is utilised by Member States to their benefit (European Commission, 2023e).

Due to the fragmentation and inadequacy of NIS to address current cyber-security dangers and future problems as well as the need to strengthen cyber-resilience evidenced by COVID-2019 crisis (Negreiro, 2023, p. 3), the EU decided to amend NIS in 2021 (Negreiro, 2023, p. 11). NIS2 establishes three broad goals:

1. Improve the cyber-resilience of a diverse collection of firms working across all key industries in the EU,

2. Enhance the level of joint situational awareness and the collective power to prepare and respond to cyber-security vulnerabilities and incidents (Negreiro, 2023, pp. 7–8),
3. Reduce discrepancies in resilience across the internal market in the sectors covered by this legislative framework (Negreiro, 2023, pp. 7–8).

Furthermore, the EU Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA)²³ considers that NIS2 improves the existing cyber security status across EU by:

1. Creating the necessary cyber crisis management structure (CyCLONe),
2. Increasing the level of harmonization regarding security requirements and reporting obligations,
3. Encouraging Members States to introduce new areas of interest such as supply chain, vulnerability management, core internet and cyber hygiene within their national cybersecurity strategies,
4. Bringing novel ideas such as peer reviews for enhancing collaboration and knowledge sharing amongst the Member States,
5. Covering a larger share of the economy and society by including more sectors means that more entities are obliged to take measures to increase their level of cybersecurity (ENISA, n.d.-c).

2.1.2.3 Cybersecurity Act (CSA)

The CSA established a common European framework for the cybersecurity certification of Information and communications technology (ICT) products, services, and processes. Its central objective is to strengthen cybersecurity across the EU, safeguarding against a wide array of threats. Key components of this framework involve granting a continuous mandate to the ENISA and establishing a unified European certification context for ICT products, services, and processes. Under this framework, ICT products, services, and processes undergo certification based on specific criteria, categorizing them into the **three predefined security levels: (i) basic, (ii) substantial, and (iii) high**. Each CSA assurance level defines how resilient the specific product, service or process must be against a cyberattack with a certain level of skill and resources (e.g., high level certification means protection against advanced attacks from attackers with significant skills and resources) (ENISA, n.d.-b).

By establishing a standardized and reliable cybersecurity certification framework at the EU level, CSA empowers consumers to make more informed decisions about the products, processes, and services they choose to use, removing the difficulties in assessing cybersecurity risks posed by various providers. At the same time, it also increases transparency, bolsters trust, and promote safer practices in the ever-evolving digital landscape (ENISA, n.d.-b).

The CSA certification operates on a voluntary basis, unless specified otherwise by other EU or national laws. However, there are certain EU regulation proposals, such as the NISII, and Cyber Resilience Act (CRA), which empower the EC to establish obligations for CSA certification under these regulations. Mandatory certification can take various forms. Alternatively, certification might

²³ <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/> - ENISA, European Union Agency for Cybersecurity

serve to demonstrate compliance with cybersecurity requirements for a particular regulation, acting as a presumption of compliance (European Commission, 2023c).

ENISA, together with Member states represented through European Cybersecurity Certification Group (ECCG), market-oriented organizations, and European institutions participating Stakeholder Cybersecurity Certification Group (SCCG), develops CSA certification schemes (European Commission, 2023g). It is also responsible for managing the certification schemes in collaboration with the member states and is entrusted with public communication regarding the certification schemes as well as the issuance of certificates through a dedicated website, safeguarding transparency and accessibility for stakeholders and the public (European Commission, 2023g). Each European scheme specifies:

1. the categories of products and services covered,
2. the cybersecurity requirements, such as standards or technical specifications,
3. the type of evaluation, such as self-assessment or third party,
4. the intended level of assurance.

2.1.2.4 Cyber Resilience Act (CRA)

The current EU legislation concerning cybersecurity lacks direct mandatory requirements specifically targeting the security of products with digital elements. As a result, the existing EU legislation and initiatives only partially address the identified cybersecurity issues and risks. This has led to a legislative patchwork within the internal market, causing legal uncertainty for manufacturers and users of these products (European Commission, 2023c). This is enhanced by escalating cyberattacks on hardware and software products which have resulted in significant consequences, with the projected global annual cost of cybercrime reaching €5.5 trillion by 2021 (European Commission, 2023c). These products are plagued by two primary issues, leading to increased expenses for users and society. These issues are:

1. Minimal Level of Cybersecurity: The prevalence of vulnerabilities and the inadequate and inconsistent delivery of security updates contribute to a widespread lack of cybersecurity in these products. This vulnerability leaves them susceptible to malicious attacks, compromising user data and system integrity.
2. Unsatisfactory Understanding and Access to Information: Users face challenges in making informed decisions about choosing products with robust cybersecurity features or using them securely. A lack of accessible information hinders their ability to identify and select products with adequate cybersecurity measures, leaving them vulnerable to potential threats (European Commission, 2023c).

To address these problems, the EU put forward a proposal for CRA, which is going to increase the overall level of cybersecurity of all products with digital elements placed on the internal market. It will introduce objective-oriented and technology-neutral essential cybersecurity requirements for these products that apply horizontally, thereby contributing to two cyber-security objectives that are pursued by the EU, namely:

1. Promoting Secure Product Development: The first goal is to foster an environment that encourages the development of secure hardware and software products. This involves ensuring that products entering the market have minimal vulnerabilities, and manufacturers prioritize security throughout the entire life cycle of their products. In these confines, the aim is to enhance the overall cybersecurity of the products available to consumers and businesses.
2. Empowering Users with Cybersecurity Awareness: The second objective is to empower users to consider cybersecurity aspects when selecting and using products with digital elements. By providing relevant information and resources, users can make well-informed choices and use these products securely, mitigating potential risks associated with cyber threats (Council of European Union, 2023).

In this context, CRA will: (i) ensure that manufacturers improve the security of products with digital elements since the design and development phase and throughout the whole life cycle, (ii) safeguard a coherent cybersecurity framework, facilitating compliance for hardware and software producers, (iii) enhance the transparency of security properties of products with digital elements, and (iv) enable businesses and consumers to use products with digital elements securely (European Commission, 2023c).

Figure 5: The CRA work practices (Cyber Risk GmbH, n.d.)

2.1.3 Energy-specific laws

Nearly a quarter of a century has passed since the most prominent publication of the paper on energy laws (Bradbrook, 1996). In this context, the purpose of this section is to demonstrate the content of the energy-specific laws. This review is primarily conducted in response to the privatization and liberalization of energy markets worldwide, the ongoing process of energy transition, and the internationalization and transformations occurring in energy markets. Consequently, energy laws as a legal field have experienced substantial growth and development.

In addition, given the significant influence of DATA CELLAR on the energy sector, it is crucial to provide a comprehensive illustration of the laws specifically pertaining to energy. These laws are thoroughly described below, with the application specifically discussed within the summary section 2.1.4, within the context of the DATA CELLAR project.

2.1.3.1 Electricity Market Directive (EMD)

The EU seeks to establish an integrated energy market to ensure security, sustainability, and affordability regarding energy supplies for the EU citizens. Via the implementation of implementing common rules in energy market, and common cross-border infrastructure, energy can be produced in an EU country and be delivered across the union, enhancing market competition (European Commission, n.d.-c). In order to facilitate it, EMD provides a legal framework aiming at creation of common, competitive, accessible, flexible and non-discriminatory markets for electricity (art. 3 EMD; Ciucci, 2022). In doing so, it puts forwards legal rules and conditions aiming at consumer participation, cross-border trade, rights and duties of energy communities, access to energy data, smart meters, flexibility provisions and overall organisation of electricity sector (Chapter II and art. 2(11), 11, 16, 29 EMD).²⁴

2.1.3.2 Renewable Energy Directive (RED)

The EU has achieved the increase in the share of renewable energy sources (RES) in the energy consumption from the 12.5% in 2010 to 21.8% in 2021, with countries such as Sweden demonstrating a share of 62.2% of the consumed energy produced by RES (eurostat, 2023). In this context, and in order to further strengthen its competitive position in the global energy markets RED aims at promotes the use of energy from renewable sources and contributing to the acceleration of the clean energy transition. RED addresses transportation, heating, and cooling sectors, as well as supports the rights of renewable energy production and consumption and indicates sustainability criteria for biomass (EU Science Hub, n.d.). The EU's renewable energy efforts align with its commitment to climate neutrality by 2050 (European Commission, n.d.-a).

2.1.3.3 Implementing Regulation on interoperability requirements and non-discriminatory and transparent procedures for access to metering and consumption data (IR)

Considering the EMD, which establishes uniform regulations for the internal market for electricity, the Commission has recently implemented new implementing regulation on interoperability

²⁴ https://european-union.europa.eu/institutions-law-budget/institutions-and-bodies/search-all-eu-institutions-and-bodies/agency-cooperation-energy-regulators-acer_en - ACER

requirements as well as non-discriminatory and transparent procedures for accessing metering and consumption data (IR) (Directorate-General for Energy, 2023b).

IR will enable consumers enjoy convenient accessibility to their metering data and give them the ability to grant authorization for third parties to employ data pertaining to their energy usage or generation in manners that confer benefits upon them (Directorate-General for Energy, 2023a). Consequently, this ensures the provision of robust safeguards for consumers, while endowing them with the agency to assume proactive roles as active contributors in the ongoing energy transition (Directorate-General for Energy, 2023a).. In addition, expectations for streamlining the businesses' procedures and system operators within the internal market ensure the seamless, reliable, and protected transmission of data to entities that require it (Directorate-General for Energy, 2023a).. IR will also enable operators to enhance their current practices and foster the advancements of innovative energy services, including but not limited to energy sharing and demand response (DR) (Directorate-General for Energy, 2023a). In this context, IR will encourage innovation and promote the proliferation of cutting-edge solutions that cater to evolving energy demands (Directorate-General for Energy, 2023a). This implementing regulation has been indicated as the initial step in a series of forthcoming measures planned for implementation over the next years, with the overarching objective of fostering the interoperability of energy consumer data (Directorate-General for Energy, 2023a).

IR also introduces the common reference modes ²⁵ which is a comprehensive framework encompassing a collection of standardized procedures and information exchanges governing data access among market players. It primarily focuses on the business, function, and information layers of interoperability, while allowing the communication and the component layers to be tailored based on national contexts. It is a role model, which outlines the various roles and corresponding responsibilities, as well as their interactions. In addition, it bears information regarding objects, attributes, and interrelationships between these objects, while also providing a breakdown of the procedural steps (European Commission, 2017).

2.1.4 Summary of the relevant frameworks

Table 1: Summary of the relevant legal frameworks

Type	Name	Description
Data Protection L.	GDPR	Compliance with the GDPR is vital for DATA CELLAR. To ensure the protection of individuals' personal data, DATA CELLAR must adhere to GDPR principles, including lawful and transparent data processing, collecting data for specific purposes, and limiting data collection to what is necessary.
Data Protection L.	ePR	By complying with ePR, DATA CELLAR can build trust with users and stakeholders, demonstrating its commitment to protecting the privacy and

²⁵ANNEX to the COMMISSION IMPLEMENTING REGULATION (EU).../...on interoperability requirements and non-discriminatory and transparent procedures for access to metering and consumption data (2023) C(2023) 3477 final.

Type	Name	Description
		<p>security of electronic communication while advancing energy sustainability goals and addressing climate challenges. As public energy dataspace facilitate the development of LECs in the EU, DATA CELLAR processes electronic communication data, such as user interactions. Therefore, adherence to ePR principles ensures confidentiality, security, and consent regarding processing electronic communication data. DATA CELLAR must respect the confidentiality of communication and implement appropriate security measures to safeguard electronic communication data. Moreover, the project needs to seek user consent when using cookies or similar technologies for tracking and analytics purposes. Clear and user-friendly cookie consent mechanisms should be provided to users to grant or withdraw their consent.</p>
Data Protection L.	DGA	<p>By promoting the establishment of Data Sharing Service Providers (DSSPs), DATA CELLAR can act as a secure intermediary, enabling controlled data sharing among the stakeholders. The Act's focus on data encourages DATA CELLAR to contribute to the public good by sharing datasets for societal benefits. In this context, this Act provides a safe environment for conducting the aforementioned actions.</p>
Data Protection L.	ODD	<p>By complying with the Open Data Directive, energy-related data must be available for reuse, enabling DATA CELLAR to access valuable datasets to enrich its services. Moreover, the Directive's principles of promoting data sharing and interoperability foster collaboration between DATA CELLAR and various public sector entities, enhancing the scope and value of energy data available.</p>
Data Protection L.	WAD	<p>DATA CELLAR should comply with the Directive's guidelines and standards, ensuring that its websites and applications are designed and developed in a way that facilitates access for individuals with disabilities, thus, creating a more inclusive and user-friendly environment for all stakeholders. In addition, developing a platform that fosters AI accessible for Energy Communities.</p>

Type	Name	Description
Cyber-security R.	eIDAS	The regulation aims to enhance electronic business transactions within the EU, thus, promoting interoperability among the DATA CELLAR's validation cases (VCs). Moreover, it allows people and businesses to use their national electronic identification schemes for accessing online public services in other EU countries, facilitating the operation of DATA CELLAR. It reduces administrative burdens, improves efficiency, and fosters consumer trust in electronic transactions. On top of that, the project's influence will further benefit businesses of all sizes with smoother service delivery and secure solutions.
Cyber-security R.	DA	The Data Act is designed to foster a competitive data market, promote data-driven innovation, and enhance data accessibility, resulting in the emergence of innovative services and more competitive pricing. By harnessing the Data Act's potential, DATA CELLAR is set to produce a positive impact with significant benefits. The enhanced data accessibility provided by the framework empowers the project to access a diverse pool of energy-related information, generating comprehensive insights into energy patterns and usage. Furthermore, DATA CELLAR will be empowered to leverage advanced technologies and analytics for the optimization of energy supply chains, improvements in efficiency, and the development of sustainable energy solutions, all facilitated by the Data Act regulation. Finally, the focus towards users' data and their protection against unfair sharing delivered by the framework promotes trust and collaboration among the stakeholders (energy, technology, management, etc.).
Cyber-security R.	CSA	CSA applies to DATA CELLAR considering the harmonized European system for cybersecurity certification, ensuring robust data protection and secure energy dataspace. Undergoing certification based on specific criteria and predefined security levels, the project achieves improvements on its cybersecurity measures, effectively safeguarding sensitive energy data from a broad range of cyber threats. Moreover, by aligning

Type	Name	Description
		with the CSA's standardized certification framework, DATA CELLAR will be able to infuse trust and transparency among stakeholders by assuring them of the project's implementation of best practices for data management.
Cyber-security R.	CRA	CRA establishes clear and standardized cybersecurity requirements, ensuring hardware and software products within the dataspace and the VCs are developed with higher security levels, concerning the safeguard of data integrity and protection of citizens' privacy. Due to its emphasis on promoting secure product development and enhancing transparency in security properties, the CRA delivers enhanced resilience on energy dataspace against cyber threats and introduces user confidence. Therefore, empowering EU citizens with increased cybersecurity awareness further promotes trust and enables informed decision-making.
Energy-specific L	EMD	This regulation promotes a common energy market and cross-border infrastructure across EU member states, significantly amplifying the impact and influence of DATA CELLAR. By providing a market design with heightened resilience, consumer protection, and seamless integration of RES, the framework creates an enabling environment for DATA CELLAR's operations, while positively impacting its marketplace section. The emphasis on utilising RES and empowering individuals to generate their electricity leads not only to lower consumer prices, but also promotes active participation.
Energy-specific L	RED	This directive actively supports the rights of energy consumers to renewable energy production and consumption, emphasising the sustainability criteria. This framework facilitates DATA CELLAR in making our contribution to the collective effort of achieving the ambitious target of at least 27% renewables in final energy consumption by 2030, with half of the electricity sourced from RES. Moreover, the directive also fosters the development of Energy Communities, further enhancing DATA CELLAR's potential to make a

Type	Name	Description
		positive influence in the energy landscape. The Directive facilitates the achievement of the two main impacts of the project, the promotion of EU Energy System Green and Digital Transition, and the stimulation of Energy Communities’ widespread in Europe.
Energy-specific L	IR	As this guideline establishes uniform regulations for the internal electricity market, it sets the basis for seamless data access and transmission within the energy sector. By ensuring convenient accessibility to metering data and promoting non-discriminatory procedures for data access, the regulation aligns with the objectives of DATA CELLAR. In addition, the framework enhances collaboration and knowledge-sharing among various energy players. DATA CELLAR will provide valorising private metering devices to data and store streams of them into decentralised dataspace. This is made possible by the regulation. On top of that, the framework motivates actors, such as those in DATA CELLAR, to share their data. Finally, the regulation applies to the innovative distribute-ledger (DLT)-driven data remuneration scheme that, with the DATA CELLAR Private Energy Metering, will elevate the LEC prosumers roles as data providers.

2.2 Ethical Aspects

Ethics is a branch of philosophy which is focused on human conduct. It is composed of a range of moral values and principles used to assess the “goodness” or ‘rightness’ (van der Poel, 2020, p.45) of certain conduct or, in this context, data handling within the DATA CELLAR project. Yet, ethics itself is composed of a range of different theories which correspond to different types of ‘goodness’ or ‘rightness’ that can both complement and contradict each other. For example, ethical theories such as utilitarianism dictate that the most ethical course of action is that one which maximises the good, e.g., happiness, focused solely on consequences. On the other hand, deontological ethical theories profess that principles determine the rightness of an act and rightness is determined regardless of consequences. Virtue ethics is instead person-centred, positing that a person’s virtues guide them in making positive ethical choices. The goodness of a certain act according to this type of theory is therefore not dependent on adhering to particular principles or rules of right and wrong behaviour, as within deontology, but rather focuses on a person’s inward ethical values (Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy, 2022). Given the range of ethical theories, it may not be possible to fully adhere to or to realise all the relevant ethical values simultaneously through one ethical framework or theory.

Rather than choosing to maximise one particular good, such as happiness, as one would when using a utilitarian theory, or following one principle or a hierarchical set of principles, this deliverable chooses to use a set of principles. This approach is a form of principlism. (Beauchamp & Childress, 2012). Principlism is an ethical approach especially dominant in biomedical ethics. It assumes that there are several ethical principles and goods, each of which, depending on the context, can be decisive in determining the ethical way to action. To decide the desired ethical course of action, one needs to assess the context and determine what principles or goods are most relevant and outweigh the others. No predetermined system, independent of context, exists to determine the weight of these principles or goods. This approach assumes that ethical issues cannot be unequivocally defined in the abstract, rather they are dependent on the contexts in which they arise. To ensure that this task's guidelines, protocols, and recommendations are both applicable to the relevant use cases within the project and operational within the DATA CELLAR infrastructure, ethical issues and values should be understood contextually.

In line with this principlist approach, the deliverable will avail of a range of ethical codes of conducts and frameworks governing emerging technology, some of which also adopt principlist approaches. There is an abundance of such codes and principles. Thus, following the work of the SHERPA project, this deliverable will focus on those codes most pertinent in the context of DATA CELLAR. These include the HLEG Ethical Guidelines on Trustworthy AI (AI HLEG, 2019), OECD's AI Principles (OECD, 2019), OECD's Good Practice Principles for Data Ethics in the Public Sector (OECD, 2021), the CEN/CENELEC Green and Sustainable AI report (CEN/CENELEC, 2017), the Data Ethics Framework (UK government, 2020), the ISO Working Group's overview of ethical and social guidelines (ISO/IEC, 2022), and technical reports from the JRC (Fulli et al, 2022, Blockchain solutions for the energy transition. Fulli et al, 2022, Policy and regulatory challenges for the deployment of blockchains in the energy field. Nai Fovono et al, 2021). The HLEG Ethical Guidelines, OECD's AI Principles, OECD's Data Ethics Principles, and the UK Data Ethics Framework all identify principles which inform their recommendations and requirements. All the above ethical frameworks will be applied holistically and interchangeably throughout the deliverable. Applying a range of ethical frameworks within the deliverable ensures that the guidelines and recommendations it provides are as comprehensive as possible.

Additionally, whilst the HLEG AI guidelines form the main analytical framework for the ethical requirements outlined in section 5.2.1 and 6.2.1, it is appreciated that this framework is specifically addressed to AI and some of the functionalities developed within the project do not rely on AI technology. This choice of framework can be justified for three reasons. First, the HLEG guidelines encompass a range of ethical values and principles that generally apply across data processing and handling and remain applicable even in non-AI-specific areas. This is highlighted within the ethical requirements tables in sections 5.2.1 and 6.2.1. Second, the requirements of the HLEG guidelines are reinforced by frameworks such as the Data Ethics Framework, which pertains to data handling within the public sector more generally. Thus, this framework is particularly useful when examining the data marketplace functionality. The NIST framework for improving Critical Infrastructure Cybersecurity is used to influence the ethical requirements identified and guidelines developed for cyber and data security of technologies, regardless of whether these utilise AI. Further, technical reports from the JRC which discuss ethical issues pertaining to blockchain and DLT technology support the ethical requirements and guidelines delivered for this functionality within the project. Third, the HLEG guidelines are used simply as an analytical framework and ethical values and

requirements which were identified and prioritised as important in each of the ethics workshop breakout rooms also guide the guidelines and protocols developed within this deliverable. This ensures a full examination of the ethical values pertaining to each of the specific functionalities developed, regardless of whether they rely on AI.

Using the principlist approach as well as drawing on the relevant ethical frameworks aforementioned, this deliverable seeks to examine the main ethical values and issues engaged by the DATA CELLAR functionalities and their data handling processes. Five ethical values are instrumental to promote within the DATA CELLAR project. These include the basic ethical principles underpinning research activities, as identified by the Belmont Report, namely beneficence, autonomy, and justice. Further, the HLEG Guidelines' ethical requirements, which guide sections 5.2 and 6.2 of this deliverable, were informed by the principles of respect for human autonomy, prevention of harm, fairness, and explicability. Thus, the promotion of these principles will also be prioritised throughout the deliverable. Yet, rather than strictly adhering to the principles set out in the HLEG guidelines, this deliverable will also promote privacy as an independent value, instead of this value becoming subsumed under the principles of autonomy or non-maleficence. This is due to its importance as an ethical principle²⁶ within this project, as identified by project partners during the April 2023 Ethics Workshop.

In line with the project's co-design approach, the most pertinent ethical values and concepts in the context of the DATA CELLAR project and energy-sharing spaces were also identified based also on feedback from project partners during the April workshop. Across the functionalities discussed in each of the breakout rooms, one of the most relevant ethical values was privacy. A more detailed overview of the other relevant ethical values for data handling within DATA CELLAR, issues that relate to these values, and explanations for these respective aspects are provided in section 3.2. For this section's purposes, it is sufficient to state that the core ethical aspects that will be promoted throughout this deliverable are respect for human autonomy, prevention of harm, fairness, explicability, and privacy.

2.3 Relationship and overlap between legal and ethical aspects

In the interests of clarity and ease, this deliverable will deal with the legal and ethical guidelines pertaining to data handling separately. Yet, the relationship between law and ethics and the interrelation between legal and ethical principles is appreciated throughout. Put simply and avoiding jurisprudential debates on the distinction between law and ethics as far as possible, the law refers to the rules that emanate from an authoritative institution and govern societal conduct. Individuals feel bound to follow such rules as law (Hart, 2012). Unlike the rules-based structure of law, ethics involves moral values, practices, norms, and principles that "guide and limit our conduct and shapes our basic behavioural patterns" (Spinello, 2001). Whilst ethics also influences people's behaviour and conduct, ethical frameworks are not enforceable per se. Rather, ethics answers the question of

²⁶ It is widely acknowledged academically that privacy is an ethical principle in and of itself whose realisation contributes to the achievement of a range of goods and ends. See Allen, A.L. (2012) What Must We Hide: the Ethics of Privacy and the Ethos of Disclosure. Faculty Scholarship at Penn Carey Law. 557.

how one should live their life and is not as focused on using sanctions to ensure subscription to its frameworks.

Despite these differences, it is appreciated that law and ethics are interconnected. Alongside its position as a prominent branch of philosophy, ethics is understood to be a core component to ensuring legal and regulatory compliance by the European Commission (European Commission, 2023). Ethics can help bridge the inevitable gaps between the underlying spirit and wording of a particular regulation or piece of legislation. Law's punitive power requires its rules and regulations to be concrete and sufficiently specific for individuals. Conversely, ethical values and principles are often broader, representing the rationale underpinning a particular legal rule. Thus, ethical considerations can be a useful source of guidance in areas where the law has not had an opportunity to adapt to or regulate new technologies or technology-enabled practices.

Moreover, ethics are a fundamental constituent of legal human rights obligations and are repeated in various human rights documents such as the European Charter of Fundamental Rights. Thus, ethics plays a key role in ensuring the DATA CELLAR technology does not “impair fundamental human rights [but rather] contributes to the values they embody.” (Mordini et al, 2009, p.211) For example, whilst the grounding of privacy and data protection as enforceable rights speaks to their importance, their application to the DATA CELLAR technology is not exclusively limited to their legal remit. This is because no matter how widely drafted, fixed rules and rights can “never prevent or anticipate all possible misconduct” (Marchant et al, 2011, p.160). Thus, the underlying spirit of the right to privacy may not always be upheld even where the legal terms of the right are adhered to. Kershaw summarises this concept, stating that legal rules are “both under and over-inclusive in relation to the original principle” (Kershaw, 2005, p.605). For this reason, whilst privacy exists as a legal right, it is also applied throughout this deliverable as an ethically enforceable principle with its own moral weight, independent of its legal existence. As a result of this relationship, although the deliverable separates legal and ethical guidelines, the two may overlap and interconnect throughout. Where two guidelines overlap or are linked, this is highlighted with a footnote.

3 General overview of the ethical and legal issues

The objective of the section is to identify and describe the main legal and ethical issues: e.g., gaps in data, bias or inaccuracies, unlawful data collection contrary to intellectual property rights or data protection laws, unfair data access policies, biases in the DATA CELLAR services or algorithms, or problems with data subjects rights (e.g., issues with the rectification of information). To do so, this section will be structured accordingly:

3.1 Legal issues

According to desk research, the main legal issues relating to the energy dataspace are: 1) legal uncertainty, 2) data ownership and control, 3) security, 4) interoperability, 5) data governance, and 6) compliance with legal frameworks and fundamental rights.

3.1.1. Legal uncertainty

Legal uncertainty relates to the uncertainty about the applicability of law due to the dichotomy between a) public and private data (Apráez, 2021, p. 3; Fia, 2021, p. 184) and b) personal and non-personal data (Apráez, 2021, p. 2; Fia, 2021, p. 185; Graef & Gellert, 2021, p. 5). This uncertainty could be also attributed to c) tensions between and within (upcoming or already existing) regulations (Graef et al., 2019, p. 25; Espinosa Apráez, 2022, p. 110). Furthermore, due to the novelty of data sharing regulations and the technologies that enable it, there is d) a lack or unclear terms and provisions (Kerber, 2023, p. 120).

3.1.1.1 Dichotomy between public and private data

To establish the applicability of the legal framework, one can rely on the distinction between public and private sector data (Apráez, 2021, p. 3; Fia, 2021, p. 184). Nonetheless, as argued by Fia and Apráez, this distinction may not necessarily represent today's realities of data generation and might have negative implications for legal certainty (Apráez, 2021, p. 3; Fia, 2021, p. 184). In this context, EU data protection regulation often relies on the notions of either 'publicly held data' or 'privately held data' (Apráez, 2021, p. 3; Fia, 2021, p. 184). As shown by Apráez, this is problematic where 1) the rights of data holders are not unambiguous, with both public and private bodies participating in the generation of the data in many cases, and 2) blurred border between private and public sphere as private bodies are assuming tasks and responsibilities of public bodies due to delegation or privatization (Apráez, 2021, pp. 12–13; Espinosa Apráez, 2022, p. 167).

3.1.1.2 Dichotomy between personal and non-personal data

The applicability of the legal framework could be based on the nature of the data. Nonetheless, as shown by the legal literature, most prominently by Graef and Gellert, the distinction between personal data and non-personal data can be very challenging due to the over-arching definition of personal data (Apráez, 2021, p. 2; Fia, 2021, p. 185; Graef et al., 2019, p. 12; Graef & Gellert, 2021, p. 5) and the presence of 'mixed data sets' (Graef & Gellert, 2021, p. 5).²⁷ 'Mixed data' sets are composed of both personal and non-personal data and make-up the most datasets used in the data economy (the European Guidance on the FFPDR, 2019, p.8; Graef & Gellert, 2021, p. 5). Respectively, the processing of personal data and non-personal data must comply with either GDPR or FFPDR provisions (art. 2(2) FFPDR; the European Guidance on the FFPDR, 2019, p. 8; Graef & Gellert, 2021, p. 5). Nonetheless, it might be hard to distinguish which exact part of the data set is personal or non-personal (Graef & Gellert, 2021, p. 5). This difficulty is not effectively solved by legal instruments. The European Strategy for Data does not elaborate on this problem but refers to the European Guidance on the FFPDR whereas some legal frameworks such as DGA do not even refer to the concept of 'mixed data sets' (the European Guidance on the FFPDR, 2019, p.6; Graef & Gellert, 2021, p. 5).

The former is problematic due to the vagueness of European Guidance on the FFPDR, which states that mixed data sets are "inextricably linked" where a "dataset contains personal data as well

²⁷ European Commission, 'Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council: Guidance on the Regulation on a Framework for the Free Flow of Non-Personal Data in the European Union (the European Guidance on the FFPDR) COM (2019) 250 Final' (2019) 8.

as non-personal data, and separating the two would either be impossible or considered by the controller to be economically inefficient or not technically feasible” (the European Guidance on the FFNPDR, 2019, p. 9; Graef & Gellert, 2021, p. 5-6). This guidance states that such datasets comply with GDPR (the European Guidance on the FFNPDR, 2019, p. 9; Graef & Gellert, 2021, p. 5-6). As a result of this broad interpretation, most mixed datasets could be classified as ‘inextricably linked,’ hence, triggering the applicability of GDPR. This results in a higher threshold for data processing that could limit data sharing (Graef et al., 2019, p. 12; Graef & Gellert, 2021, p. 5). The latter could lead to a conflict between legal frameworks, in particular, some DGA provisions may be at odds with the GDPR, and it is unclear what would occur in the event of a clash (Finck & Mueller, 2023, p. 127; Graef & Gellert, 2021, p. 6).

3.1.1.3 Tensions between and within (upcoming or already existing) regulations

Legal tensions can be found within one legal framework or appear between two or more legal frameworks. In the case of the former, as shown by Graef and others, tensions are visible within the GDPR, namely, due to its data processing principles: purpose limitation and data minimization (Graef et al., 2019, p. 25). These principles are capable of restricting data sharing, whilst some data rights, such as the right of data portability, promote data exchange (Graef et al., 2019, p. 25). Nonetheless, the scholarship also has differing opinions on whether the connection between these concepts can be classified as legal tension (Graef et al., 2019, p. 25).

The latter relates to the tension between two different legal frameworks, in particular, data protection regulation and sector-specific regulation, rendering it especially challenging to situate the position of energy dataspace (Curry et al., 2022, pp. 377-378). Legal literature shows that there is an interplay between data protection laws, for example, GDPR and energy-specific laws, in particular, EMD (Espinosa Apráez, 2022a, pp. 109-110). This can affect how they are interpreted as when interpreted in conjunction, the provisions of one framework could either increase or limit the scope of the other (Espinosa Apráez, 2022a, p. 110).²⁸ The parallel application of different and often corresponding legal rules is likely to lead to an entwinement of different data roles, rights and obligations that can be found in both legal regimes (Espinosa Apráez, 2022a, p. 109).²⁹ In the context of energy communities, it can lead to ambiguity about their data-related rights and obligations since they can perform different market activities and roles (Alanton & Tounquet, 2020, p. 35; Duisberg, 2022, p. 73). Thus, it results in legal uncertainty due to different policy objectives, levels of national transposition or implementation, and supervisory authorities (Espinosa Apráez, 2022a, p. 192; Huhta, 2020, p. 8).

The foregoing is also exacerbated by new and upcoming regulations such as the DGA and DA, which are introducing new rights, legal and policy objectives as well as organizational aspects related to data sharing (Curry et al., 2022, pp. 377-378). This raises the question of what are the potential tensions which can be expected based on the interaction of these new regulations with already existing legal frameworks (Curry et al., 2022, pp. 377-378). In this context, DGA may be at odds with data protection and GDPR because public sector data could also be personal, and its exchange may be unanticipated or pose a risk to the privacy of the data subjects (Ruohonen & Mickelsson, 2023, p. 6). Consequently, to preclude the applicability of the GDPR, it might be necessary to anonymize

²⁸ For more information see Graef, Husovec, et al., 2019.

²⁹ For more extensive information see Espinosa Apráez, 2022b.

personal data which itself might be problematic due to the growing risk of re-identification of data subjects (Ruohonen & Mickelsson, 2023, p. 6; Narayanan & Shmatikov, 2007; Ohm, 2010, p. 1704). This challenge is also present in the case of the non-personal data that is subject to the relevant confidentiality obligations (Ruohonen & Mickelsson, 2023, p. 6). Lastly, the provision of DGA increases the responsibilities of national data protection authorities, for example, requiring them to review data protection impact assessments, including anonymization, before permission to re-use data is granted (rec. 15 DGA; art. 35-36 GDPR; Ruohonen & Mickelsson, 2023, p. 6). This requirement raises questions of whether data protection authorities will be able to ensure compliance and enforcement of the DGA (Ruohonen & Mickelsson, 2023, p. 6).

Similar challenges are also encountered by the DA, which raises open questions about this regulation's relationship with data protection, trade secret law and sector-specific regulation (Kerber, 2023, p. 120). Firstly, concerning data protection laws, the dichotomy between personal and non-personal data can lead to disputes relating to the scope and text of data-sharing agreements, which will raise transaction costs and make data sharing less attractive (Kerber, 2023, p. 126). Secondly, it might be hard to assess through a court dispute whether certain data is protected by the trade secret law, resulting in a higher data processing threshold, the need for confidentiality agreements, and technical and security protection measures (Kerber, 2023, p. 126). Thirdly, DA gives the data holder the possibility to ask for reasonable compensation under fair, reasonable and non-discriminatory terms, which might be contrary to 1) the GDPR where the fee is usually zero and 2) the EMD and IR where data should be made free of charge to final customers and to authorized third parties under the right to portability (art. 20 GDPR; art. 20 and 23 EMD; art. 7 IR; Graef & Husovec, 2022, pp. 3–4; Kerber, 2023, p. 126). Furthermore, more generally, it raises the question of “what is ‘reasonable compensation’ and how is it calculated?” (Kerber, 2023, p. 126).

3.1.1.4 Lack or unclear terms and provisions relating to data sharing

Data sharing could be hampered by the lack of clear terms or ambiguous terms and provisions (Kerber, 2023, p. 120). This can be demonstrated by the use of very broad terms in DGA and an absence of clarity and clear instructions on DGA compliance (art. 12(l) DGA; Richter, 2023, p. 465). With regards to the former, DGA's terminology is very different from the terminology that is used by dataspace (Hilberg, 2023; Richter, 2023, p. 465). For instance, DGA has very broad definitions of data intermediaries, data holders, and users that do not cover the complexity of dataspace. Thus, there is a need for increased alignment between the terminology used by dataspace and the terms employed by the legislation (Hilberg, 2023).

With regards to the latter, for example, art. 12(l) DGA requires data intermediaries to “take necessary measures to ensure an appropriate level of security for the storage, processing and transmission of non-personal data, and the data intermediation services provider shall further ensure the highest level of security for the storage and transmission of competitively sensitive information” (Carovano & Finck, 2023, p. 9; Richter, 2023, p. 465). Nonetheless, it is unclear how these security requirements could be fulfilled in practice (Carovano & Finck, 2023, p. 9). This is also the case for measures seeking to prevent unlawful data transfers (art. 12 (j) DGA) or prerequisites for service continuity which require data intermediaries to continue providing their services in the event of their insolvency (art.12 (h) DGA; Von Ditfurth & Lienemann, 2022, p. 290). This is further exacerbated by the possibility of simultaneous compliance monitoring schemes by competition authorities, data

protection authorities, and other relevant competent authorities, which is likely to result in a disproportionate burden on small market players (art. 13 DGA; Von Ditfurth & Lienemann, 2022, p. 290).

3.1.2 Data ownership and control

In the EU, data ownership is not openly and clearly acknowledged (Boerding et al., 2019, p. 326; Hummel et al., 2021, p. 547; International Data Spaces Association, n.d.-b; Van Asbroeck, 2017). Since it is not regulated, it is hard to establish who is the data owner and what are legal conditions that determine data ownership (Boerding et al., 2019, pp. 326–333; Hummel et al., 2021, pp. 547–551). Data ownership is usually afforded to a “legal entity or natural person executing control over data” (International Data Spaces Association, n.d.-a; Thouvenin & Tamò-Larrieux, 2021, p. 317). This control is often exercised through consenting or giving permission to data sharing or data rights (Duisberg, 2022, p. 62), which gives legal entities or natural persons the ability to decide about the usage of their data (Otto, 2022, p. 5). Nonetheless, because various stakeholders can be entitled to various degrees of data ownership and control, it might be hard to determine who the owner of data is or what data rights should be available to any given natural person or legal entity.³⁰

Furthermore, the exercise of control over data through data rights can be also negatively affected by factors such as legal uncertainty, interference with other legal frameworks, information asymmetries, interoperability, transparency, security and costs (Borgogno & Colangelo, 2019, p. 6; Fia, 2021, p. 191; Graef, Tombal, et al., 2019, pp. 1376–1379; Kerber, 2023, pp. 125–127; Van De Waerd, 2020, p. 2), age, mental and decisional capacity, level of awareness, literacy (also energy and digital literacy) or gender, amongst others (Curry et al., 2022, p. 378; Malgieri & Niklas, 2020, pp. 4–5) .

3.1.3 Security

Due to the increasing reliance on ICT, blockchain, and AI, there is a growing danger of cyber-attacks, data breaches, and other security threats (Espinosa Apráez, 2022a, p. 64; Duisberg, 2022, pp. 75–78). The foregoing requires the incorporation of proper legal, technical, and organizational measures that need to comply with the conditions set by legislative frameworks described in section 6.1.1. Furthermore, it might also necessitate the use of the proper identity and access management, appropriate use of data encryption, and anonymization (Duisberg, 2022, pp. 75–78; Graef & Gellert, 2021, p. 6; Tardieu, 2022, p. 47). The latter can be challenging because “the more non-personal data are combined with other available information, the more difficult it will be to ensure anonymisation because of the increased re-identification risk for data subjects” (Graef & Gellert, 2021, p. 6).

3.1.4 Interoperability

Interoperability is not a legal notion, but it has legal implications. Data-sharing regulations often require a certain degree of interoperability in relation to ICT, data formats, sources, standards, and API (Ahle & Hierro, 2022, p. 416; Curry et al., 2022, p. 378; O’Brien et al., 2022, p. 457; Wierling et al., 2021, p. 7). The main challenge here relates to compliance with interoperability requirements set by the applicable legal frameworks (Ahle & Hierro, 2022, p. 416). This can be perplexing due to the

³⁰ For more information see Annex: T2.6 Ethics Workshop Report.

lack of general adherence to already existing and evolving best practices and standards, as well as their immaturity (Curry et al., 2022, p. 370).

3.1.5 Data governance

Data governance refers to the development of policies and processes that will explain and control data processing as well as ensure protection from inappropriate or unauthorized use (García Mangas et al., 2023, section 3.2). Development of data governance can be difficult due to: 1) the legal uncertainty surrounding new data-sharing regulations, 2) the need to achieve balance between different applicable regulations which often have different objects and goals, and 3) tension between data protection laws and sector-specific regulations (Curry et al., 2022, p. 370).

Data governance also aims to accurately extract value from data (García Mangas et al., 2023, pp. 11-12). This can be complicated due to the absence of data valuation guidelines, assessment tools or measures, and a lack of skills and understanding (Curry et al., 2022, p. 370). These concerns mostly derive from the inability to measure 'perceived data value' against the risks of data sharing, for example loss of data ownership, risks of data breaches or trade secrets (Curry et al., 2022, p. 370). More fundamentally, in the case of energy data and energy communities, the value of data can also change over time. This means that depending on the situation, time data about flexible consumption might be more valuable than data about renewable energy production.

3.1.6 Compliance with legal frameworks and fundamental rights

The regulatory framework surrounding data sharing and dataspace is very extensive and complicated as the applicable regulations overlap and come from different domains of law, namely, data protection, competition, intellectual property, and energy law (Hilberg, 2023). Because dataspace is fairly novel, it is still uncertain how the relationship between these legal frameworks will affect them given the difficulties in understanding the scope and interoperability with and between (existing and upcoming) legislations (Hilberg, 2023). The foregoing can negatively affect DATA CELLAR compliance with applicable legal frameworks. This is also enhanced by its usage of distributive technologies such as AI and blockchain. Their employment might raise compliance issues with, for example, data processing principles, data subjects' rights, and the principle of data by design and default found in the GDPR,³¹ thereby, negatively impacting the right to privacy and freedom from discrimination.

3.2 Ethical issues

As briefly mentioned in section 3.2, some of the key ethical values within the DATA CELLAR dataspace include privacy, human autonomy, prevention of harm, transparency and explicability, and fairness and energy justice. These values have been identified through a literature review, including ethical guidelines and papers. Additionally, issues of data ownership and control, environmental sustainability, and accountability were identified as key ethical issues within the ethics

³¹ For more extensive information see Duarte, 2019, p. 42; Espinosa Apráez, 2022a, p. 201; Finck, 2018, p. 29; Ibáñez et al., n.d., p. 6; Kosta & Leenes, 2022, p. 3; Malgieri & Niklas, 2020, p. 2; Van De Waerdt, 2020, p. 14.

workshop in M10. This section will provide a brief overview of the key issues relating to each of these values which will be addressed by the ethical guidelines as well as the protocols and recommendations for their implementation formulated within this deliverable.

With regard to privacy within DATA CELLAR, specific issues which will be addressed include the potential difficulties balancing privacy with accurate algorithmic functioning and the provision of fine-tuned energy recommendations. Additionally, the collection of personal data such as energy consumption data and the protection of users’ identity on the blockchain pose potential problems in the DATA CELLAR space. Other issues include the variety of stakeholders with a potential entitlement to ownership over the data used in the project and resolving the subsequent control issues. Control issues and repurposing of data is also an important ethical issue in relation to values like transparency. Transparency is a key part of building credibility and trust in the DATA CELLAR space and thus was an important part of workshop discussions between project stakeholders. Further issues which the guidelines will address include the accountability mechanisms in place as well as issues relating to security, such as the protection of energy data from cyberattacks, particularly those targeted towards IoT sensors. Lastly, some of the key ethical issues to be tackled through the ethical guidelines pertain to the notion of energy justice and the question as to whether end-users would reap equitable benefits from the DATA CELLAR space. Concerns regarding bias both within the datasets used and in how energy is eventually distributed and shared are important facets of this question.

3.3 Summary

This section summarises the main findings described within the previous sub-sections. Furthermore, it mentions the issues that are not legal or ethical but nonetheless are important for the fairness of data handling processes. These are presented below in Table 2:

Table 2: Summary of the relevant issues

Issue	Explanation	Classification (e.g. ethical, legal, economic, or technical)
Legal uncertainty	Legal uncertainty relates to uncertainty about the applicability of law and ambiguity about certain legal provisions.	Legal
Privacy	An individual’s control over his/her personal information as well as the ability to choose who to share that information with, who can access that information, and who can use it depending on the given context. Context includes the purpose for which an individual’s data is sought or shared, or the scenario in which an individual is sharing or is requested to share his/her information.	Ethical, Legal
Data protection	Capability, resulting from organisational, legal, ethical and technical processes and measures, which ensures	Ethical, Legal

	privacy, confidentiality, integrity and availability of relevant data.	
Data portability	Ability to move data from one data eco-system, system, or service to the other.	Legal
Data governance	Refers to the development of policies and processes that will explain and control data processing as well as ensure protection from inappropriate or unauthorized use.	Legal
Trust	A belief or confidence that a person or thing will act in a desirable way, particularly in circumstances characterised by risk and uncertainty. A person’s ability to trust often implicitly involves that person accepting the risk that they may be wrong to do so. Trust can also be understood as a belief in the accuracy or dependability of a piece or source of information. In this way, the reliability and credibility of a source or person are key constituents to the building of trust.	Ethical
Interoperability	Ability that allows for the seamless operation of or compatibility between two systems.	Technical
Security	Freedom from threats or danger. Security can be distinguished from safety based on intentionality: safety encompasses protection from unintentional dangers or risks of harm whereas security refers to freedom from intentional threats of harm. Data security refers to the protection of digital information from unauthorised threats and attacks.	Ethical, Legal, Technical
Cybersecurity	Freedom from threats to the confidentiality, integrity, or availability of information contained in the cyber realm. It can also be understood as the measures or processes adopted to protect cyber systems from unauthorised threats to data, cyber-systems, networks, or devices. As with security, cybersecurity is generally associated with intentional threats to information rather than accidents or unforeseen hazards.	Ethical, Legal, Technical
Safety	Protection from hazards caused by natural disasters, accidents, and human errors. Safety can be distinguished from security based on intentionality: security encompasses freedom from intentional threats of harm whereas safety refers to protection from unintentional dangers or risks of harm.	Ethical, Legal
(Data) Ownership	Refers to the possession and control of property. It entails accepting responsibility for that property. For example, with regards to data ownership, the owner of	Ethical, Legal

	data possesses that information and has a degree of power over its access, how it is processed or edited, and how it is used. With this ownership and control comes responsibility for that data.	
(Data)Control	Possessing a degree of power and influence over how a person or object conducts themselves or is used. Data control involves power over data throughout its life cycle.	Ethical, Legal
Informed Consent	Consent needs to be “freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous indication of the data subject's agreement to the processing of personal data relating to him or her, such as by a written statement, including by electronic means, or an oral statement”(rec.32, art. 7 GDPR).	Ethical, Legal
Autonomy	An individual's ability for self-government. To be capable of self-government individuals require at least some knowledge to form their own thoughts and ideas, known as deliberative autonomy, as well as the freedom to act on these deliberations, referred to as executionary autonomy. Autonomy involves an individual's freedom from undue influence on their decision-making capacity and the space to execute those decisions.	Ethical
Balance of power	The equal distribution of power between respective parties.	Ethical
Human Oversight	The degree by which humans can oversee the actions or processes of a given technology or system.	Ethical
Transparency	Openness regarding a system, process, concept, event, or other set of circumstances. For example, AI transparency requires developers and deployers of AI to disclose key information on the AI systems to end users and affected parties, such as the purpose of the systems, source code, and datasets used for the training. Transparency can also be a legal requirement. For example, in relation to processing personal data, data controllers are required to inform data subjects in a transparent manner about the relevant aspects of data processing.	Ethical, Legal
Information asymmetry	Refers to a situation when one party has more information than another one.	Economic
Explainability	The clarity or understandability of a system, process, or concept. For example, AI explainability requires AI outputs to be understandable by a particular audience,	Ethical, Legal

	whether they are developers, deployers, end-users or impacted parties. Explainability can be distinguished from transparency. Transparency merely requires that information is available to people whereas explainability demands that that information is displayed or interpreted in a way in which people can understand. Explainability can be also a legal requirement, for example, the GDPR requires human-legible explanations for AI-based decision-making systems (art. 22 GDPR; Hamon et al., 2022).	
Accountability	The requirement is that one can explain or justify their actions or the outcome of those actions and is subsequently held responsible for those actions or outcomes.	Ethical, Legal
Responsibility	Possessing a duty to handle or control a certain situation or decision. Responsibility is closely related to accountability. However, while accountability is more concerned with a person’s response after a situation has already occurred and is generally backwards-looking, responsibility is generally more focused on the present.	Ethical, Legal
Efficiency	The ability of a person, object, or process to achieve its end goal using only the necessary effort and resources.	Economic
Reliability	The degree to which a person, service, system, or thing can be depended upon and trusted to perform well in a consistent and predictable manner. For example, data reliability speaks to the trustworthiness of a dataset, including the validity, completeness, and accuracy of the data contained within it.	Ethical
Traceability	The capability to follow the development or history of something as well as to find and track it. For example, data traceability is the ability to follow the lifecycle of data or a particular dataset, tracking when and where changes were made to the data.	Technical
Auditability	Accounts, results, or research that can readily be verified or checked by an ‘auditor.’ Auditability depends on the transparency and the level of documentation of the records to be audited.	Ethical, Legal
Data reproducibility	The degree of consistency and accuracy which can be retained when a process is repeated over and over. Reproducibility can be distinguished from replicability as reproducibility generally refers to the same team using the same data to regenerate consistent results.	Technical

	Conversely, replicability involves a new team arriving at the same results using new data.	
Robustness	Strength, sturdiness, health, and low risk of breaking or failing in the face of interference or force. For example, data robustness describes a dataset that can maintain validity whilst withstanding interference from outliers and missing values.	Technical
Bias	The tendency to accord a disproportionate and unreasonable amount of weight to one idea, concept, person, or thing, over another. Data bias exists where some elements of a dataset are overrepresented and overemphasised in a manner that is incommensurate with the statistical weight or value of those elements. This can be the result of social biases towards certain groups of people who are often discriminated against or unfairly excluded from datasets.	Ethical
Discrimination	The unfair and unjustifiable treatment of an individual based on who they are. Individuals have a legal right to non-discrimination.	Ethical, Legal
Justice	Fair division of benefits and burdens as well as opportunities and challenges within a group. Thus, whilst justice requires a degree of impartiality, it does not demand that all individuals within a population are treated equally. Rather, justice requires equity which recognises that some individuals may require differential treatment to achieve the same outcome as other individuals due to their background, situation, or personal profile and abilities.	Ethical, Legal
Fairness	Equal, impartial, and non-discriminatory treatment or behaviour. Fairness is often juxtaposed with injustice and thus is associated with individuals receiving treatment that is reasonable and just in the given circumstances.	Ethical, Legal
Diversity	Degree of variety or difference in a given scenario or entity. Diversity within a group is the inclusion of a range of persons from various backgrounds and with different characteristics. Similarly, diversity within a dataset means that a range of different groups is represented in the data.	Ethical
Accessibility	The extent to which individuals or groups in the same situation have equal opportunity to be able to use, reach, obtain, examine, or receive benefits from a system, information, product, or service.	Ethical, Legal

Inclusivity	The incorporation of a diverse range of fields, subjects, or people in a comprehensive and fair manner. Often used to describe the provision of equal access to resources and opportunities for all people.	Ethical
Energy justice	Fair division of the benefits and burdens as well as the opportunities and challenges of the energy sector and its services amongst society.	Ethical
Just Transition	An approach within climate policy plans that involves ensuring that the benefits of a transition to a green economy are equally distributed amongst all of the individuals within that economy.	Ethical
Sustainability	Operating and using resources in a way that ensures that both current and future needs can be met. In this regard, resources refer to the natural resources within the earth's environmental systems, economic resources, and social resources such as human rights protection and basic necessities for current and future generations.	Ethical, Legal
Environmental Impact	Any effect that human activity or otherwise has on the physical environment, including the air, land, and sea. These include negative impacts on the environment such as any contribution to global warming or air pollution, and positive impacts, such as increasing biodiversity.	Ethical
Beneficence	The duty is to maximise any potential benefits and minimise risks or harms.	Ethical
Non-maleficence	The duty not to harm others.	Ethical
Human dignity	Recognition that human beings have inherent worth based on their humanity. Thus, human dignity demands that humans are treated in a way that accords with that worth and may not be deskilled, objectified or instrumentalised. Human dignity is universal; it applies to all human beings and is the foundation (Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU, 2000).	Ethical, Legal
Respect for fundamental rights	Fundamental rights are rights that warrant the highest level of protection such as the right to privacy and freedom from discrimination.	Legal

4 Description and classification of relevant data, data roles of data users and functionalities

The aim of this section is to introduce the different data types that will be used by the DATA CELLAR dataspace, to describe the different types of users of this space, and to explain what kinds of roles these users can assume. This section will be structured in the following way: Firstly, it will clarify the different kinds of data that will be used by DATA CELLAR and categorize them by the level of their sensitivity (low, medium and high). It will also put forward potential harms that could be associated with each kind of data. Secondly, it will define potential users and explain their different data roles according to applicable legal frameworks, thus allowing for a clearer comprehension of the legal requirements and guidelines in sections 5.1 and 6.1. Thirdly, it will briefly describe functionalities that will be developed by the DATA CELLAR project.

4.1 Relevant data types, their description, classification and potential harms

This sub-section will briefly define different types of data and assign to them potential harms and data sensitivity levels using the [Table](#) format proposed below. Before doing so, three types of data sensitivity categories that are important for the data that will be processed by DATA CELLAR are provided, namely:

1. **High risk:** data will be classified as high risk when it is either:
 - a. classified as “special category data” under the GDPR, or
 - b. could lead to the loss of confidentiality, integrity, or availability of data, could have a significant adverse impact on DATA CELLAR’s objectives, or could result in damage/distress to DATA CELLAR users or other individuals.
2. **Medium risk:** data will be classified as such when:
 - a. it is not generally available to the public e.g., is confidential due to the DATA CELLAR’s policy, or
 - b. defined by the GDPR as “personal data”, or
 - c. could lead to the loss of confidentiality, integrity, or availability of data, could have a mildly adverse impact on DATA CELLAR’s objectives, or could result in damage/distress to DATA CELLAR users or other individuals.
3. **Low risk:** data will be classified as such when:
 - a. data can be freely used, reused and redistributed by anyone with no existing local, national or international legal restrictions on access or usage, or
 - b. data is intended for public disclosure, or
 - c. is unlikely to lead to the loss of confidentiality, integrity, or availability of data, low risk of having an adverse impact on DATA CELLAR’s objectives, bearing low risk of damage/distress to DATA CELLAR users or other individuals.³²

³² Based on and slightly adapted from (Georgetown University, n.d.; University of Glasgow, 2018; University of Stanford, n.d.)

Table 3: Relevant types of data, their potential harms and sensitivity

Data type	Explanation	Examples	Potential harms	Data sensitivity level
Personal data	Data relating to an identified or identifiable individual [art.4(1) GDPR].	Name, email addresses, financial information, gender.	Personal data disclosure, financial loss.	Medium-high
Non-personal data	Data that does not relate to an identifiable individual and cannot be traced back to a natural person.	Commercially sensitive information, data policy, anonymised data, aggregated statistics.	Loss of IP or trade secrets, negative impact on competition.	Low- High (depending on the adverse impact on DATA CELLAR's objectives, users, individuals and other individuals)
Energy data	Data consisting of meter, market and grid data (THEMA, 2017, p. 21).	User and contract data, injected electrical energy data, withdrawn electrical data, weather and environmental data, flexibility data, electrical price data, real-time data, known outages.	Personal data disclosure, negative impact of energy systems and infrastructure.	Low-High (depending on the adverse impact on DATA CELLAR's objectives, users, and other individuals).

4.2 Data users' description and explanation of their different roles

When creating dataspace relevant stakeholders need to be properly represented in order to enable energy data sharing and exchange (Nagel & Lycklama, 2022, p. 81). DATA CELLAR's dataspace will be used by a variety of energy stakeholders, for example, energy consumers, energy communities, distribution system operators (DSOs), users of another dataspace, local energy market representatives, and energy services or tool providers (Queiroz, 2022, section 3.3). These users are going to be either natural or legal persons and come from both public and private sectors. Since they will participate in numerous data processing activities, it is necessary to clarify their data roles stemming from applicable legislative frameworks. In this context, a data user of the DATA CELLAR dataspace could be classified as a:

1. Data intermediary: user that is responsible for the organisation of data sharing and operation of dataspace such as data brokers, marketplace operators and facilitators [art.2 (11) DGA].
2. Data subject: refers to an "identified or identifiable natural person" [art.4(10) GDPR, art.2(7) DGA].

3. Data controller: “natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data” [art. 2(7) GDPR].
4. Data processor: “natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which processes personal data on behalf of the controller” [art.2(8) GDPR].
5. Recipient: “natural or legal person, public authority, agency or another body, to which the personal data are disclosed, whether a third party or not” [art.2(9) GDPR]. In the case of public bodies, this data role does not apply when they receive personal data as a result of an inquiry that took place in accordance with relevant national or EU law [art.2(9) GDPR].
6. Data recipient: “means a legal or natural person, acting for purposes which are related to that person’s trade, business, craft or profession, other than the user of a product or related service, to whom the data holder makes data available, including a third party following a request by the user to the data holder or in accordance with a legal obligation under Union law or national legislation implementing Union law” [art.2(7) DA].
7. Third party: “natural or legal person, public authority, agency or body other than the data subject, controller, processor and persons who, under the direct authority of the controller or processor, are authorised to process personal data” [art.2(10) GDPR].
8. Data holder: “legal person or a natural person ” who: 1) is not a data subject but “has the right to grant access to or to share certain personal data or non-personal data” [art.2 (8) DGA] or 2) “has the right or obligation (...), or in the case of non-personal data and through control of the technical design of the product and related services, the ability, to make available certain data available” [art.2(6) DA].
9. Data user: “natural or legal person who has lawful access to certain personal or non-personal data and has the right, (...) in the case of personal data, to use that data for commercial or non-commercial purposes” [art. 2(9) DGA].
10. User: “natural or legal person that owns, rents or leases a product or receives a services” [art. 2(5) DA].

4.3 Description of functionalities

DATA CELLAR will be fueled by several components and tools, namely, a Decision Support System (DSS), INTEMA (INTEgrated Energy MANagement) and VERIFY (Virtual intEgrated platfoRm on LCA), Digital Twin, Blockchain-based Marketplace with Loyalty and Tokenization Scheme, and AI and ML models, which will provide main services to end-users. Their utilization might raise several legal and ethical issues. Before proceeding with their analysis, this section will briefly introduce the rationale behind these functionalities:

4.3.1 Decision Support System

A Decision Support System (DSS) is a software component that will allow dataspace end-users to better operate their energy system and assets in terms of renewable energy production, vehicle-to-grid possibilities or battery energy storage systems, amongst others (Baka et al., 2023, section 3). This tool will assist end-users, in particular, energy communities, energy consumers, and distribution system operators, in their energy decision-making, and will permit them to maximize their revenues, minimize costs, and provide flexibility to the grid (Baka et al., 2023, section 3).

4.3.2 INTEMA and VERIFY

The operation of DSS will be supported by two tools, namely, the Building Energy Assessment service which will be provided by INTEMA and the Environmental and Economic Assessment service which will be offered by the VERIFY-D tool (Baka et al., 2023, section 3).

INTEMA is an energy analytical tool offered as a web-based application which can create accurate and precise building energy simulations for buildings with active energy systems (production, consumption and storage) (Apostolopoulos et al., 2023, p. 5). This tool will allow end-users to make approximations about energy-related activities and enable them to compare different energy technologies allowing for better energy management, building retrofitting and/or operation (Baka et al., 2023, section 3).

VERIFY-D is grounded in quantitative methodologies and utilises algorithms that can classify, measure, and analyse life cycle assessments and life cycle costing indicators for different energy components and technologies that are relevant and can be connected in buildings (Apostolopoulos et al., 2023, p. 4). It allows for the execution of environmental and economic assessments of buildings and districts using a component-based life cycle approach (Apostolopoulos et al., 2023, p. 4), enabling end-users to better and more accurately estimate the environmental and economic impact of single or multiple buildings, which can incentivise them to set up an energy community (Baka et al., 2023, section 3).

4.3.3 Digital Twin

Digital Twin is an ICT platform for data-driven models which is a digital mirror of physical systems. In the case of DATA CELLAR, it will be used for the virtual representation of low and/or medium electricity grids (Baka et al., 2023, section 3). It will also empower users to better optimise the use of their energy resources, contribute to local energy saving and allows them to more efficiently engage in flexibility services (Baka et al., 2023, section 3). This tool interacts with DSS, namely, by providing operational data to DSS, which will allow for long-term multi-vector planning through dynamic and flexible simulations (Baka et al., 2023, section 3).

4.3.4 Marketplace with Loyalty platform and Tokenisation

DATA CELLAR will also have an open blockchain-based marketplace on which dataspace users will be able to share and sell their energy data, AI models, and services from previously described tools. This will ultimately contribute to the data economy, research in the energy sector and the creation of new markets. DATA CELLAR's marketplace will be supported by a loyalty platform and tokenisation scheme which will incentivise users to use DATA CELLAR marketplace by providing them with rewards, personalized support, discounts and special offers (Baka et al., 2023, section 3).

4.3.5 AI and ML Models

The AI Deployment Platform will gather the AI and ML models as well as empower end-users to deploy their own models and make them available in the Marketplace. In this context, dataspace users will be able to develop AI models tailor-made to their needs, sharing them on the Marketplace later on and benefiting from a tokenization scheme (Baka et al., 2023, section 3).

5 Data processing

This section aims to describe the legal and ethical requirements that need to be fulfilled during data processing, to elaborate on the risks associated with data processing, and provide guidelines that could mitigate the risks and fulfil the requirements. This section will be structured accordingly.³³

5.1 Legal Requirements for data processing

This sub-section will be divided into two sections: Section 5.1.1 will summarise data processing requirements found in data protection law and energy law. Section 5.1.2 will put forward conditions that apply to data processing and assign risks and guidelines connected to them. Section 5.1.1 summarises all the relevant requirements found in the applicable legislative framework. It serves as a complementary part to Section 5.1.2 which refers to relevant legal conditions, potential risks and factors that could affect their fulfilment and guidelines to address them.

5.1.1 Legal Requirements

In line with the applicable legislative frameworks discussed in section 2.1, the following table will explain and summarise data protection law requirements (PLR) and energy law requirements (ELR). These requirements will be numbered PLR 1, PLR2 and so on, which will allow the reader to match them with corresponding guidelines, protocols, and recommendations for implementation which will be labelled as PRL1.1,1.2, 2.1 etc.

³³ The structure of this section together with section 6 will be loosely based on and adapted from Iannone et al., 2021.

5.1.1.1 Data protection law

Table 4: Legal requirements for data processing found in data protection law³⁴

Legal framework	Requirement	Explanation
GDPR	Lawfulness (PLR 1)	Data processing requires a legal basis [art. 5 1(a) and 6 GDPR; De Terwangne, 2020, p. 314; Kotschy, 2020, p. 325]. This also relates to international data transfers and data access are a form of data processing (Kuner, 2020, pp. 755, 765). In this context, both personal data transfer and data access to data controllers and processors in third country or international organizations need to comply with the GDPR provisions (art. 44 GDPR; Kuner, 2020, p. 757). Furthermore, such transfer or data access needs to be based on an appropriate legal basis either a) adequacy decision (art. 45 GDPR), b) appropriate safeguards (Art. 46 GDPR) or c) applicable derogations (art. 49 GDPR). It is also important have a contract with a third party that processes data in a third country, which needs to include a standard contract clause (European Commission, 2021). There are three different modules of such clause (European Commission, 2021), thus, at the project level, we should determine which one will be the most appropriate.
	Fairness and transparency (PLR 2)	Data processing should be fair and transparent. In this context, relevant data should be attained lawfully and using lawful means (De Terwangne, 2020, p. 314). Furthermore, the data subject must be informed about all important aspects relating to data processing [art. 5 1(a) and art. 12-14 GDPR; De Terwangne, 2020, pp. 314-315].
	Purpose limitation (PLR 3)	Data processing activities must have a clear, well-defined and legitimate purpose [art. 5 1(b) GDPR; De Terwangne, 2020, p. 315].

³⁴ This tables was based on and adapted from Bygrave, 2020; De Terwangne, 2020; Directorate General for Research and Innovation, 2022; European Commission, 2021; Iannone et al., 2021; Kotschy, 2020; Krämer et al., 2023; Kuner, 2020; Richter, 2023; Von Ditfurth & Lienemann, 2022.

Legal framework	Requirement	Explanation
	Data minimisation (PLR 4)	Data processing needs to be “adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary for relation to the purposes for which they are processed” [art. 5 1(c) GDPR; De Terwangne, 2020, p. 317].
	Storage limitation (PLR 5)	Data storage must be restricted in both time and amount of relevant data [art. 5 1(e) GDPR; De Terwangne, 2020, p. 318].
	Accuracy (PLR 6)	Data that is processed needs to be correct and each inaccuracy should be timely adjusted [art. 5 1(d) GDPR; De Terwangne, 2020, p. 317].
	Integrity and confidentiality (PLR 7)	Data processing needs to be safe and safeguard “against unauthorised or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction or damage, using appropriate technical or organisational measures” [art. 5 1(f) GDPR; De Terwangne, 2020, p. 318].
	Accountability (PLR 8)	Data controllers are required to demonstrate compliance with data processing principles described above [art. 5 (2); for more details see art.5, 12, 24-28, 30-35 GDPR; Bygrave, 2020, p. 573; De Terwangne, 2020, pp. 318-319].
	Respectful and appropriate technical, legal and organizational measures and procedures for data subject rights (PLR 9)	It is important to ensure that technical and organizational measures, as well as procedures, enable the exercise of data subjects' rights, namely, the right to information (arts. 13, 14 GDPR), the right to access (art. 15 GDPR), the right of rectification [art. 5 (1d), 16 GDPR], the right to erasure (art. 17 GDPR), the right to restrict processing (art. 18 GDPR), the right of data portability (art. 20 GDPR), the right to object to certain processing (art. 21 GDPR), the rights concerning automated decision making and profiling (art. 22 GDPR) (Iannone et al., 2021, p. 12).
	Data protection by design and by default (PLR 10)	The main rationale behind this requirement is to ensure that both the design and development of the dataspace will comply with data protection principles and that they will be effectively incorporated into the designed

Legal framework	Requirement	Explanation
		<p>dataspace (Bygrave, 2020, p. 573). Furthermore, following the privacy by default principle, data controllers are required to employ and implement technical and organisational mechanisms and safeguards that will ensure that, by default, personal data is processed lawfully, fairly and transparently and following purpose limitation requirement (Bygrave, 2020, p. 577). Additionally, it ensures processing is in line with data minimisation, storage limitation, data integrity and confidentiality as well as the accountability principle (art. 25 GDPR; Bygrave, 2020, p. 577).</p>
ePD	Security (PLR 11)	<p>Service providers must implement organizational and technical measures as well as procedures that will safeguard the security of electronic communications [art.4(1) ePD]. They should “ensure a level of security appropriate to the risk presented” [art.4(1) ePD]. They should at least: a) ensure access to personal data is granted only to authorized people for instance by using specific types of software or encryption technologies [rec. 20 ePD; art.4(1a) ePD]; b) protect against accidental or unlawful disclosure of personal data; c) implement suitable a security policy [art.4(1)(a) ePD]; d) inform users of the services about risks relating to the security of the network [art.4(1a) and (2) ePD] and e) notify data protection authority and users in case of data breaches (art.4(3) ePD).</p>
	Confidentiality (PLR 12)	<p>It is required to ensure the secrecy of communications and traffic data related to them, meaning, that they could not be disclosed, recorded and stored without the consent of the user and “having been provided with clear and comprehensive information” [art.5(1) and (3) ePD] unless they are proof or “evidence of a commercial transaction or any other business communication” [art. 5(10 and (2) ePD]. In this context, it is necessary to</p>

Legal framework	Requirement	Explanation
		implement measures against unauthorized access (rec. 21, 23 and art. 5(3) ePD).
	Prohibition of storage (PLR 13)	There is a prohibition of storage and processing of communications as well as related traffic data unless user consent is given [rec. 22 and art.5(1) ePD]. This prohibition is “not intended to prohibit any automatic, intermediate, and transient storage of this information in so far as this takes place for the sole purpose of carrying out the transmission in the electronic communications network and provided that the information is not stored for any period longer than is necessary for the transmission and traffic management purposes and that during the period of storage, the confidentiality remains guaranteed” (rec.22 eDP).
	Data protection (PLR 14)	Processing of personal data should take place under European data protection rules (rec. 17 and 32 ePD).
ePR	Prohibition of storage (PLR 15)	Data processing activities related to data stored in and related to end-users' terminal equipment and the collection of information produced by terminal equipment is prohibited unless “(a) it is necessary for the sole purpose of carrying out the transmission of an electronic communication over an electronic communications network; or (b) the end-user has given his or her consent; or (c) it is necessary for providing an information society service requested by the end-user; or (d) if it is necessary for web audience measuring, provided that such measurement is carried out by the provider of the information society service requested by the end-user” [art. 8(1) ePR]. Collecting data produced by terminal equipment is prohibited unless “(a) it is done exclusively in order to, for the time necessary for, and for the purpose of establishing a connection; or (b) a clear and prominent notice is displayed informing of, at least, the modalities of the collection, its purpose, the

Legal framework	Requirement	Explanation
		person responsible for it and the other information required under Article 13 of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 where personal data are collected, as well as any measure the end-user of the terminal equipment can take to stop or minimise the collection.” [art.8(2) ePR].
	Confidentiality of the communications (PRL 16)	Data relating to electronic communications must be treated as confidential (rec. 15 and art.5 ePR).
	Data protection (PLR 17)	Processing data from electronic communications should comply with the principles of data protection found in the GDPR (rec. 17-18, art. 8-9 ePR), such as requirements for consent (rec. 18, 24 ePR) as well as data protection by default and design (rec.23 ePR). In this context, if there is a high risk of infringement of data subjects' rights and fundamental rights, it is necessary to perform a data protection impact assessment (DPIA), which needs to be carried out per Articles 35 and 36 of GDPR (rec.17 ePR).
DGA	Promotion of competition (PLR 18)	To safeguard and promote competition, there is a prohibition on exclusive arrangements, which prohibits public sector entities that disclose data for reuse from entering into exclusive arrangements (art. 4 and rec. 13-14 DGA). If such arrangements are possible due to the existence of national and EU law that allows it, they should be subject to procedural [art. 4(2) and (3) DGA], temporal [art. 4(4) DGA], and transparency and non-discrimination requirements [art. 4(5) DGA]. Furthermore, in the case of the data intermediation services, their providers are obligated to implement procedures aiming at deterrence of fraudulent or abusive practices [art. 12(g) DGA] (Richter, 2023, p. 664; Von Ditfurth & Lienemann, 2022, p. 287).
	Fairness, transparency, neutrality and non-discrimination (PLR 19)	Requirements for data re-use and procedures for data intermediation services must be fair, transparent, non-discriminatory, proportional, and objectively justified [art. 5(2) and 12(f) DGA] (Richter, 2023, p. 463; Von

Legal framework	Requirement	Explanation
		Ditfurth & Lienemann, 2022, pp. 279, 287). Furthermore, there is a requirement of neutrality relating to the data intermediation services which states that disintermediation services should be provided by a separate legal person [rec. 33 and art.12(a) DGA] (Richter, 2023, p. 463; Von Ditfurth & Lienemann, 2022, p. 284). To ensure their impartiality, data intermediaries cannot alter the data format used by data holders themselves [art.12(a) DGA] (Richter, 2023, p. 463; Von Ditfurth & Lienemann, 2022, p. 283). Conditions for the re-use of data by public bodies should published and compliant with national laws [art.5(1) DGA].
	Interoperability(PLR 20)	Data should be interoperable. In this context, data intermediation services providers must “take appropriate measures to ensure interoperability with other data intermediation services” [art.12(i) DGA](Richter, 2023, p. 664; Von Ditfurth & Lienemann, 2022, p. 279), for example utilising open standards used [art.12(i) DGA] (Richter, 2023, p. 664; Von Ditfurth & Lienemann, 2022, p. 289) or by converting “the data into specific formats only to enhance interoperability within and across sectors or if requested by the data user or where mandated by Union law or to ensure harmonisation with international or European data standards” [art.12(d) DGA] (Richter, 2023, p. 664; Von Ditfurth & Lienemann, 2022, p. 285)].
	Confidentiality(PLR 21)	Ensure that data subject to confidentiality regulations under both national and European law remains confidential [art. 5(8) DGA] (Directorate General for Research and Innovation, 2022, p. 27).
	Incorporation of technical, organisational and legal safeguards (PLR 22)	To facilitate data re-use and data intermediation, it is necessary to employ institutional, technical and organisational requirements, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For data intermediation services; the services should be provided through a separate entity [art.12(a) DGA; Richter, 2023, p. 463; Von

Legal framework	Requirement	Explanation
		<p>Ditfurth & Lienemann, 2022, p. 284]; their commercial terms cannot be “dependent upon whether the data holder or data user uses other services provided by the same data intermediation services provider or by a related entity” [art.12(b) DGA; Richter, 2023, p. 664; Von Ditfurth & Lienemann, 2022, p. 284]; usage of unchanged data format obtained from data holder unless different format would enhance interoperability [art.12(d) DGA; Richter, 2023, p. 664; Von Ditfurth & Lienemann, 2022, p. 285]; services providers should employ measures to safeguard against abusive and unlawful practices [Art. 12(g) DGA; Richter, 2023, p. 664; Von Ditfurth & Lienemann, 2022, p. 287]; services providers ensure fairness, transparency and non-discrimination in relation to their access procedures and their commercial conditions [Art. 12(f) DGA; Richter, 2023, p. 663; Von Ditfurth & Lienemann, 2022, p. 286]; services providers when providing their services to data subjects must act in their best interest “by informing and, where appropriate, advising data subjects in a concise, transparent, intelligible and easily accessible manner about intended data uses by data users and standard terms and conditions attached to such uses before data subjects give consent” [Art. 12(m) DGA; Richter, 2023, p. 664].</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For re-use of relevant data: public bodies must ensure fairness, transparency and non-discrimination in relation to their data re-use conditions [art.5(2) DGA]; they are required to ensure that the relevant data is protected using appropriate security precautions, including, mechanisms aimed at prevention of re-identification [art.5(3) abd (5) DGA](Directorate General for Research and Innovation, 2022, pp. 26–27). - When data is held by public sector bodies, international transfers and access can only take place when appropriate safeguards, including,

Legal framework	Requirement	Explanation
		<p>technical, legal and organisational measures, are incorporated [art.31(1) DGA]. These measures should:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Prohibit transfer and data access in case of “conflict with Union law or the national law” [art. 31(1) DGA]. ○ Require legal basis for a) data processing activity and b) data transfer or access [art. 5(9) DGA; rec. 22, art. 31(2) and (3) DGA]. ○ Be carried out under sectoral, namely, energy laws when they impose stricter conditions [rec. 24 DGA]. ○ Impose contractual obligations on data re-users in third countries to ensure that they adhere to EU data protection standards and requirements [rec.21 DGA]. ○ Ensure “the availability of enforceable rights and effective legal remedies” [rec. 21 DGA] and the information about “whose rights and interests may be affected by that intention, purpose and the appropriate safeguards” [art. 5(9) and 31(5) DGA]. ○ Respect the nature of data, which might require additional technical and security measures [art.5 (8), (10), (12) and (13) DGA; Chapter V GDPR] (Directorate General for Research and Innovation, 2022, pp. 26-27).
	Reasonable compensation and fees (PLR 23)	Public bodies can impose charges for data re-use, which need to be “transparent, non-discriminatory, proportionate, and objectively justified and shall not restrict competition” [art.6(2) DGA]. In case of data re-use for non-commercial purposes, public bodies should promote data reuse to be free of charge [art. 6(4) and rec. 20 DGA].
	Respect and procedures for data rights (PLR 24)	It is important to ensure the existence of technical and organizational measures as well as procedures to enable the exercise of data rights,

Legal framework	Requirement	Explanation
		namely, rights to use, and re-use data and the right to use data intermediation services and data subject rights [art.1(3), 10(b) and 12(h) DGA] (Richter, 2023, p. 464; Von Ditfurth & Lienemann, 2022, p. 290). These procedures must be fair, “non-discriminatory, transparent, proportionate and objectively justified” [art. 5(2) and 12(f) DGA] (Directorate General for Research and Innovation, 2022, p. 26; Richter, 2023, p. 463; Von Ditfurth & Lienemann, 2022, pp. 279, 287).
	Compliance with other legal frameworks (PLR 25)	In case of the re-use of data, it is also necessary to achieve compliance with other legal frameworks, namely for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In intellectual property law, for example, it might be necessary to acquire permission or authorisation from the holder of data [art.5(7) DGA], - Database law, namely DGA, restricts the exercise of the sui generis right when it would constrain data re-use envisioned by the DGA [art.5(7) DGA] (Directorate General for Research and Innovation, 2022, pp. 26–27).
	Personal data protection (PLR 26)	Processing data should comply with the principles of data protection found in the GDPR (rec. 4 DGA).
DA	Lawfulness (PLR 27)	Data processing, namely, data use and re-use is possible for “any lawful purpose” (rec. 28, art. 4 DA; Krämer et al., 2023, p. 15). In the case of personal data, when a data user cannot be classified as a data subject, then data processing activity must be justified by one of legal bases found in art. 6 (1) GDPR must apply [art. 4(5) and 5(6) DA; Krämer et al., 2023, p. 15]. To use non-personal, data holders must sign a contract [art. 4(6) DA; Krämer et al., 2023, p. 15], which needs to be “fair, reasonable and non-discriminatory terms” and provided “in a transparent manner” [art. 8(1) DA and 4(6) DA; Krämer et al., 2023, p. 46; for more contract requirement see art. 13 DA].

Legal framework	Requirement	Explanation
	Transparency (PLR 28)	Prior to a contract for either the purchase, rent or lease of a product or a related service, certain transparency obligations need to be fulfilled. In particular, it is necessary to inform potential data users, in a clear and accessible format, about: a) type and amount of data; b) information about whether data will be generated in real-time and continuously; c) information about data access; d) who will be re-use data and for which purpose; e) who is data holder; f) how to quickly and effectively communicate with data holder; g) how to make a request data sharing with a third-party; (h) how user can use his or her right to complain [art.3(2) DA and rec. 24; Krämer et al., 2023, p. 40].
	No harm principles (PLR 29)	Third parties who are receiving data at the request of the user, should not cause harm. They should: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - delete personal data when “they are not necessary for fulfilling the agreed purpose” [art.6(1) DA] (Krämer et al., 2023, p. 46). - not “coerce, deceive or manipulate the user in any way” [art.6(2a) DA] (Krämer et al., 2023, p. 46). - not use the data for the profiling of natural persons [art.6(2b) DA] (Krämer et al., 2023, p. 46). - should not disclose data to another third party, “in raw, aggregated or derived form” [art.6(2c and d) DA] (Krämer et al., 2023, p. 46). - not “use the data develop a product that competes with the product from which the accessed data originate or share the data with another third party for that purpose” [art.6(2e) DA] (Krämer et al., 2023, p. 46). - “prevent the user, including through contractual commitments, from making the data it receives available to other parties” [art.6(2f) DA] (Krämer et al., 2023, p. 46).

Legal framework	Requirement	Explanation
	Accessible, easy and secure data access (PLR 30)	Data produced by the utilisation of products or related services should be accessible, namely “provided, in such a manner that data generated by their use are, by default, easily, securely and, where relevant and appropriate, directly accessible to the user” [art.3(1) DA; Krämer et al., 2023, p. 15].
	Respect for data rights (PLR 31)	DA provides natural and legal persons with a) the right to access data, b) the right to use data that is produced by the usage of products or related services (art. 4 DA) and c) the right to share data with third parties (art. 5 DA). In both cases, to enable the exercise of these rights, it is necessary to incorporate legal, technical and organisational measures. For example, data holders need to “make available to the user the data generated by its use of a product or related service without undue delay, free of charge and, where applicable, continuously and in real-time” [art. 4(1) and 5(1) DA; Krämer et al., 2023, p. 38]. Additionally, concerning the right to share data with third parties, it is also important to ensure the technical feasibility of third-party access (rec. 31 and art. 5 DA; Krämer et al., 2023, p. 15). In the data sharing contract with the third party, it is necessary to ensure that the user rights are contractually enforced [art. 8(2) DA] as well as that contract terms are not unfair and biased [art. 8(3) DA] (Krämer et al., 2023, p. 46).
	Data protection (PLR 32)	DA requires compliance with GDPR when personal data is processed [rec. 8, 24, 30-31, 34, 64, art.1(3), 4(2) and (5) and 5(3) and (6) DA].
	Right to compensation (PLR 33)	Data holders are eligible for compensation in the case when they are required to make data available under national or European law or relevant provisions of DA [rec. 64 and art.8(1), 12(1) and 20(2) DA; Krämer et al., 2023, p. 16].
	Confidentiality (PLR 34)	Confidential data must remain confidential unless “they are strictly necessary to fulfil the purpose agreed between the user and the third party

Legal framework	Requirement	Explanation
		<p>and all specific necessary measures agreed between the data holder and the third party are taken by the third party to preserve the confidentiality” [art. 5(8) and 4(3) DA] for example in the case of trade secrets (Krämer et al., 2023, p. 23).</p>
	<p>Accessible, fair, reasonable, non-discriminatory and transparent conditions for data access (PLR 35)</p>	<p>Data access “should be based on fair, reasonable, non-discriminatory and transparent conditions to ensure consistency of data sharing practices in the internal market” (rec.38 and art.8 DA; Krämer et al., 2023, p. 46).</p>
	<p>Incorporate appropriate legal, technical and organizational safeguards (PLR 36)</p>	<p>To enable data sharing, it is necessary to incorporate appropriate safeguards (rec. 78 DA). In this regard, it is necessary to ensure that:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data is “by default, easily, securely and, where relevant and appropriate, directly accessible to the user” [art.3(1) DA] (Krämer et al., 2023, p. 15); - Transparency obligations before entering into a contract for the rent, lease or purchase of a product or a related service (for more extensive information see PLR 28); - “The data made available to the third party is as accurate, complete, reliable, relevant and up-to-date as the data the data holder itself may be able or entitled to access from the use of the product or related service” (rec.28 DA) (Krämer et al., 2023, p. 47); - “Any trade secrets or intellectual property rights should be respected in handling the data” (rec.28 DA) (Krämer et al., 2023, p. 23); - The presence of technical infrastructure that is capable of protecting protected data can: “(a) destroy the data made available by the data holder and any copies thereof; (b) end the production, offering, placing on the market or use of goods, derivative data or services produced based on knowledge obtained through such data, or the importation, export or storage of infringing goods for those purposes, and destroy any

Legal framework	Requirement	Explanation
		infringing goods” in the case when data recipient provided intentionally erroneous information [art.11(2) DA].
	Interoperability (PLR 36)	<p>Ensure interoperability of data, data sharing mechanisms and services. In particular:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dataspace operators are required to: a) adequately elaborate on “the dataset content, use restrictions, licences, data collection methodology, data quality and uncertainty” [art. 28(1a) DA]; b) describe consistently and publish information about “the data structures, data formats, vocabularies, classification schemes, taxonomies and code lists shall be described in a publicly available and consistent manner” [art. 28(1b) DA]; c) have the technical means to access the data need to be “sufficiently described to enable automatic access and transmission of data between parties, including continuously or in real-time in a machine-readable format” [art. 28(1c) DA]; d) smart contract needs to be interoperable within their activities and services [art. 28(1d) DA] (Krämer et al., 2023, p. 30). - For data processing interoperability specifications and standards should employed to help to enable: a) interoperability between different data processing services [art.29(1a) DA]; b) data portability [art.29(1b) DA]; (c) where technically feasible it would ensure functional equivalence between “different data processing services that cover the same service type” [art.29(1c) DA] (Krämer et al., 2023, pp. 86-87).
	Reasonable compensation (PLR 37)	Data holders are eligible for reasonable compensation to “be met by third parties, but not by the user, for any cost incurred in providing direct access to the data generated by the user’s product” [rec. 31 and art.9 DA; Krämer et al., 2023, p. 16].

Legal framework	Requirement	Explanation
	Effective switching between data providers (PLR 38)	It is necessary to remove commercial, technical, contractual and organisational obstacles to effective switching between providers of data processing services [art. 23 (1) DA]. In consequence, it must be possible to: a) terminate the contractual agreement relating to service within 30 calendar days; b) enter into a contract with a different service provider; c) move data, applications, etc. to another service provider; d) preserve the same level of “functional equivalence of the service in the IT-eco-system of the different provider or providers” [art.23(1) DA] (Krämer et al., 2023, p. 88).
WAD	Perceivability (PLR 39)	“Information and user interface components must be presentable to users in ways they can perceive” (rec.37 art. 4 WAD).
	Operability (PLR 40)	“User interface components and navigation must be operable” (rec.37 art. 4 WAD).
	Understandability (PLR 41)	“Information and the operation of the user interface must be understandable” (rec.37 art 4 WAD).
	Robustness (PLR 42)	“Content must be robust enough to be interpreted reliably by a wide variety of user agents, including assistive technologies” (rec.37 art. 4 WAD).
FFNPD	Free movement of non-personal data (PLR 43)	There is no requirement on where non-personal data should be stored (rec.10 and art. 4 FFNPD).
ODD	Transparency (PLR 44)	Requirements for the re-use of documents owned by public sector bodies should be clear and publicly available for the potential re-users (rec. 41 and art. 7 ODD) (Directorate General for Research and Innovation, 2022, p. 24).
	Promotion of competition (PLR 45)	Public documents should be available, free of charge where possible, to all interested parties to foster competition and ensure that all market players have access to the same information (rec. 36 and 47, art.6 ODD) (Directorate General for Research and Innovation, 2022, p. 24). Therefore, third parties should not be granted exclusive rights to public documents except where

Legal framework	Requirement	Explanation
		"exclusive right is necessary for the provision of a service in the public interest" [art.12(2) ODD] (Directorate General for Research and Innovation, 2022, p. 15).
	FAIR (PLR 46)	Data should be easily "findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable" [rec. 46, art. 11(1), 5 and 8 ODD] (Directorate General for Research and Innovation, 2022, pp. 14-15, 24). In this context, where appropriate, the position of people with disabilities should be considered and accounted for (rec. 43 and 71 ODD). Concerning interoperability, data should be a) "available through an open and machine-readable format" (rec. 34 and 35 ODD); and b) "suitable APIs and, where relevant, as a bulk download" (rec.32 ODD) (Directorate General for Research and Innovation, 2022, p. 15).
	Data protection (PLR 47)	Personal data must be processed in compliance with GDPR (rec.52-53 ODD).

5.1.1.2 Energy law

Table 5: Legal requirements for energy data found in energy law³⁵

Legal framework	Requirement	Explanation
EMD	Lawfulness (ELR 1)	Processing of energy data should be carried out under relevant European and national legal frameworks [art.3(4) and (5) EMD].
	Promotion of competition (ELR 2)	Member States should create a level playing field and promote fair competition in the energy market. In particular, they are required to ensure "transparent, proportionate and non-discriminatory rules, fees and treatment, in particular with respect to (...) access to data" [rec. 12-13, art. 3(4) and 13 EMD].

³⁵ This tables was based on and adapted from Annex included in García Mangas et al., 2023 as well as Kallle, 2019. The latter source was used in relation to legal requirements which are put forward by EMD.

Legal framework	Requirement	Explanation
	Transparency (ELR 3)	Member States are obligated to ensure transparency, namely, the availability of information on amongst other data access, energy data exchange and data rights [art.3, 20 and 23 EMD].
	Non-discrimination and neutrality (ELR 4)	It is important to ensure equal and non-discriminatory access to data for all eligible parties [art. 3(4), 13, 17 and 34 EMD]
	Interoperability(ELR 5)	It is necessary to ensure compatibility between different technical means to access data, communication interfaces and data formats that are utilised by different national energy markets [art. 19(3), 20, and 24 EMD].
	Data protection (ELR 6)	Energy data of a personal nature should be processed under data protection laws such as GDPR [rec. 57 and art. 23 EMD].
IR	Lawfulness (ELR7)	Data processing, namely, sharing and using metering and consumption data (e.g. validated historical and non-validated near-real-time metering and consumption data) is possible when permission, namely, “the authorisation given by a final customer for an eligible party based on a contractual agreement” [art.2(8) IR], is given by the energy consumer to whom such data belongs (rec. 3 IR).
	Timely, simple, transparent and secure data access (ELR 8)	Data access should be granted “in a timely, simple and secure manner” (rec.3 IR). It is necessary to guarantee that final customers “(i) can access their validated metering and consumption data; (ii) can make it available to eligible parties; and (iii) receive it in a structured, commonly used, machine-readable and interoperable format” [art. 4(2 and 3) and art. 5(1b) IR]
	Transparency (ELR 9)	Data access providers are required to publish through an online interface by; a) applicable data access procedures; and b) provide the processes and measures that enable “access, without unnecessary delay, their historical metering and consumption data” to final customers [art. 7 (1) IR]. Furthermore, they are also obliged to record log information and “make it

Legal framework	Requirement	Explanation
		available, free of charge, without unnecessary delay, whenever a final customer requests access” [art. 7(2) IR].
	Interoperability (ELR 10)	It is important to ensure compatibility with the reference model set by IR [art. 3, 4 and 9 and rec. 1-2, 6-7 IR].
	Non-discrimination (ELR 11)	Data access should be based on non-discriminatory and neutral conditions and be granted to all eligible parties (art. 5 IR).

5.1.2 Potential risks and guidelines to address them

This sub-section will build on the requirements described in the preceding sub-section. In particular, it will identify and assign risks and potential to the previously identified legal requirements and relevant legal frameworks as well as put forward guidelines and protocols to address them. Furthermore, it will provide an impact and probability score for each of the risks. Each of the described guidelines, protocols and recommendations for implementation are numbered as PLR1.1, PLR1.2 and can be easily matched with legal requirements described in section 5.1.2 which are referred to as PLR 1, PLR2 etc.

Table 6 Relevant risks and guidelines for their mitigation³⁶

LR	Relevant framework	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score ³⁷	Probability score
All	All	The inability to distinguish between personal and non-personal data and public and private data that will be available via DATA CELLAR’s dataspace or used by its functionalities will make it challenging to determine applicable legislative	DATA CELLAR should clearly define what and which data is available via DATA CELLAR dataspace	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DATA CELLAR should document data which will be available via its dataspace or its functionalities and for which data processing activity. DATA CELLAR should also classify this data according to its nature as either personal, non-personal or 	High	Medium

³⁶ This table was created based on the previous Table and AEPD, 2023; Iannone et al., 2021.

³⁷ The impact score refers to the impact of the risk when and where it materialises.

LR	Relevant framework	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score 37	Probability score
		framework and conditions that need to be fulfilled per different types of relevant data.	or used by its functionalities	<p>mixed data. In this context, the distinction should also be made between private and public sector data.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The foregoing will help to determine which legal conditions are applicable and which measures should be used to safeguard different types of relevant data. It could help both DATA CELLAR to develop an accurate data policy as well as could be shared with dataspace users to help them understand what, which type of data and why this data will be processed by DATA CELLAR's dataspace. 		
All	All	There is a disparity between data roles/ data governance roles described in the IDAS and GAIX as well as data roles found in the DGA or DA (Hilberg, 2023). This could raise questions about when and who will be responsible and accountable for the operation of DATA CELLAR's	DATA CELLAR should have a data policy that clearly explains different roles that could be assumed by different dataspace participants and	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DATA CELLAR should create a comprehensive data policy which clearly describes different data roles as well as define their rights, obligations and responsibilities (AEPD, 2023, pp. 32-34). 	High	Medium

LR	Relevant framework	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score ³⁷	Probability score
		dataspace and adherence to requirements set by relevant and applicable legal frameworks (Hilberg, 2023).	their legal equivalents.			
All	All	Data processing in a dataspace is very complex which can make it difficult to employ appropriate technical, organisational, and legal measures for data processing activities of DATA CELLAR’s dataspace (AEPD, 2023, p. 2,9, 68–69). ³⁸	To ensure the proper implementation of appropriate technical, organisational, and legal measures for data processing, there is a need for cooperation between project partners to formalize obligations found in applicable legal frameworks.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The partners should collectively create, implement, manage, and monitor adherence to data governance, security, risk management, and data handling policies (AEPD, 2023, pp. 68–69). • DATA CELLAR should ensure that its functionalities will be designed in compliance with data protection by design and default (AEPD, 2023, pp. 35–59). In this context, such functionalities should be designed following the EDPB Guidelines 4/2019 on Article 25 Data Protection by Design and by Default.³⁹ • DATA CELLAR should design an entity or a partner responsible for 	High	High

³⁸A similar point is made in the ethical guidelines for data processing. See ER2.3.

³⁹ EDPB (2019), Guidelines 4/2019 on Article 25 Data Protection by Design and by Default <Guidelines 4/2019 on Article 25 Data Protection by Design and by Default | European Data Protection Board (europa.eu)>accessed 3 October 2023.

LR	Relevant framework	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score 37	Probability score
				checking compliance with applicable legislative frameworks (AEPD, 2023, pp. 61-62).		
All	All	Due to the changes in law, national transpositions and entering into force of new data sharing regulations, there is a possibility that DATA CELLAR data policies might become outdated.	DATA CELLAR's data policies should be reviewed periodically and provisionally to ensure compliance with applicable legislative frameworks.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Periodical review of DATA CELLAR's data policies should be conducted by the Ethics Advisory Board to identify data protection gaps and cater for them. This review process should take place regularly, consider minor data-related incidents such as unauthorized data access, and review minor processes that could have a marginal impact on data protection (AEPD, 2023, pp. 71-72). • Provisional review by DATA CELLAR's Ethics Advisory Board should be conducted in case of a) legislative or regulatory changes, b) organisational changes, and c) data breaches and other major data and cyber vulnerabilities (AEPD, 2023, pp. 71-72). 	Medium	Low

LR	Relevant framework	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score 37	Probability score
All	All	Considering the complex data processing environment, DATA CELLAR might not be able to effectively ensure data traceability or linkability (AEPD, 2023, pp. 80-82). This can negatively impact: data sovereignty, data ownership, data protection, data access control mechanisms, compliance with IP rights, confidentiality, trade secrets protection, and the development of remuneration/monetization/tokenisation schemes for data sharing (AEPD, 2023, pp. 80-82).	DATA CELLAR must be able to track the whole data cycle.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DATA CELLAR should create data access control, authorisation and record-keeping mechanisms capable of tracing the whole data cycle on individual-level users (AEPD, 2023, pp. 80-82). 	Low	Low
PLR 1.1, PLR 10.1, PLR 14.1, PLR 17.1, PLR 26.1, PLR 47.1, ELR 1.1, ELR 7.1	GDPR, ePD, ePR, DGA, DA, ODD, EMD, IR	Data processing under DATA CELLAR might be unlawful or use the wrong legal basis (AEPD, 2023, p. 90; Iannone et al., 2021, p. 15).	DATA CELLAR must ensure that every data processing activity is lawful and/or has a legal basis.	DATA CELLAR should ensure that for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Personal data: every personal data processing activity needs to follow its respective legal basis [see PLR 1.1, ELR 1.1; AEPD, 2023, p. 90]. Additionally, when data controllers choose consent as the legal basis, they should comply with guidelines and recommendations found in Art.29 Data Protection Working 	Medium	Medium

LR	Relevant framework	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score 37	Probability score
				<p>Party's Opinion 15/2011 on the definition of consent.⁴⁰</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Non-personal and validated historical and non-validated near-real-time metering and consumption data: data sharing activities should be preceded by permission from the data holder and final customer respectively and be based on contractual agreement [see PLR 1.1, ELR 1.1]. 		
<p>PLR 2.1, PLR 10.2, PLR 14.2, PLR 17.2, PLR 24.1, PLR 26.2, PLR 27.1, PLR 28.1, PLR 47.2, ELR 3.1, ELR 6.1,</p>	<p>GDPR, ePD, ePR, DGA, DA, ODD, EMD, IR</p>	<p>Data users of DATA CELLAR's dataspace are not properly informed about data processing activities and their data rights (AEPD, 2023, pp. 39-40; Iannone et al., 2021, p. 15).⁴¹</p>	<p>DATA CELLAR should adequately inform data users and data subjects about all relevant aspects of data processing activities as well as their data rights and obligations.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DATA CELLAR should act in accordance with its transparency obligations and inform its data users about important and relevant aspects relating to data processing (AEPD, 2023, pp. 82-83). In this context, when processing personal data, the data controller must comply with Art.29 Data Protection Working Party's 	<p>Medium</p>	<p>Medium</p>

⁴⁰ ARTICLE 29 Data Protection Working Party (2011), Opinion 15/2011 on the definition of consent, 01197/11/EN WP187.

⁴¹ This is also addressed in the ethical guidelines for data processing. See ER1.2.

LR	Relevant framework	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score 37	Probability score
ELR 9.1, ELR 12.1				<p>Guidelines on Transparency under Regulation 2016/679.⁴²</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> DATA CELLAR should ensure that information is provided in an accessible form and clear and intelligible language and where relevant through the online interface (see ERL 9.1). 		
PLR 3.1, PLR 4.1, PLR 10.3, PLR 14.3, PLR 17.3, PLR 26.3, PLR 32.1, PLR 47.3, ELR 6.2, ELR 12.2	GDPR, ePD, ePR, DGA, DA, ODD, EMD, IR	DATA CELLAR or its users might be processing personal data or energy data for different purposes than it was originally intended to (Iannone et al., 2021, p. 15).	DATA CELLAR should determine the purpose of each data processing activity.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DATA CELLAR's data processing activities must have a clearly defined and legitimate purpose, which should be determined explicitly before data processing takes place (AEPD, 2023, pp. 28–29, 89). Furthermore, each new purpose needs to be compatible with the original data purpose of data processing (De Terwangne, 2020, p. 315). Data controllers in DATA CELLARs should follow Art.29 Working Party's Opinion 03/2013 on purpose 	High	Medium

⁴² ARTICLE 29 Data Protection Working Party (2017), Guidelines on transparency under Regulation, 2016/679 17/EN WP260 rev.01.

LR	Relevant framework	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score 37	Probability score
				limitation. ⁴³ They should implement and regularly review technical, organisational, and legal measures to limit data re-purposing for example data encryption, contractual safeguards and data access and authorization procedures that would ensure that data and its re-use is only possible for authorized parties (AEPD, 2023, p. 72). ⁴⁴		
PLR 4.2, PLR 5.1, PLR 10.4, PLR 13.1, PLR 15.1, PLR 26.4, PLR 34.1, PLR 47.4, ELR 6.3, ELR 12.3, PLR	GDPR, ePD, ePR, DGA, DA, ODD, EMD, IR	It might be technically impossible or very hard to erase or rectify incorrect information as well as restrict data procession of personal and energy data placed on DATA CELLAR's blockchain-based marketplace due to its technical characteristics such as immutability and complicated data governance structure (European Parliament, 2019, pp. 72-74, 75). The	DATA CELLAR should ensure that it is technically possible to remove and rectify data from the blockchain.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DATA CELLAR's dataspace must have a technical architecture which is able to correct and rectify incorrect information.⁴⁶ The consortium should consider investigating technological innovations or design choices, for instance: to choose private or federated blockchain (Duarte, 2019, p. 44; Lyons et al., 2018, p. 30); to opt 	High	High

⁴³ ARTICLE 29 Data Protection Working Party (2013), Opinion 03/2013 on purpose limitation, 00569/13/EN WP 203.

⁴⁴ ARTICLE 29 Data Protection Working Party (2013), Opinion 03/2013 on purpose limitation, 00569/13/EN WP 203, 32-33.

⁴⁶ For more extensive information see for instance PLR 35.

LR	Relevant framework	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score 37	Probability score
6.1, 10.5, 14.4, 17.4, 26.5, 32.2, 36.1, 47.5, 6.4, 12.4	PLR, PLR, PLR, PLR, PLR, PLR, PLR, ELR, ELR	foregoing might lead to a situation where personal, highly sensitive/confidential or energy data will be stored on the blockchain in perpetuity (European Parliament, 2019, p. 24). ⁴⁵		for consensus design for deleting a requested block (Wirth & Kolain, 2018); employ smart contract-based solution (Haque et al., 2021, p. 50599); store personal and sensitive data off-chain (Haque et al., 2021, p. 50599; Lyons et al., 2018, p. 30); incorporate blockchain punning (European Parliament, 2019, p. 35; Finck, 2018, p. 27); use chameleon-hashed blockchains (European Parliament, 2019, pp. 34–35; Finck, 2018, p. 31); utilise zero-knowledge proof (European Parliament, 2019, pp. 32–33; Haque et al., 2021, p. 50601); use encryption or hashing (European Parliament, 2019, pp. 29–32); noise adding (European Parliament, 2019, p. 34); and secure multi-party computation (European Parliament, 2019, p. 34; Lyons et al., 2018, p. 23).		

⁴⁵ This is also addressed in the ethical guidelines for data processing. See ER2.2.

LR	Relevant framework	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score 37	Probability score
				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DATA CELLAR should also develop a data retention policy, which will specify a) for how long different types of data will be presented b) where they will be stored, c) why the chosen period and medium of storage is appropriate taking into consideration the purpose of the data processing activity and its security and data risks, and d) describe legal grounds for the retention period (AEPD, 2023, pp. 85, 90). These retention policies should be enforced by operators of dataspace and data controllers, which conduct periodical and provisional compliance checks to ensure that data is not stored for more than it is necessary and to monitor risks related to data storage (AEPD, 2023, p. 85). DATA CELLAR should develop internal procedures for data deletion and make sure where to 		

LR	Relevant framework	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score ³⁷	Probability score
				ensure that data is permanently deleted.		
All	All	Since dataspace are inherently very complex data processing environments, it is likely that DATA CELLAR will not have adequate technical, organisation, security and legal measures to facilitate effective and legally compliant data intermediation services and data sharing which can negatively impact data trust and operation of DATA CELLAR's dataspace (AEPD, 2023, pp. 68-69)	DATA CELLAR should put forward organisational, legal, security-related, and technical measures that ensure data intermediation and data sharing services comply with relevant legal requirements.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To facilitate effective data intermediation and data sharing, DATA CELLAR needs to implement appropriate legal, technical and organisational requirements for data intermediation⁴⁷ re-use of relevant data⁴⁸ and data produced by DATA CELLAR's functionalities.⁴⁹ DATA CELLAR should ensure that throughout the whole data cycle and data handling processes, all trade secrets and intellectual property rights are adequately protected and respected.⁵⁰ In the case when data shared, intermediated or generated by DATA CELLAR's functionalities is personal data, it is also necessary to comply 	Medium	Medium

⁴⁷ For legal requirements that need to satisfied see PLR 22, PLR 20.

⁴⁸ For legal requirements that need to satisfied see PLR 20.

⁴⁹ For legal requirements that need to satisfied see PLR 36.

⁵⁰ For legal requirements that need to satisfied see PLR 36.

LR	Relevant framework	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score 37	Probability score
				<p>with GDPR requirements (AEPD, 2023, sec. V–VI).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data controllers processing personal data are required to implement appropriate technical and organisational measures in compliance line with data protection by design and default [art.5 GDPR]. In this context, the data controller should use and adhere to the best practices and guidelines described in EDPB's Guidelines 4/2019 on Article 25 Data Protection by Design and by Default.⁵¹ 		
<p>PLR 7.1, PLR 10.6, PLR 11.1, PLR 12.1, PLR 15.2, PLR 16.1, PLR 21.1,</p>	<p>GDPR, ePD, ePR, DGA, DA, ODD, EMD, IR</p>	<p>Due to data processing complexity, DATA CELLAR might not be able to guarantee a high level of integrity and confidentiality (Iannone et al., 2021, p. 15). This could give rise to issues such as, amongst others, illicit use of data.</p>	<p>DATA CELLAR should ensure a high level of integrity and confidentiality regarding its dataspace</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DATA CELLAR's dataspace should ensure a high level of integrity and confidentiality (AEPD, 2023, pp. 22–23, 59–60). It should implement technical, legal, and organisational safeguards must be implemented in the form of 	<p>Medium</p>	<p>Low</p>

⁵¹ EDPD (2019), Guidelines 4/2019 on Article 25 Data Protection by Design and by Default <Guidelines 4/2019 on Article 25 Data Protection by Design and by Default | European Data Protection Board (europa.eu)>accessed 3 October 2023.

LR	Relevant framework	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score 37	Probability score
22.1, PLR 30.1, PLR 32.3, PLR 34.2, PLR 47.6, ELR 6.5, ELR 12.5			operation and its functionalities.	policies and systems for authorization and authentication, ICT, data and cyber-security of dataspace, data retention and destruction, as well as risk management (AEPD, 2023, sec. V-VI; for more extensive information see Guidelines on data and cyber-security).		
PLR 10.7, PLR 14.5, PLR 17.5, ELR 6.6, ELR 12.6	GDPR, DGA, DA, EMD, IR	DATA CELLAR and its functionalities might use data that has been not properly anonymised and aggregated leading to the reasonable risk of re-identification of data subjects (AEPD, 2023, pp. 45, 85-86).	DATA CELLAR should ensure that its aggregation and anonymisation measures do not result in the high risk of re-identification of data subjects and at the same time guarantee a sufficient level of data utility for the effective operation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DATA CELLAR anonymisation and aggregation mechanisms need to satisfy the risk-based assessment (rec. 26 GDPR). DATA CELLAR needs to ensure that there is no reasonable risk of re-identification of data subjects. This risk should be evaluated from the perspective of the data controller and third parties while taking into consideration time, technical developments, costs that would need to use re-identify natural person as described in D2.2 of DATA CELLAR project. 	Medium	Medium

LR	Relevant framework	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score 37	Probability score
			of DATA functionalities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DATA CELLAR should publish its anonymisation and aggregation methods in the dataspace (AEPD, 2023, p. 90). While developing these mechanisms, data controllers should adopt best practices and recommendations found in Art. 29 Data Protection Working Party's Opinion 05/2014 on Anonymisation Techniques.⁵² DATA CELLAR should have additional technical and operational measures to prevent re-identification (see Guidelines on data and cyber-security). 		
PLR 2.2, PLR 9.1, PLR 20.1, PLR 14.6, PLR 17.6, PLR 24.2, PLR 32.4,	GDPR, ePD, ePR, DGA, DA, ODD, EMD, IR	Lack of or unclear information on a) how DATA CELLAR's dataspace will work and b) procedure for granting and enabling exercise of data rights which can be negatively impacted by for instance the lack of interoperability resulting in data lock-	DATA CELLAR needs to create a data policy that will clearly outline the rights and obligations of dataspace users. It	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DATA CELLAR should ensure that data users can exercise their data rights and data subjects' rights. In the case of refusal or inability to exercise one or more of these rights, such refusal is communicated to the data user and must be proportionate 	Medium	Medium

⁵² ARTICLE 29 Data Protection Working Party (2014), Opinion 05/2014 on Anonymisation Techniques, 0829/14/EN WP216.

LR	Relevant framework	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score 37	Probability score
33.1, PLR 37.1, PLR 38.1, PLR 47.7, PLR 36.2, ELR 2.1, ELR 3.2, ELR 4.1, ELR 5.1, ELR 6.7, ELR 7.2, ELR 8.1, ELR 9.2, ELR 10.1, ELR 11.1, ELR 12.7		in. This, in turn, can impair the data autonomy and sovereignty of data users of DATA CELLAR's dataspace.	should incorporate organisational, technical, and legal measures that will enable the effective exercise of available data rights.	and objectively justified (AEPD, 2023, p. 83). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> In relation to personal data, DATA CELLAR should adhere to EDPB's Guidelines 01/2022 on data subject rights and Art. 29 Working Party Guidelines on Right to data portability and Automated decision-making and profiling.⁵³ DATA CELLAR should implement legal, technical and organisational measures. DATA CELLAR should remove economic, legal, technical, contractual and organisational impediments to exercise of data rights.⁵⁴ 		
PLR 9.2, PLR 10.8, PLR 14.7,	GDPR, ePD, ePR,	Data processing by DATA CELLAR's dataspace and its functionalities can pose a risk to data rights and	DATA CELLAR should implement measures that will	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DATA CELLAR should perform Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) (AEPD, 2023, p. 64). This 	Medium	Medium

⁵³ EDPB (2023), Guidelines 01/2022 on data subject rights - Right of access < [edpb_guidelines_202201_data_subject_rights_access_v2_en.pdf \(europa.eu\)](https://edpb.europa.eu/edpb/files/2023/10/20231003_guidelines_012022_data_subject_rights_access_v2_en.pdf)> accessed 3 October 2023; ARTICLE 29 Data Protection Working Party (2016), Guidelines on Automated individual decision-making and Profiling for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679, 17/EN WP251rev.01; ARTICLE 29 Data Protection Working Party (2016), Guidelines on the right to data portability, 16/EN WP 242 rev.01.

⁵⁴ For more information see ARTICLE 29 Data Protection Working Party (2016), Guidelines on the right to data portability, 16/EN WP 242 rev.01, 15-16

LR	Relevant framework	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score 37	Probability score
<p>PLR 17.7, PLR 23.1, PLR 26.6, PLR 31.1, PLR 32.5, ELR 6.8, ELR 12.8</p>	<p>DGA, DA, EMD, IR</p>	<p>fundamental freedoms because it could be disproportional to the purpose of data processing or, data users could be involuntarily subjected to the automatic processes or data processing (AEPD, 2023, pp. 62-65). Furthermore, DATA CELLAR’s functionalities (e.g., DSS or Digital Twin functionalities) could be biased and their usage could result in discrimination. The foregoing could be worsened due to storage of data and communications in third countries or overall excessive data collection. Further, the processing of various of different types of data and granularity could also pose a risk to individuals’ data rights and fundamental freedoms (AEPD, 2023, pp. 62-65).</p>	<p>safeguard against high risk to data rights and fundamental rights as well as prevent their violations.</p>	<p>assessment should be carried out in compliance with EDPB’s Data Protection impact assessments High risk processing.⁵⁵</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Furthermore, DATA CELLAR should ensure there is possibility of human intervention in and human oversight of DATA CELLAR’s dataspace and its functionalities (AEPD, 2023, pp. 73, 94). In this context, DATA CELLAR should designate an entity for assessing, mitigating biases and discrimination, and ensuring fairness in the processing (AEPD, 2023, pp. 73, 94). • DATA CELLAR should also have a remedy and reparation system to be able to redress and compensate for re-identification, potential violations of data and fundamental rights (AEPD, 2023, p. 90). 		

⁵⁵ ARTICLE 29 Data Protection Working Party (2017), Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) and determining whether processing is “likely to result in a high risk” for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679, 17/EN WP 248 rev.01.

LR	Relevant framework	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score 37	Probability score
<p>PLR 9.3, PLR 10.9, PLR 14.8, PLR 17.8, PLR 19.1, PLR 30.2, PLR 35.1 PLR 46.1, ELR 2.2, ELR 3.3, ELR 4.2, ELR 5.2, ELR 6.9, ELR 7.3, ELR 8.2, ELR 9.3, ELR 10.2, ELR 11.2, ELR 12.9</p>	<p>GDPR, ePD, ePR, DGA, DA, ODD, EMD, IR</p>	<p>DATA CELLAR could implement discriminatory and unfair procedures for data access and data re-use. Additionally, data itself being may become inaccessible due to commercial, legal, contractual, technical and organisational obstacles.</p>	<p>DATA CELLAR should ensure that data is accessible, and that data access policies and systems are fair, non-discriminatory, and transparent.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DATA CELLAR should design a data access policy as well as incorporate technical and organisational mechanisms which will ensure that data access is granted only to authorized people (AEPD, 2023, pp. 72-73). All DATA CELLAR's procedures for data access should be lawful, fair, non-discriminatory, and transparent. Data access via DATA CELLAR should be arranged "in a timely, simple and secure manner" [rec 13, art. 4(2 and 3) and art.5(1b) IR]. Data available via DATA CELLAR should be easily and directly accessible to data users. In this context, it should also be "findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable" (rec. 46, art. 11(1), 5 and 8 ODD). 	<p>Medium</p>	<p>Medium</p>
<p>PLR 1.2, PLR 10.10, PLR</p>	<p>GDPR, ePD,</p>	<p>Data users of DATA CELLAR's dataspace might be transferred to</p>	<p>DATA CELLAR should prohibit</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DATA CELLAR needs to ensure that all data transfers are lawful, meaning 	<p>High</p>	<p>High</p>

LR	Relevant framework	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score 37	Probability score
14.9, PLR 17.9, PLR 22.2, PLR 26.7, PLR 32.6, PLR 47.8, ELR 6.10, ELR 12.10	EPR, DGA, DA, ODD, EMD, IR	third countries or international organisations which do not have the same level of data protection as warranted by the applicable EU and national law (AEPD, 2023, pp. 87–89).	international access and transfer which could result in conflict with applicable EU and national law unless data protection level of a third country is equivalent to the one found in the EU and national law.	that, firstly, data processing activities have a legal basis and, secondly, that data transfer to a third country or international organisation is based on appropriate legal grounds. ⁵⁶ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> DATA CELLAR should also contractually ensure that the third-party processing data in third country will do so in compliance with requirements set by the EU law, including sectoral law and relevant national law. 		
PLR 22.3, PLR 39.1, PLR 40.1, PLR 41.1, PLR 42.1	DGA, WAD	DATA CELLA's dataspace and its functionalities are not accessible and user-friendly for vulnerable users thus failing to meet legal standards on inclusive design. ⁵⁷	DATA CELLAR should be accessible to all its users.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DATA CELLAR, its dataspace and functionalities needs to be designed and operated in a manner that will ensure that they will be accessible from people with disabilities and other vulnerable users as well as accommodate for their data rights, needs and abilities. 	Medium	Low

⁵⁶ For more extensive information on legal bases see PLR 1 and PLR 22.

⁵⁷A similar point is made in the ethical guidelines for data processing. See ER4.2.

LR	Relevant framework	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score ³⁷	Probability score
<p>PLR 18.1, PLR 22.4, PLR 23.2, PLR 38.2, PLR 43.1, PLR 45.1, ELR 2.3</p>	<p>DA, DGA, ODD, EMD</p>	<p>DATA CELLAR’s operation can harm competition.</p>	<p>DATA CELLAR should take technical, legal, and organisational measures to ensure that its operation is beneficial to competition and to the data economy.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DATA CELLAR should ensure that its operation is beneficial to competition and to the data economy by implementation of legal, technical and technical, and organisational measures aimed at deterrence of anti-competitive actions such as fraudulent or abusive practices, exclusive agreements or other anti-competitive procedures or conducts. 	<p>Medium</p>	<p>Low</p>
<p>PLR 9.4, PLR 20.2, PLR 22.5, PLR 36.3, PLR 46.2, ELR 5.3, ELR 10.3</p>	<p>GDPR, DGA, DA, ODD, EMD, IR</p>	<p>DATA CELLAR might not achieve the required level of data interoperability resulting in the inability to move data from DATA CELLAR’s dataspace to the other. Furthermore, a lack of interoperability could result in non-compliance with data protection laws (AEPD, 2023, pp. 73-74).</p>	<p>DATA CELLAR should ensure the semantical, legal, organisational, and technical interoperability of its dataspace.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DATA CELLAR should implement legal, technical, and organisational measures for interoperability (AEPD, 2023, p. 91).⁵⁸ DATA CELLAR ensures that data can be shared with “organisations under different jurisdictions and frameworks with common legally binding conditions” (NL AI Coalition, 2021, p. 27). 	<p>Medium</p>	<p>Medium</p>

⁵⁸ For more extensive information on interoperability requirements see PLR 20, PLR 36, ELR 5 and ELR 10.

LR	Relevant framework	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score 37	Probability score
PLR 29.1	DA	Third parties to whom data from DATA CELLAR is shared could use this data to cause harm to the DATA CELLAR platform and its users.	DATA CELLAR dataspace and its functionalities should be designed and operated in a manner which will create a safe environment.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DATA CELLAR should have contractual, technical, and organisational measures and procedures that will preclude third parties from causing harm to the DATA CELLAR ecosystem and its users. In this context, DATA CELLAR should implement mechanisms against manipulation, fraud and intimidation, prohibition of data profiling, deterrence of unlawful data disclosure and unlawful anti-competitive practices. 	High	High

5.2 Ethical Requirements for data processing

This subsection will focus on the ethical considerations regarding data processing within the DATA CELLAR project. This includes relevant ethical aspects and issues arising throughout the entire data lifecycle, including data collection, data pre-processing, data usage, access, and sharing, data analysis, and data storage, retention, and repurposing. First, section 5.2.1 will outline the ethical requirements expounded by the HLEG for Trustworthy AI (AI HLEG, 2019), addressing a range of ethical issues including human oversight and agency, privacy and data governance, transparency, diversity, non-discrimination, and fairness, societal and environmental wellbeing, and accountability. An explanation for each of these ethical requirements will be provided as well as an explanation of the specific ethics norms which these requirements are composed of. The final requirement detailed by the Trustworthy AI guidelines, technical robustness and safety, will be addressed in chapter 6 on the ethical aspects of cybersecurity in the DATA CELLAR dataspace.

Then, using the HLEG requirements as the primary analytical framework, the main risks posed by data handling within the DATA CELLAR space will be identified within section 5.2.2. As mentioned in section 3.2, the risks identified, and guidelines formulated within this step will be bolstered using other ethical guidelines as well as partner feedback from the T2.6 Ethics workshop. By integrating feedback received from the T2.6 Ethics workshop within its analysis, this chapter adopts a dialectic approach that corresponds with the “comprehension orientated ethical analysis” recommended by the SIENNA framework (SIENNA, 2022, p.23). This allows this deliverable to build on and contextualise the HLEG’s requirements to the data handling processes within DATA CELLAR. Following this mapping exercise, general ethics guidelines will be formulated to address these risks. Then, based on these guidelines, “practice-specific” protocols and recommendations for implementation will be developed, in line with the SIENNA methodology (SIENNA, 2021). By translating the high-level ethics guidelines into practice-specific recommendations, the protocols and recommendations for implementation will outline exactly why, when, and where the guidelines will be necessary and how they will be operationalised in a practical manner by the consortium.

5.2.1 Ethical requirements

In line with the HLEG, the following table summarises the key ethical requirements for trustworthy AI systems as well as the ethical norms that contribute to their realisation. These include the ethical norms that exist in a similar “value cluster” (van de Poel, 2020, p.46) to the main ethical requirements expounded by the HLEG. Some of these ethical norms are mentioned within the HLEG as subcategories of the ethical requirements whilst others have been extracted from ethical literature review and desk research. The ethical requirements (ER) are numbered as ER1, ER2 and so on. This ensures that the ethical guidelines, protocols, and recommendations for implementation can be easily matched to the corresponding ethical requirement and norms. Where there is more than one applicable guideline and protocol for a given ethical requirement, these will be labelled as ER1.1, 1.2, 1.3, etc.

Table 7: Ethical requirements for personal data

Ethical framework	Ethical Requirement (ER)	Relevant ethical norms	Explanation
Ethical guidelines for trustworthy AI (EGTAI), ISO Overview of Ethical and Societal Concerns for AI	Human Agency and oversight (ER1)	Autonomy, positive liberty, negative liberty, balance of power, informed consent.	"AI systems should support human autonomy and decision-making, as prescribed by the principle of respect for human autonomy. This requires that AI systems should both act as enablers to a democratic, flourishing and equitable society by supporting the user's agency and foster fundamental rights, and allow for human oversight." (HLEG, 2019, p.15)
EGTAI, OECD Data Ethics Principles, ISO Overview of Ethical and Societal Concerns for AI	Privacy and data governance (ER2)	Data protection, data quality and integrity of data, data access, data storage and repurposing, data ownership and control, and informed consent.	"Privacy ...[is] a fundamental right particularly affected by AI systems. Prevention of harm to privacy also necessitates adequate data governance that covers the quality and integrity of the data used, its relevance in light of the domain in which the AI systems will be deployed, its access protocols and the capability to process data in a manner that protects privacy. (HLEG, 2019, p.17)
EGTAI, UK Data Ethics Framework, OECD Data Ethics Principles, ISO Overview of Ethical and Societal Concerns for AI	Transparency (ER3)	Explicability, explainability, traceability, communication, trust.	"This requirement is closely linked with the principle of explicability and encompasses transparency of elements relevant to an AI system: the data, the system and the business models." (HLEG, 2019, p.18)

Ethical framework	Ethical Requirement (ER)	Relevant ethical norms	Explanation
EGTAI, UK Data Ethics Framework. OECD AI Principles, ISO Overview of Ethical and Societal Concerns for AI	Diversity, non-discrimination, and fairness (ER4) ⁵⁹	Bias, accessibility, non-discrimination, inclusion, justice (distributive, procedural, restorative, and energy justice), Just Transition.	"In order to achieve Trustworthy AI, we must enable inclusion and diversity throughout the entire AI system's life cycle. Besides the consideration and involvement of all affected stakeholders throughout the process, this also entails ensuring equal access through inclusive design processes as well as equal treatment. This requirement is closely linked with the principle of fairness." (HLEG, 2019, p.18)
EGTAI, ISO Overview of Ethical and Societal Concerns for AI, CEN/CENELEC Green and Sustainable AI report	Societal and environmental well-being (ER5)	Fundamental needs, human dignity, democracy, sustainability, resource-efficiency.	"In line with the principles of fairness and prevention of harm, the broader society, other sentient beings and the environment should be also considered as stakeholders throughout the AI system's life cycle. Sustainability and ecological responsibility of AI systems should be encouraged, and research should be fostered into AI solutions addressing areas of global concern, such as for instance the Sustainable Development Goals. Ideally, AI systems should be used to benefit all human beings, including future generations." (HLEG, 2019, p.19)
EGTAI, UK Data Ethics Framework, OECD AI	Accountability(ER6)	Auditability, redress, responsibility,	"The requirement of accountability complements the above requirements, and is closely linked to the principle of fairness. It necessitates that

⁵⁹Fairness, non-discrimination, and diversity are all also outlined as ethical issues for blockchain specifically in the JRC technical reports. See: Fulli, G., Kotzakis, E., Nai Fovino, I., Policy and regulatory challenges for the deployment of blockchains in the energy field, EUR 30781 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2021, ISBN 978-92-76-40551-1, doi:10.2760/416731, JRC125216.

Ethical framework	Ethical Requirement (ER)	Relevant ethical norms	Explanation
Principles, OECD Data Ethics Principles, SO Overview of Ethical and Societal Concerns for AI		reproducibility, replicability.	mechanisms be put in place to ensure responsibility and accountability for AI systems and their outcomes, both before and after their development, deployment and use.” (HLEG, 2019, p.19)

5.2.2 Potential risks and guidelines to address them

In light of the requirements outlined above, the following table presents the potential risks posed to the realisation of these ethical requirements by the various functionalities developed within the DATA CELLAR project. This includes the functionalities described in section 4.3 such as the data marketplace, decision support system (DSS), digital twins, blockchain functionality, and the use of AI. Additionally, the requirements address the risks associated with the INTEMA and VERIFY tools developed within the DATA CELLAR project. INTEMA (INTEgrated Energy MAnagement) is an energy systems’ modelling and simulation platform whilst VERIFY (Virtual intEgrated platfoRm on LCA) is a platform which will be used to conduct economic (Life Cycle Cost) and environmental (Life Cycle Assessment) analyses at a Community level. This approach differs slightly from that used within section 5.1 which has a column dedicated to applicable legal frameworks. This is because the ethical requirements overlap extensively within each of the ethical frameworks and are largely based on one main framework, the EGTAI, as seen in table 7. Thus, to avoid repetition, table 8 instead includes what functionality or functionalities the ER corresponds to. The table also provides an impact and probability score for each of the risks. These scores were collaboratively formulated by the project’s T2.6 partners, in line with the project’s co-design approach.

Table 8: Relevant risks and guidelines for their mitigation

ER	Relevant functionality	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score ⁶⁰	Probability score
ER1.1	Data marketplace	Individuals and families may feel forced to consent to involvement in energy communities if this is the only option for affordable energy. This is particularly true for those facing poverty.	DATA CELLAR functionalities should respect the principle of informed consent throughout the design, development and deployment of the tools.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Informed consent must be acquired from all individuals and families participating in the data marketplace. Partners should follow the Ethical Protocol within D9.2 and the informed consent mechanisms provided therein. • Homeowners should be made aware of their freedom to opt in or opt out of an energy community, its advantages and disadvantages, as well as any potential risks of their involvement. • Spot-checks should be conducted to ensure that financial pressures, undue influence, or imbalances in power have not been exploited to coerce individuals from becoming involved in the marketplace or communities. Investigations should be conducted where there is suspicion of such influence and consent should be invalidated where this is the case 	Medium	Medium
ER1.2	DSS, Digital twin, VERIFY, INTEMA.	Automation bias could lead to an over-reliance on the tools.	DATA CELLAR functionalities should support human agency and decision-making,	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Users should be notified of the fact that they are interacting with an automated system and informed of the degree of automation within it. • End-users and consumers should be notified when a decision impacting their energy usage has been fully or partly automated. 	Medium	Medium

⁶⁰The impact score refers to the impact of the risk when and where it materialises.

ER	Relevant functionality	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score ⁶⁰	Probability score
			<p>ensuring that respect for the principle of human autonomy is embedded within the design and use of the DATA CELLAR functionalities.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Users of the system should receive regular training on the use of the systems to inhibit potential de-skilling of workers in the energy sector. This includes training on automation bias and its impact on decision-making so as to reduce user complacency and maintain meaningful human control over energy decisions. • Where the systems interfere with or influence human decision-making, this should be minimised. Any interference should be justified through a risk assessment (SHERPA, 2019). • Developers should evaluate the impact of the method of decision support adopted on users' cognitive abilities. A method which allows for "high interactivity and control of the decision process" is advised (Walling and Vaneeckhautea, 2020, p.26). • All energy decisions must contain human oversight, through human on the loop, human in the loop, or human in command mechanisms. • Recommendations offered by the DSS should be framed as advice rather than as a command. Instructive language should be minimized, and an unassertive tone adopted where possible. Users should be encouraged to actively evaluate the recommendations provided by the tools. 		

ER	Relevant functionality	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score ⁶⁰	Probability score
ER1.3	AI, DSS, Digital twins, VERIFY, INTEMA	Accuracy issues, errors, or the structure of the tools' systems may prevent users from making properly informed choices.	DATA CELLAR functionalities should seek to enhance users' deliberative autonomy and contribute to informed choices.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Users should be notified of the limitations of the DATA CELLAR tools, including the potential for inaccuracies or mistakes, through regular training. A comprehensive user guide on how the AI system reached a decision and its reasoning should be provided to users. If users are required to make lots of decisions, they may experience decision fatigue, leading to a reduction in their oversight capabilities. The DSS should be designed to "avoid unnecessary and superfluous decisions" (Walling and Vaneckhautea, 2020, p.22). The DSS should be designed in a user-friendly manner, ensuring that text is presented in a readable way rather than as bulks of information which may overwhelm the user. 	Medium	Medium
ER2.1	All	Depending on the granularity of data used, the collection, storage, and processing of energy data may be problematic. Inferences about	Ensure clear procedures regarding personal data which maximise privacy.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The granularity of data selected for the project must be explained and justified in accordance with the project purposes. Personal data should be anonymised, and identifiers should be removed from datasets as far as possible. This can be achieved through suppression, data masking, or the use of synthetic data to reduce the risk of reidentification. 	High	Medium

ER	Relevant functionality	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score ⁶⁰	Probability score
		<p>the behaviours and habits of DATA CELLAR users may be drawn from information on their energy consumption including on lifestyles, daily routines, or absences from the home.</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Partners should continue to adhere to the Ethical Protocol within D9.2 and update the Data Management Plan accordingly. Where personal data is processed, partners should consult with TRI, as the projects' appointed data protection advisor, or an appointed DPO. Partners may also wish to seek advice from the project advisory board. Partners should appoint an individual to be responsible for data breach notification duties. Clear and detailed descriptions of the roles, responsibilities, and privileges of users towards different types of data processed within the project must be outlined. A validated log detailing who has access to certain data should be maintained and an oversight log on where, when, why, and by whom it has been accessed should be maintained. Individuals involved in collecting, storing, using, analysing, preparing, or processing the data should sign a code of conduct regarding their privacy practices. Aggregation techniques should be used to ensure that previously non-personal data does not become personal or sensitive. 		

ER	Relevant functionality	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score ⁶⁰	Probability score
				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Due to the public nature of blockchain or DLT as well as the data marketplace, all personal data to be shared on these platforms should have all direct identifiers removed via generalisation, pseudonymity, or complete data removal-suppression. Alternatively, permissioned ledgers could be used to restrict access to such data. Anonymisation of personal data must be balanced with the efficiency requirements of the tool, e.g., the AI models and DSS tools may struggle to provide fine-tuned recommendations using anonymised data. To build and maintain trust, data quality assessments should be implemented, and quality controls placed on datasets. 		
ER2.2	Blockchain/DLT	Blockchain immutability means that any past records of users' consumption habits are permanent.	Interests of security, accuracy, and efficiency must be balanced with respect for individual's privacy.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Developers should combine on-chain and off-chain data, minimising the personal data stored on the blockchain. As information about users involved in transactions or data-sharing may travel across the blockchain, encryption or data transformation techniques should be used to mask users' identities on the chain. 	Medium	Medium
ER2.3	All	A range of agents contribute to the	Ensure clear procedures and	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Where data is repurposed or used for a secondary purpose, informed consent must be sought for 	Low	Medium

ER	Relevant functionality	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score ⁶⁰	Probability score
		datasets used, complicating data ownership and control, particularly where data is reused or repurposed.	delimitations of responsibility regarding the ownership and control of data amongst all relevant stakeholders.	<p>that purpose or an alternative legal basis relied upon.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Where prevailing laws on the ownership of certain data or datasets are insufficiently clear, agreements with the providers of such data should clearly delimit the parameters of ownership and control (SHERPA, 2019). A controller should be identified for the different data types collected and used throughout the DATA CELLAR project. 		
ER3.1	DSS, AI, Digital twins, VERIFY, INTEMA	Black box algorithms and a lack of transparency regarding how the tools operate as well as the reasoning behind their decisions.	Ensure that the necessary transparency and explainability mechanisms and procedures are implemented into the tools' infrastructure at the design, development, and deployment phases.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Algorithmic transparency should be implemented to ensure that the tools can effectively prescribe actions to humans and that users can contest those actions or decisions. Decision parameters should be made as transparent as possible and post-hoc feedback permitted. Complete algorithmic transparency must be balanced with the reduced efficacy and accuracy which may come with it as well as geopolitical tensions which may complicate data transparency. Potential loopholes should be continually assessed and mitigated. All trade-offs should be justified. The design of the user interface for the DSS, AI, and digital twin functionalities should display the steps and processes grounding their 	Medium	Medium

ER	Relevant functionality	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score ⁶⁰	Probability score
				<p>recommendations through a comprehensive user guide. This would include information on assumptions that impact the result validity.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explainability of the models and their rationale should be adjusted to the needs of the project as well as the understanding of the tools' users. • Users and end-users should be made aware that the tools they are interacting with use AI or that the decisions which impact them are automated. • Decisions which impact end-users or consumers should be understandable, delivered in colloquial rather than overly technical language. 		
ER3.2	All	The variety of agents involved in data collection, usage, access, sharing, processing, and storage may inhibit transparency regarding data handling processes.	Ensure that transparency mechanisms and procedures are integrated at each phase of the data lifecycle.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pilots can be used to examine the transparency of the tools' data management processes. • The models, their development process and their decision-making mechanisms should be clearly documented to maximise traceability, allow developers to fine-tune the tools, and to ensure that regulators can check tool compliance. Explanations regarding the tools' operations or decisions should be available upon request to an auditor or end-user where they impact end-users or there is a potential for harm (SHERPA, 2019). 	Low	Low

ER	Relevant functionality	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score ⁶⁰	Probability score
ER4.1	All	Certain individuals or groups may be overrepresented or underrepresented in the datasets used to train and develop the tools.	Inclusion and diversity should be maximised when collecting data and curating the datasets used within the project.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Before collecting or processing any data, the business requirements of the tools should be established and data planning clearly documented, labelling the social groups which the data should represent. This documentation should be used as a point of reference throughout the data lifecycle, with oversight mechanisms implemented to ensure its requirements are being fulfilled. • Data collection processes should be monitored to ensure that a diverse and inclusive range of social groups are represented in the data. A representative dataset minimises inaccuracies or unfairness in the tools' decisions. • At the data analysis phase, precaution should be taken to remove variables which may introduce bias and produce unfair decisions. For example, AI algorithms often display bias towards smaller electrical loads from poorer households. • Unconscious bias training should be provided to data handlers on the potential for biased datasets to worsen pre-existing societal biases or inequalities. • During data preparation and selection, the parameters as to which data to use and which to exclude must be explained and justified in light of 	Medium	Medium

ER	Relevant functionality	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score ⁶⁰	Probability score
				<p>the tools’ purpose and with regards to the principles of energy justice and just transition.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Before deployment, a diversity report using a diversity metric should be produced on the range of users represented in the data, with a particular focus on users more likely to experience energy poverty. • Exploiting datasets from other projects as well as interoperability and data clustering could help with mitigating bias in project datasets. • Solutions such as regularisation should be employed to prevent data overfitting. • The models should be tested and simulated prior to their deployment to test for the formation of algorithmic feedback loops which may entrench and worsen societal inequalities or biases as well as contribute to energy poverty. 		
ER4.2	All	The tools and their outputs may not be accessible or provide equitable benefits to all users.	Inclusion and accessibility should be integrated into the design and infrastructure of the tools.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The principles of Universal Design should be implemented into the design and development of the DATA CELLAR tools. The Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (W3C, 2023) or standards such as the European Digital Accessibility Requirements (EN 301 549) should be used to maximise accessibility for the widest possible range of users. 	Medium	Medium

ER	Relevant functionality	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score ⁶⁰	Probability score
				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consultations should be held with stakeholders who are directly or indirectly impacted by the tools throughout their lifecycle. • The project should hire and engage with a diverse range of stakeholders from different cultures, disciplines, and backgrounds. • Pilots or collaborative activities involving vulnerable individuals or typically marginalised populations should be used to formulate accessible user and end-user requirements. • The tools should be accompanied with comprehensive user and end-user guides which are accessible for a range of different literacy levels. The outputs and results of the DSS should be viewable at different levels of expertise and detail, tailored to the user (Hart et al, 2022). • At the deployment and implementation phase, the tools should be evaluated to ensure that no persons or groups are disproportionately harmed or negatively impacted. Such harms should be minimised. 		
ER5.1	All	The tools' development may prove resource-intensive and the	The tools should be designed, developed and deployed in a	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Frameworks for monitoring the greenhouse gas emissions of the AI tools should be established, measuring computational impacts, short-term 	Medium	Medium

ER	Relevant functionality	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score ⁶⁰	Probability score
		decisions recommended by the tools may increase energy usage, producing a negative environmental impact.	manner which adheres to the principles of sustainability and resource efficiency.	<p>impacts, and structural impacts with wider societal effects.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developers should work to limit the carbon footprint produced by datacentres throughout the data lifecycle, potentially through reusing algorithms or federated learning techniques. • Human oversight mechanisms should be implemented to evaluate the decisions and recommendations of the tools with regards to their environmental impact 		
ER5.2	Data marketplace, DSS, VERIFY, INTEMA	Inaccuracies or problems with the tools may disrupt energy distribution, impacting the supply of energy or requiring public taxation to compensate for mistakes.	Ensure that relevant safeguarding measures are implemented to protect fundamental needs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tools should be tested and simulated prior to deployment to ensure that fundamental needs, energy security, and critical aspects of social life will not be impaired through their operation. • Continuous assessments of the accuracy of IoT meters should be conducted to ensure that the data collected and fed into the digital twins and DSS is reliable. • Technical safeguards or fall-back plans should be implemented in case of a grid defection due to disruptions caused by local marketplaces. 	Medium	Medium
ER5.3	AI, DSS	Using AI to balance energy needs may require it to make	To ensure that human dignity is protected, the use of AI to	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work conducted by the AI system and by humans should be delegated based on their respective skills through human-machine teaming as far as possible (Kasparov, 2018). 	High	Low

ER	Relevant functionality	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score ⁶⁰	Probability score
		inherently moral decisions which it is not equipped.	make moral or ethical decisions should be minimised.			
ER6	All	A range of agents contribute to the design, development, testing, and use of the tools, complicating the attribution of responsibility and the accountability process where harm is caused.	Ensure that the necessary accountability mechanisms are integrated into the project and its tools, maximising auditability and traceability.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traceability must be ensured so that the relevant actors may be held accountable at each phase of the data handling and deployment of the tools. The tools' systems and outputs should be monitored and logged through user access control and proper documentation of the tools' performance, including any actions taken to counter potential problems. • Accountability frameworks detailing the responsible actors at each phase of the tool's design, development, and deployment should be constructed. This includes a defined channel for giving feedback as well as obtaining information. This is particularly important given the impact that tools such as the digital twins can have on physical assets and persons. • Trade-offs between values may be required. Such trade-offs should be documented and justified in openly available reports. 	High	Medium

ER	Relevant functionality	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score ⁶⁰	Probability score
				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Independent reporting mechanisms and protectionary regimes for whistleblowers should be implemented to ensure that a culture of accountability is maintained. • An incident reporting process should be developed to ensure incidents are reported in a timely manner. • Performance indicators should be formulated and used as a benchmark to consistently measure the tools' outputs. • Data and result reproducibility should be prioritised. • Internal and external audits of the developed systems should be conducted. • Project partners' decisions and discussions should be documented in meeting minutes that are available to all partners for viewing and amendment. • Redress and remedial mechanisms should be formulated before the tools are deployed. This could be achieved through consultation with key stakeholders and end-users. 		

5.3 Guidelines and best practices that should be adopted by DATA CELLAR

This section aims to summarise best practices and guidelines that should be incorporated by DATA CELLAR. The structure of this section will reflect these goals. Similar to the preceding subsections, this one will also rely on tables to convey its findings.

Table 9: Summary of general ethical and legal guidelines for data processing⁶¹

No.	Guidelines
ER2.1, ER2.3, All PLR(s)	DATA CELLAR needs to create, implement and publish a data policy that will clearly outline the rights and obligations of all relevant stakeholders in relation to data ownership, data rights and data processing activities.
ER1.2, ER1.3, ER3.1, ER5.2, ER5.3, PLG7, PLG14, PLG15	DATA CELLAR needs to incorporate organisational, technical and legal measures that will enable the effective exercise of available data rights, protect data autonomy, sovereignty, and human dignity as well as fundamental rights of individuals such as the right to privacy and freedom from discrimination are safeguarded throughout the duration of the project. DATA CELLAR should also have adequate remedies in case of fundamental and data rights violations.
All	Project partners should cooperate throughout the duration of the project to ensure proper implementation of technical, ethical, organisational, and legal measures for data processing found in applicable legal and ethical frameworks.
All	DATA CELLAR's data policies should be reviewed periodically to ensure compliance with applicable legislative and ethical frameworks.
ER1.1, PLR 1.1, PLR 10.1, PLR 14.1, PLR 17.1, PLR 26.1, PLR 47.1, ELR 1.1, ELR 7.1, PLR 3.1, PLR 4.1, PLR 10.3, PLR 14.3, PLR 17.3, PLR 26.3, PLR 32.1, PLR 47.3, ELR 6.2, ELR 12.2, PLR 1.2, PLR 10.10, PLR 14.9, PLR 17.9, PLR 22.2, PLR 26.7, PLR 32.6, PLR 47.8, ELR 6.10, ELR 12.10	DATA CELLAR should ensure that every data processing activity will have an appropriate legal basis and will be lawful under national and European law.
ER3.2, All PLR(s)	DATA CELLAR should ensure that transparency mechanisms and procedures relating to data

⁶¹ This table follows guidelines from AEPD, 2023, pp. 89–93.

No.	Guidelines
	processing activities are integrated and implemented at each phase of the data lifecycle.
ER2.1, PLR10.7, PLR14.5, PLR17.5, ELR6.6, ELR12.6, PLR9.2, PLR10.8, PLR14.7, PLR17.7, PLR23.1, PLR26.6, PLR31.1, PLR32.5, ELR6.8, ELR12.8	DATA CELLAR should ensure its procedures, functionalities and tools, where applicable and relevant, will be aimed at maximizing privacy.
ER2.1, ER2.2, PLR4.2, PLR5.1, PLR10.4, PLR13.1, PLR15.1, PLR26.4, PLR34.1, PLR47.4, ELR6.3, ELR12.3, PLR7.1, PLR10.6, PLR11.1, PLR12.1, PLR15.2, PLR16.1, PLR21.1, PLR22.1, PLR30.1, PLR32.3, PLR34.2, PLR47.6, ELR6.5, ELR12.5, PLR9.2, PLR10.8, PLR14.7, PLR17.7, PLR23.1, PLR26.6, PLR31.1, PLR32.5, ELR6.8, ELR12.8	DATA CELLAR should ensure that its procedures, functionalities, and tools will balance the interests in security, accuracy, and efficiency with respect to the data privacy of individual users.
ER4.1, ER4.2, PLR9.3, PLR10.9, PLR14.8, PLR17.8, PLR19.1, PLR30.2, PLR35.1, PLR46.1, ELR2.2, ELR3.3, ELR4.2, ELR5.2, ELR6.9, ELR7.3, ELR8.2, ELR9.3, ELR10.2, ELR11.2, ELR12.9, PLR22.3, PLR39.1, PLR40.1, PLR41.1, PLR42.1	DATA CELLAR should ensure that its dataspace, functionalities, and tools will be inclusive and accessible and should be integrated into the design and infrastructure of the tools to all its potential users.
PLR18.1, PLR22.4, PLR23.2, PLR38.2, PLR43.1, PLR45.1, ELR2.3	DATA CELLAR should contribute to competition and the data economy by taking suitable technical, legal and organisational measures.
ER5.1	DATA CELLAR's dataspace, tools and functionalities should be designed, developed and deployed in accordance with the principles of sustainability and energy efficiency.
PLR9.4, PLR20.2, PLR22.5, PLR36.3, PLR46.2, ELR5.3, ELR10.3	DATA CELLAR should be designed, and developed and by default ensure the semantical, legal, organisational and technical interoperability of its dataspace.
PLR29.1	DATA CELLAR should ensure that any third parties who obtain data from its dataspace are contractually, technically, and organisationally prohibited from abusing it in any way.
ER.6.1, PLG5	DATA CELLAR must implement organisational, technical, and legal measures to track the whole data cycle.

6 Cyber and data security

This section gives an overview of the ethical and legal obligations drawn from applicable EU-wide laws such as the CSA, CRA and NIS, as well the GDPR. This section will follow the same format as

section 5. Firstly, it will examine the legal requirements for legislative requirements for data security. Additionally, it will pinpoint risks and risk-reduction strategies linked to the previously established requirements resulting from legal frameworks. A parallel approach will be adopted with regards to providing ethical requirements related to data and cyber security. This section focuses particularly on identity authentication, anonymization and aggregation, encryption, and data access control as means for achieving cyber and data security.

6.1 Legal Requirements for cyber and data security

6.1.1 Legal Requirements

Table 10 Legal requirements from personal data⁶²

Legal framework	Requirement	Explanation
GDPR	Data security (CLR 1)	Data controllers and processors are required to implement security-related technical and organisational safeguards to guarantee the level of security which is appropriate to the risk, including: “(a) the pseudonymisation and encryption of personal data; (b) the ability to ensure the ongoing confidentiality, integrity, availability and resilience of processing systems and services; (c) the ability to restore the availability and access to personal data promptly in the event of a physical or technical incident; (d) a process for regularly testing, assessing and evaluating the effectiveness of technical and organisational measures for ensuring the security of the processing” [art. 32(1) GDPR] and (e) notification of data breach to the relevant supervisory authority (art.33 GDPR) and in case of high risk to data rights and fundamental freedoms to data subjects (art.34 GDPR) (Burton, 2020a, pp. 630, 632, 634–636, 2020b, p. 643, 2020c, p. 655). Furthermore, it is important to ensure access to personal data is granted only to authorized people and assess “risks that are presented by processing, in particular from accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorised disclosure of, or access to personal data transmitted, stored or otherwise processed” [art. 32(2) GDPR; Burton, 2020, p. 632].
ePR and ePD	Security (CLR 2)	Service providers must implement organisational and technical measures that will safeguard information stored in and related to end-users’ terminal equipment (rec. 20 ePD). In doing so, they must comply with security requirements found in art. 32 of GDPR [rec. 37 and 8(1b) ePR] as well as “inform end- users of measures they can take to protect the security of their communications for instance by using specific types of software or encryption technologies” (rec.32 ePR) and detected security risks (art. 17 ePR). They must incorporate measures relating to a) authentication and authorisation policy and system to shield against unauthorized access [rec. 20, 21, 23 and art. 5(3) ePD], b) data access policy and systems to protect

⁶² This tables was created on the basis of Burton, 2020a, 2020b, 2020c; Kalle, 2019; Richter, 2023; Von Ditfurth & Lienemann, 2022.

Legal framework	Requirement	Explanation
		<p>against accidental or unlawful disclosure (rec. 21 art. 4(1a) ePD), and c) security policy, risk management policy and notification system to monitor, manage, remedy and minimise data and cyber-security risks [rec. 20, 32, art.4(1a), (2) and (3)and 17 ePD].</p>
DGA	Security (CL 3)	<p>Dataspaces must ensure an appropriate level of security (rec. 2 DGA)(AEPD, 2023, p. 66; Richter, 2023, p. 646; Von Ditfurth & Lienemann, 2022, p. 282). In case of both data re-use and data intermediation, appropriate security mechanisms must be implemented and where relevant they should comply with the data security principle found in GDPR (see CLR 1)(Richter, 2023, p. 646; Von Ditfurth & Lienemann, 2022, p. 282). These mechanisms should include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For data intermediation: incorporation of measures and procedures to avert the unlawful transfer or access (art. 12(j) DGA); notification of data holders ‘in case of an unauthorised transfer, access or use’ (art. 12(k) DGA); ensuring ‘an appropriate level of security’ for different data types during their “storage, processing and transmission” (art. 12(l) DGA); creation of data availability and resilience enabling to perform services even in case of insolvency [art. 12(h) DGA]; obligation to make a record of the data processing activities (art. 12(o) DGA)(Richter, 2023, p. 646; Von Ditfurth & Lienemann, 2022, pp. 287, 290). - For data re-use: Public sector bodies need to ensure that the protected nature of data is safeguarded for instance by a) anonymisation, modification, aggregation or other appropriate mechanism [rec. 15 and art.5(3)(ai) and (aii) DGA], b) secure environment for data processing and access [art. 5(3)(b) DGA], which complies with high-security standards [art. 5(3)(c) DGA], c) notification system [art. 5(5) DGA] and d) procedures and measures for international transfers and access ensuring protection from unauthorized persons (rec.20 DGA) as well as protection of confidential data allowing when needed to adopt additional technical and security measures [art.5 (8), (10), (12) and (13) DGA]. International access and transfer must also comply with sectoral, namely, energy laws when they impose stricter conditions [rec. 24 DGA] and fulfil GDPR conditions when personal data is transferred or accessed (see Chapter V GDPR).

Legal framework	Requirement	Explanation
DA	Security (CLR 4)	Data produced by-products and related services ought to be “securely (...) accessible to the user” [art.3(1) DA]. To ensure this, it is necessary to incorporate appropriate security measures, namely: a) “the technical feasibility of third-party access for all types of data” [rec.31 and art. 3(1) DA]; b) technical safeguards and rules protecting against unauthorised use or disclosure of relevant data such as smart contracts [art.11(1) DA], “the encryption of data, the frequent submission to audits, the verified adherence to relevant security reassurance certification schemes, and the modification of corporate policies” (rec 78 DA); c) technical infrastructure which is able to erase and rectify incorrect information [art.11(2) DA]; and d) measures requiring the data holder, user third party to only record data when it "is necessary for the sound execution of the user’s access request and for the security and the maintenance of the data infrastructure" [art. 4(2) and 5(3) DA].
FFNPD	Security (CLR 5)	It is necessary to comply with relevant security laws for example laws of MS of residence or establishment of the natural or legal persons (rec.34 and 35 FFND).
NIS2	European cybersecurity certification schemes (CLR 6)	Since European cyber-security certification is required in some MS, it might be mandatory to certify ICT products, ICT services and ICT processes, developed by DATA CELLAR dataspace [art. 24 (1) NIS].
	Standardisation and interoperability (CLR 7)	To foster interoperability and standardisation, it is advised to use “European and international standards and technical specifications relevant to the security of network and information systems” [art.25(1) NIS].
	Data protection (CLR 8)	When distributive technologies are used, such as AI or blockchain, it is necessary to comply with EU data protection law, especially “the data protection principles of data accuracy, data minimisation, fairness and transparency, and data security, such as state-of-the-art encryption” (rec. 51 NIS). Furthermore, the processing of personal data should limit to what is necessary and proportionate to safeguard the security of networks and information systems (rec. 121 NIS).
	Implementation of appropriate risk	It is necessary to adopt appropriate security measures [art. 4 and 21(1) NIS] which will: - “Include measures to identify any risks of incidents, to prevent, detect, respond to and recover from incidents and to mitigate their impact” (rec. 78 NIS).

Legal framework	Requirement	Explanation
	management measures (CLR 9)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - "Include the security of stored, transmitted and processed data" (rec.78 NIS). - "Provide for systemic analysis, taking into account the human factor, in order to have a complete picture of the security of the network and information system" (rec. 78 NIS). - Based cybersecurity risk-management measures on an "all-hazards approach, which aims to protect network and information systems and the physical environment" (rec 79 NIS). - Ensure that measures "are proportionate to (...) exposure to risks and to the societal and economic impact that an incident would have" [rec. 82 and art. 21(1) NIS] considering "criticality of the entity, and the risks, including societal risks" [rec 82 and art. 21(1) NIS]. - "Adopt a wide range of basic cyber hygiene practices" and "where appropriate, pursue the integration of cybersecurity enhancing technologies, such as artificial intelligence or machine-learning systems to enhance their capabilities and the security of network and information systems" (rec.89 NIS).
	Notification system (CLR 10)	All incidents and data breaches should be notified [rec. 102 and art. 23(1) NIS]. It is also necessary to "communicate, without undue delay, to their service recipients any measures or remedies that they can take to mitigate the resulting risks from a significant cyber threat. Those entities should, where appropriate and in particular where the significant cyber threat is likely to materialise, also inform their service recipients of the threat itself" [rec. 103 and art. 23 NIS].
	Security by design and security by default (CLR 11)	"Electronic communications services should implement security by design and by default" (rec. 104 NIS).
CSA	certification scheme for ICT digital products, services, and processes (CLR 12)	<p>It might be necessary to undergo EU cyber-security certification where European or national law requires it [rec.91 and art 56(2) CSA]. This certification scheme requires adopting measures that will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - "Protect stored, transmitted or otherwise processed data against accidental or unauthorised storage, processing, access or disclosure during the entire life cycle of the ICT product, ICT service or ICT process" [art. 51(1a) and rec.75 CSA];

Legal framework	Requirement	Explanation
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - "Protect stored, transmitted or otherwise processed data against accidental or unauthorised destruction, loss or alteration or lack of availability during the entire life cycle of the ICT product, ICT service or ICT process" [art. 51(1b) and rec.75 CSA]; - "Authorised persons, programs or machines are able only to access the data, services or functions to which their access rights refer" [art. 51(1c) and rec.75 CSA]; - "To identify and document known dependencies and vulnerabilities" [art. 51(1d) and rec.75 CSA]; - "Record which data, services or functions have been accessed, used or otherwise processed, at what times and by whom" [art. 51(1e) and rec.75 CSA]; - "Make it possible to check which data, services or functions have been accessed, used or otherwise processed, at what times and by whom" [art. 51(1f) and rec.75 CSA]; - "Verify that ICT products, ICT services and ICT processes do not contain known vulnerabilities" [art. 51(1g) and rec.75 CSA]; - "Restore the availability and access to data, services and functions in a timely manner in the event of a physical or technical incident" [art. 51(1h) and rec.75 CSA]; - "ICT products, ICT services and ICT processes are secure by default and by design" [art. 51(1i) and rec.75 CSA]; - "ICT products, ICT services and ICT processes are provided with up-to-date software and hardware that do not contain publicly known vulnerabilities and are provided with mechanisms for secure updates" [art. 51(1j) and rec.75 CSA].
	<p>Security by default and security by design (CLR 13)</p>	<p>It is important to ensure security by default and security by design (rec. 12-13 CSA). In this context, it is important to consider security aspects during the design stage and development of ICT products, ICT services or ICT processes (rec.12-13 CSA) to limit possibility of cyberattacks (rec.12-13 CSA). "Security should be ensured throughout the lifetime of the ICT product, ICT service or ICT process by design and development processes that constantly evolve to reduce the risk of harm from malicious exploitation" (rec.12-13 CSA).</p>

Legal framework	Requirement	Explanation
eIDAS	Security (CLR 14)	It is crucial to ensure the security of e-identification. This could be achieved by obtaining a certification “based on international standards such as ISO 15408 and related evaluation methods and mutual recognition arrangements” (rec. 55 eIDAS). In the case when there are no standards, it is important to evaluate these solutions using alternative processes that “should be comparable to the standards for IT security certification insofar as their security levels are equivalent” (rec. 55 CSA) Furthermore, trust service providers are required to “take appropriate technical and organisational measures to manage the risks posed to the security of the trust services they provide” [art. 19(1)eIDAS] including “technical controls, the purpose of which is to prevent misuse or alteration of the identity” (art. 8 eIDAS). These measures should consider a) technological developments, b) the level of security and level of risk and c) impact of security incidents [art. 19(1)eIDAS]. Furthermore, they should also have a notification system by which all relevant parties would be timely informed in case of security incidents and breaches [art. 10, 19(1) and (2) eIDAS].
	Technical compatibility and interoperability (CLR 15)	This Regulation is technology-neutral (rec.27 eIDAS), but it requires ensuring technical compatibility and interoperability between different e-identification measures (rec.50 and art. 12 eIDAS).
	Accessibility (CLR 16)	When it is possible, trust services and end-user products should be accessible for persons with disabilities (art. 15 eIDAS).
	Data protection (CLR 17)	Processing of personal data should take place under European data protection rules (art.5 eIDAS).
	Reliability and quality (CRL 18)	To ensure reliability and quality, it is necessary to implement these minimum technical specifications, standards and procedures: “(a) the procedure to prove and verify the identity of natural or legal persons applying for the issuance of electronic identification means; (b) the procedure for the issuance of the requested electronic identification means; (c) the authentication mechanism, through which the natural or legal person uses the electronic identification means to confirm its identity to a relying party; (d) the entity issuing the electronic identification means; (e) any other body involved in the application for the

Legal framework	Requirement	Explanation
		issuance of the electronic identification means; and (f) the technical and security specifications of the issued electronic identification means” [art.8(3) eIDAS].
CRA	Security (CLR 19)	<p>Products with digital elements should appropriate security safeguards, in particular:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “(a) Be delivered with a secure by default configuration, including the possibility to reset the product to its original state; - (b) Ensure protection from unauthorised access by appropriate control mechanisms, including but not limited to authentication, identity or access management systems; - (c) Protect the confidentiality of stored, transmitted or otherwise processed data, personal or other, such as by encrypting relevant data at rest or in transit by state-of-the-art mechanisms; - (d) Protect the integrity of stored, transmitted or otherwise processed data, personal or other, commands, programs and configuration against any manipulation or modification not authorised by the user, as well as report on corruptions; - (e) Process only data, personal or other, that are adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary concerning the intended use of the product (‘minimisation of data’); - (f) Protect the availability of essential functions, including the resilience against and mitigation of denial-of-service attacks; - (g) Minimise their negative impact on the availability of services provided by other devices or networks; - (h) Be designed, developed and produced to limit attack surfaces, including external interfaces; - (i) Be designed, developed and produced to reduce the impact of an incident using appropriate exploitation mitigation mechanisms and techniques; - (j) Provide security-related information by recording and/or monitoring relevant internal activity, including the access to or modification of data, services or functions; - (k) Ensure that vulnerabilities can be addressed through security updates, including, where applicable, automatic updates and the notification of available updates to users” (art. 5 Annex I section 1(3) CRA).

Legal framework	Requirement	Explanation
	Implementation of risk management policies (CLR 20)	<p>Furthermore, it is required to put in place coordinated vulnerability disclosure policies (rec. 36 and Annex I), which will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “Identify and document vulnerabilities and components contained in the product, including by drawing up a software bill of materials in a commonly used and machine-readable format covering at the very least the top-level dependencies of the product; - Concerning the risks posed to the products with digital elements, address and remediate vulnerabilities without delay, including by providing security updates; - Apply effective and regular tests and reviews of the security of the product with digital elements; - Once a security update has been made available, publicly disclose information about fixed vulnerabilities, including a description of the vulnerabilities, information allowing users to identify the product with digital elements affected, the impacts of the vulnerabilities, their severity and information helping users to remediate the vulnerabilities; - Put in place and enforce a policy on coordinated vulnerability disclosure; - Take measures to facilitate the sharing of information about potential vulnerabilities in their product with digital elements as well as in third-party components contained in that product, including by providing a contact address for the reporting of the vulnerabilities discovered in the product with digital elements; - Provide for mechanisms to securely distribute updates for products with digital elements to ensure that exploitable vulnerabilities are fixed or mitigated promptly; - Ensure that, where security patches or updates are available to address identified security issues, they are disseminated without delay and free of charge” (Annex I section 2 CRA).
EMD	Data security (CLR 21)	This requirement requires maintaining the confidentiality of energy data and achieving compliance with cyber-security regulatory frameworks and standards [rec. 57, art. 20 (b) and 23 EMD] (Kalle, 2019, pp. 8-10).
IR	Security (CLR 22)	To ensure secure data access, it is encouraged to use digital solutions that are compliant with eIDAS regulations (rec.12 IR).

6.1.2 Potential risks and guidelines to address them

Table 11: Relevant risks and guidelines for their mitigation⁶³

LR	Relevant framework	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score	Probability score
All	All	Wrong implementation of data and cyber-security measures for example incorporation of safeguards and procedures that do not appropriately cater for unforeseen events such as cyber-attacks, system vulnerabilities, power outages, theft or personal data breaches, could cause harm to both DATA CELLAR's dataspace and its users (AEPD, 2023, p. 61; Iannone et al., 2021, p. 23). ⁶⁴	DATA CELLAR has to implement technical, legal and organizational procedures, measures and safeguards for data and cyber-security to ensure that DATA CELLAR's dataspace and its functionalities have the highest level of data and cyber security.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data processing of DATA CELLAR's dataspace and its functionalities should provide a high level of data and cyber-security, in particular, be able to safeguard high degree of confidentiality and integrity to adequately protect data that will be available on dataspace as well as ensure that its users are safeguarded against system vulnerabilities and cyber-attacks (AEPD, 2023, pp. 66-67).⁶⁵ DATA CELLAR should collectively create and implement data handling and retention policy, notification system, data and cyber-security policy, including risk management, authorization and authentication policy and data access policy. The foregoing procedures should incorporate relevant legal, technical and 	High	High

⁶³ This table was created on the basis of previous Table and AEPD, 2023; Iannone et al., 2021.

⁶⁴ A similar point is made in the ethical guidelines for cyber and data security. See ER7.1.

⁶⁵ For more extensive requirements that need to be complied by a) data controllers see CLR 1, b) service providers CLR 2 and c) data intermediation services see CLR 1, CLR 3-5, CLR 9-10, CLR 11, CLR 13-14, CLR 19-22.

LR	Relevant framework	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score	Probability score
				organisational measures (AEPD, 2023, pp. 68-69, 72, 74-75, 85; Iannone et al., 2021, p. 24).		
CLR 2.1, CLR 21.1	ePR, EMD	Data users of DATA CELLAR are not informed about security risks related to personal data processing and measures that could be taken to prevent them (AEPD, 2023, pp. 39-40; Iannone et al., 2021, p. 15).	DATA CELLAR should adequately inform its users about all security risks connected to data processing and the measures that could be used or are being employed to address them.	When personal data is processed, data controllers of DATA CELLAR should have notification system in place to inform users about security measures employed or procedures that could be utilised.	Medium	Low
All	All	There is the possibility that personal data on DATA CELLAR's dataspace could be breached as well and data that was anonymized could be re-identified and traced back, which would lead to privacy loopholes and breach of trust (AEPD, 2023, pp. 45, 85-86). ⁶⁶	DATA CELLAR should ensure that it has adequate security measures to protect personal data.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DATA CELLAR should design and operate its dataspace in the manner which will ensure 'high' level of security for data processing activities, in particular, for data collection, transfers and storage (AEPD, 2023, p. 66). Every successful attempt to reidentify a real person should be treated by DATA CELLAR as a data breach and handled accordingly (AEPD, 2023, p. 68). 	Medium	Medium

⁶⁶ A similar point is made in the ethical guidelines for cyber and data security. See ER7.2.

LR	Relevant framework	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score	Probability score
CLR 1.1, CLR 8.1, CLR 21.2	GDPR, NIS, EMD	There is a risk that the usage of distributive technologies such as AI or blockchain will become a reason for interference and their usage will infringe on fundamental rights of individuals such as the right to privacy or freedom from discrimination (AEPD, 2023, pp. 62-65; Iannone et al., 2021, p. 15). ⁶⁷	DATA CELLAR should ensure that its functionalities comply with data protection laws and that their risks are monitored and evaluated throughout the duration of the project.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DATA CELLAR needs to ensure that their functionalities are designed using data by protection and default principle with a focus on “the data protection principles of data accuracy, data minimisation, fairness and transparency, and data security, such as state-of-the-art encryption”(rec. 51 NIS; AEPD, 2023, p. 62). DATA CELLAR should ensure that personal data is only processed where is indispensable to protect the security of DATA CELLAR’s systems (rec. 121 NIS; AEPD, 2023, p. 66). Security measures are not always designed to cater for the risks to data rights and fundamental freedoms, therefore, DATA CELLAR in its risk management should consider security and data risks that could harm data rights and fundamental freedoms (AEPD, 2023, p. 67). 	High	High

⁶⁷ A similar point is made in the ethical guidelines for cyber and data security. See ER7.3.

LR	Relevant framework	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score	Probability score
CLR 1.2, CLR 9.1, CLR 20.1, CLR 21.3	GDPR, NIS, CRA, DA, EMD	There is a risk of cybersecurity attacks and data breaches on the DATA CELLAR's dataspace, its functionalities and other elements that could be connected to dataspace which could have a negative impact on the data users, trust and operation of dataspace and potential functioning of energy system (AEPD, 2023, pp. 67, 79; Iannone et al., 2021, pp. 23-24).	DATA CELLAR should implement appropriate risk management measures and vulnerability disclosure policies.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DATA CELLAR should implement risk management policy and measures which needs to be able to “identify any risks of incidents, to prevent, detect, respond to and recover from incidents and to mitigate their impact” (rec. 78 NIS). These measures should include a) systemic analysis, b) cybersecurity and data risk management with focus on potential societal and economic impact, c) cyber hygiene practices⁶⁸ and d) coordinated vulnerability disclosure policies⁶⁹ (AEPD, 2023, pp. 67-68). 	High	High
CLR 4.1, CLR 11.1, CLR 13.1, CLR 19.1,	NIS, CSA, CRA	Inappropriate design of the dataspace and its functionalities which do not account for the security aspects could increase the risks of cyber-attacks and data protection breaches	DATA CELLAR, namely, its dataspace and its functionalities, should be designed according to security by design and security by default	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Security by design and default should be warranted throughout the lifetime of the DATA CELLAR in order to continuously limit the risk of cyber-attacks, data breaches and other vulnerabilities. DATA CELLAR should ensure that a) it is secure by default configuration, b) has 	High	Medium

⁶⁸ For more information see CLR 9.

⁶⁹ For more information about elements that need to be accounted for in coordinated vulnerability disclosure policies see CLR 20.

LR	Relevant framework	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score	Probability score
CLR 21.4		(Iannone et al., 2021, pp. 23-24).	principle found in the cyber-security law.	authorisation and data access mechanism, and c) is resilient, namely, can ensure availability of data in case of cyber-attack, data breach or other system vulnerabilities, d) is designed in the way to cater for possible attacks such as denial of service attack, external service interferences etc., e) records and monitors suspicious activities, and f) is capable of remedying system vulnerabilities for example through system updates.		
CLR 6.1, CRL 12	NIS, CSA, EMD	DATA CELLAR may not fulfil certification requirements for relevant digital components of its dataspace, which could result in the violation of the EU and national cyber-security law and result in low security.	When applicable, DATA CELLAR should obtain relevant certification for its digital products, services, and processes.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European cyber-security certification is not mandatory, but it might be required in some Member States. DATA CELLAR should investigate when such certification is required and obtain it when it is necessary. 	Medium	Medium
CLR 1.3, CLR 2.2, CLR 3.1, CLR	GDPR, ePR, DGA, NIS, EMD	Lack of or inappropriate notification system can lead to untimely responses of DATA CELLAR's dataspace to	DATA CELLAR should ensure that system administrators are notified of data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DATA CELLAR should design and implement a notification system, which will promptly and clearly a) inform about potential data and cyber-security threats, b) notify supervisory authorities 	Medium	Medium

LR	Relevant framework	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score	Probability score
10.1, CLR 21.5		security vulnerabilities, potentially compromising the integrity of and user trust in its dataspace (Iannone et al., 2021, p. 23).	breaches and cyber security attacks .	<p>and relevant natural and legal persons about data or cyber-security breaches, and c) inform about measures and remedies that will be taken or are available to relevant parties (Iannone et al., 2021, p. 24).⁷⁰</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> DATA should ensure that personal data breach notifications are compliant with EDPB’s Guidelines 9/2022 on personal data breach notification under GDPR.⁷¹ 		
CLR 1.4, CLR 2.3, CLR 3.2, CLR 4.2, CLR 21.6	GDPR, ePR, DGA, DA	The use of inappropriate authorization methods which are incapable of tracking the data cycle, makes it very challenging to reconstruct a chain of events and increases the possibility of unlawful or unauthorized transfer that could compromise the integrity and security of DATA CELLAR’s dataspace (AEPD, 2023, p.	DATA CELLAR needs to have an effective and secure authorization system.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DATA CELLAR should design and implement an authorization policy and a system which will ensure that data access is only granted to authorized people (AEPD, 2023, p. 89; Iannone et al., 2021, p. 24). DATA CELLAR should also implement technical safeguards including , anonymization, pseudonymisation, aggregation, smart contracts or data encryption, and certification schemes, amongst others (Iannone et al., 2021, p. 24). 	Medium (Iannone et al., 2021, p. 24)	Medium

⁷⁰ For more information see CLR 1, CLR 2, CLR 3, CLR 10 and CLR 21.

⁷¹ EDPB, Guidelines 9/2022 on personal data breach notification under GDPR <[Guidelines 9/2022 on personal data breach notification under GDPR | European Data Protection Board \(europa.eu\)](https://european-data-protection-board.europa.eu)> accessed 5 October 2023.

LR	Relevant framework	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score	Probability score
		79; Iannone et al., 2021, p. 24).				
CLR 14.1, CLR 15.1, CLR 16.1, CLR 17 and CLR 18.1, CLR 22	eIDAS	DATA CELLAR's identification, authentication systems and trust services could be inadequate due to unsuitable security measures, lack of accessibility, technical incomparability or interoperability leading to lost trust and possibly providing attackers with sensitive and confidential information (AEPD, 2023, pp. 73-74, 79).	DATA CELLAR should have a proper authentication and identification system.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DATA CELLAR should have robust authentication system and procedures, which is able to a) verify the identity of natural or legal persons; (b) have clear procedures for electronic identification means; (c) has the authentication mechanism that is able to effectively confirm its identity of relevant natural and legal person; (d) has designated entity that will be in charge of these mechanisms; and (e) complies with relevant the technical and security conditions and (f) incorporate appropriate notification system (Iannone et al., 2021, p. 24).⁷² DATA CELLAR should also periodically consider and review the security of its system with a focus on a) technological advances, b) security risks and c) the effect of data and security occurrences. In this context, DATA CELLAR should consider obtaining a certification "based 	Medium	Medium

⁷² See CLR 18.

LR	Relevant framework	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score	Probability score
				<p>on international standards such as ISO 15408 and related evaluation methods and mutual recognition arrangements” (AEPD, 2023, pp. 71-72).⁷³</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lastly, DATA CELLAR should ensure interoperability and accessibility of its system to vulnerable users and persons with disabilities.⁷⁴ 		
CLR 1.5, CLR 2.4, CLR 3.3, CLR 21.7	GDPR, ePR, DGA, EMD	Lack of data traceability of processing activities can hamper DATA CELLAR's inability to track the data cycle and trace back a chain of events resulting in incapability to timely detect security and data vulnerabilities (AEPD, 2023, pp. 80-82; Iannone et al., 2021, p. 24).	DATA CELLAR should be able to trace data cycles at an individual user level (AEPD, 2023, p. 81).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data intermediation service providers, data controllers or data processors carrying out processing activities on behalf of a controller should keep record of data processing, including: a) name and contact details, b) description of data users and categories of relevant data, c) purpose of data processing, d) description of recipient and data which will be available to them and e) in case international transfer or data access description of third party or organisation, f) retention period as well as brief explanation of legal, technical and organisation security measures [art. 	Medium	Low

⁷³ See CLR 14-15.

⁷⁴ See CLR 14-16.

LR	Relevant framework	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score	Probability score
				30 GDPR, art. 12(o) DGA] (AEPD, 2023, p. 81; Iannone et al., 2021, p. 24)..		
CLR 1.6	GDPR, DGA	The DATA CELLAR's dataspace may not be able to adequately safeguard resilience, availability of data and its services in case of various physical, organizational and technical incidents such as overload of operations, data breaches, cyber-security attacks and insolvency which could result in the potential harm to its users and DATA CELLAR ecosystem (AEPD, 2023, p. 67; Iannone et al., 2021, p. 23).	DATA CELLAR should ensure data availability and resilience even in unforeseen circumstances.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DATA CELLAR should have the technical capability, namely, resilient and strong technical infrastructure and technical protocols, that will enable to restore the availability and resilience of its data and services in the event of a physical or technical occurrence or in case of insolvency (AEPD, 2023, p. 67). For example, DATA CELLAR should be able to safeguard the security of data storage, safe data access transfer as well and the possibility of recovering data of users (AEPD, 2023, p. 67). 	High	High
CLR 1.7, CLR 2.5, CLR 3.4,	GDPR, ePR, DGA, EMD	Data and cyber security measures and risk management measures of DATA CELLAR might become outdated due to new technical	DATA CELLAR should ensure that its data and cybersecurity policies and management measures remain up to	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DATA CELLAR should periodically review its data and cyber security measures and risk management measures to accommodate minor changes in law, data and cyber-security 	Medium	Medium

LR	Relevant framework	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score	Probability score
CLR 21.8		developments, changes in law or other relevant circumstances (AEPD, 2023, p. 79).	data in light of changing circumstances .	<p>incidents such as unauthorized assess (AEPD, 2023, p. 71).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> DATA CELLAR should also review such policies on an ad hoc basis in case of a) legislative or regulatory changes, b) organisational changes, and c) data breaches and other major data and cyber vulnerabilities (AEPD, 2023, pp. 71-72). 		
All	All	The complexity of DATA CELLAR's data processing environment might pose challenges to ensuring the security of data processing activities and the overall security of DATA CELLAR's dataspace (AEPD, 2023, p. 68).	DATA CELLAR should implement a data security policy which will outline the different roles and responsibilities of relevant parties in relation to data and cyber-security.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DATA CELLAR's consortium should collectively create, implement, manage and monitor data and cybersecurity risks (AEPD, 2023, p. 68). It is necessary that ensure that all functionalities of the DATA CELLAR's and dataspace itself will be designed under the principle of security by design and default (AEPD, 2023, p. 35). DATA CELLAR should design an entity that will be responsible for checking compliance dataspace with applicable legislative frameworks (AEPD, 2023, p. 91). 	Medium	Medium
CLR 1.8, CLR 2.6, CLR	GDPR, ePR, DGA, EMD	International data transfer and data access to third parties and organizations might not have	DATA CELLAR should contractually ensure that international organizations and third	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DATA CELLAR should ensure that data is protected from unauthorized access and that third parties will have adequate 	High	High

LR	Relevant framework	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score	Probability score
3.5, CLR 21.9		appropriate security measures (AEPD, 2023, pp. 87-89).	parties in third countries will ensure the same level of protection that is provided in applicable EU and national law.	organisational, legal and technical safeguards (AEPD, 2023, p. 91).		
CLR 1.9, CLR 2.7, CLR 3.6, CLR 4.3, CLR 5.1, CLR 8.2	GDPR, ePR, DGA, DA, FFNDP, NIS	Data processing on DATA CELLAR's dataspace and though its functionalities could be a security risk in itself (AEPD, 2023, pp. 62-65).	DATA CELLAR should ensure that data processing is proportional to the purpose of the data processing activity.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DATA CELLAR should not require its users to provide more information and data than is necessary (AEPD, 2023, pp. 65, 90). If that is not possible, then DATA CELLAR should design measures that will lessen this risk (AEPD, 2023, p. 65). 	Medium	Medium
CLR 7.1, CLR 21.10	NIS, EMD	Not using security standards could hamper interoperability.	DATA CELLAR should foster interoperability and standardisation, using EU and international standards and technical conditions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DATA CELLAR should collectively agree on which security and international standards should be used by its dataspace. While doing so, it should consider their effectiveness in terms of security and ability to foster interoperability (AEPD, 2023, pp. 73-74). 	Medium	Low

6.2 Ethical Requirements for cyber and data security

Cybersecurity is not “merely a matter of technologies” (JRC, 2021, Policy and regulatory challenges, p.23) and legal obligations. Rather, cybersecurity poses ethical consequences which may impact society. All digital services, software, and technologies are similar in that they require a relationship of trust with the projected end-user. Trust that, firstly, the services, software, and technology can be used in the manner intended without disruption and, secondly, that their privacy and personal data will be protected. Thus, this subsection will focus on the ethical considerations regarding cyber and data security within the DATA CELLAR project. As with the approach adopted in section 5.2, this section will address the final requirement detailed by the HLEG Guidelines for Trustworthy AI, technical robustness and safety, which covers cyber and data security aspects. Using this HLEG requirement as an analytical tool, the main risks posed by cyber and data security within the DATA CELLAR space will be identified. This step will also be based on partner feedback from the T2.6 Ethics workshop as well as desk research on relevant cybersecurity standards and guidelines. When formulating corresponding protocols and recommendations for the implementation of these guidelines, this section draws on recommendations provided in the HLEG guidelines, the SHERPA project, the NIST framework for improving Critical Infrastructure Cybersecurity⁷⁵, technical reports from the JRC, and international standards for information security

⁷⁵The NIST framework is a voluntary framework for “owners and operators of critical infrastructure to help them identify, assess, and manage cyber risks” - Executive Order no. 13636, Improving Critical Infrastructure Cybersecurity, DCPD-201300091, February 12, 2013. <https://www.gpo.gov/fdsys/pkg/CFR-2014-title3-vol1/pdf/CFR-2014-title3-vol1-eo13636.pdf>

6.2.1 Ethical requirements

Table 12: Ethical requirements for cyber and data security

Ethical framework	Ethical Requirement (ER)	Relevant ethical norms	Explanation
EGTAI	Technical robustness and safety (ER7) ⁷⁶	Security, reliability, reproducibility, resilience, accuracy, non-maleficence.	“Technical robustness requires that AI systems be developed with a preventative approach to risks and in a manner such that they reliably behave as intended while minimising unintentional and unexpected harm and preventing unacceptable harm. This should also apply to potential changes in their operating environment or the presence of other agents (human and artificial) that may interact with the system in an adversarial manner. In addition, the physical and mental integrity of humans should be ensured.” (HLEG, pp.16)

6.2.2 Potential risks and guidelines to address them

Table 13: Relevant risks and guidelines for their mitigation

ER	Relevant functionality	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score	Probability score
ER7.1	All	A cyber-attack on the projects’ software,	Ensure sufficient that	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cybersecurity assessment and testing, such as penetration testing should be 	Medium-High ⁷⁷	Medium-High

⁷⁷ Dependent on the impact of the cyber-attack.

ER	Relevant functionality	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score	Probability score
		hardware, tools, or the energy infrastructure connected to the tools could cause a disruption in energy transmission, a failure in the energy infrastructure, produce energy imbalances, result in miscalculated readings of energy flows, or cause physical harm to people or assets.	cybersecurity measures are implemented throughout the project lifecycle to ensure the accuracy of the tools' outputs and to ensure the security and resilience of the tools as well as the physical assets and processes they are connected to.	<p>used to evaluate potential cybersecurity risks before, after, and during deployment of the tools. Further, network scanning and monitoring tools can be used to check network traffic to check risk boundaries. Such testing procedures should be clearly documented. The integrity of DATA CELLAR software, hardware, or tools should all be tested. This is particularly important in light of the relative vulnerability of IoT sensors and smart meters to cyberattacks and manipulation (Sopra Steria, 2021, Gemini Principles).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The reproducibility of the tools' results should be tested in a range of different environments to ensure accuracy of results, particularly under unexpected conditions such as a cyberattack. • Cybersecurity training should be provided to all stakeholders interacting with the tools and their systems. 		

⁷⁷ Dependent on the impact of the cyber-attack.

ER	Relevant functionality	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score	Probability score
				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Appropriate resilience safeguards should be adopted to ensure the provision of critical services in case of a cyberattack or grid failure. This includes a fallback plan and requirements to support the provision of energy during duress or attack and during recovery. • Systems should include a 'safe shut down' option to minimise potential physical harm caused when physical assets are targeted. • Response and recovery plans should be formulated and consistently updated. • System or tool failures as well as cyberattacks should be logged and documented. Previous incidents should be used to guide necessary adjustments to security measures, produce 'lessons learned,' formulate predictive indicators, and for analysis of particular attack types and methods. • The concept of least functionality should be maintained throughout the design, development, and deployment of the DATA CELLAR tools' configuring systems. This ensures that the systems 		

ER	Relevant functionality	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score	Probability score
				<p>are only being relied upon to provide their intended, essential capabilities, restricting their exposure to cybersecurity threats.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> An information security management process should be adopted to continually ensure that the cybersecurity controls within the DATA CELLAR space match the cybersecurity needs of its systems, processes, and tools. 		
E7.2	All	Personal data may become breached or poisoned as a result of cyberattacks on the tools.	Ensure that adequate data security measures are adopted to protect the integrity, confidentiality, and availability of data.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data security and privacy training should be provided for all stakeholders interacting with the tools and their systems. Such training should illustrate the potential impacts of data poisoning or a data breach in the DATA CELLAR context. Data leak and data loss prevention software should be integrated into the project’s cybersecurity plan. This is particularly important given the range of different nodes communicating within the DATA CELLAR space. 	Medium-High ⁷⁸	Medium-High

⁷⁸Dependent on the nature and impact of the cyber-attack as well as the sensitivity of the data targeted or impacted.

ER	Relevant functionality	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score	Probability score
				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data in transit encryption measures should be implemented. • Red teaming and penetration testing should be used to evaluate potential privacy risks before, after, and during deployment of the tools. Such testing procedures should be clearly documented. The integrity of DATA CELLAR software, hardware, or tools should all be tested. 		
E7.3	All	Cybersecurity measures taken may themselves pose a threat to individuals' privacy and personal data.	Project partners should ensure that cybersecurity risk prevention and response measures should respect individuals' privacy and personal information.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data security measures should be adopted to complement cybersecurity measures, including clear protocols on data collection and retention. These should work to minimise the risk of over-collection or over-retention of personal data due to cybersecurity measures. • The potential privacy implications of cybersecurity measures should be identified, mapped, and documented. This documentation should guide all cybersecurity processes and systems. • Service providers providing cybersecurity-related services for the project should be informed about the project's privacy policies and approach 	Medium	Low

ER	Relevant functionality	Risk	Guidelines	Protocols and recommendations for implementation	Impact score	Probability score
				<p>to personal data collection, usage, sharing, storage, retention, and repurposing. This should be integrated into all relevant training.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Processes to measure the implementation of the projects' privacy policies and controls should be adopted. Those providing cyber-security-related services should be subject to identification processes. Two-factor identification should be adopted in accordance with the challenge response or zero knowledge standard (ISO/IEC 9798, 2019). Access permissions and authorisations should be managed through an access log based on the principles of least privilege and separation of duties. All encryption keys should be safely stored in a secure environment and manner. The consortium should articulate a clear data destruction policy and adhere to this. 		

6.3 Guidelines and best practices that should be adopted by DATA CELLAR

Table 14: Summary of general ethical and legal guidelines for data and cyber-security⁷⁹

No.	Guidelines
All CLR(s)	DATA CELLAR should create appropriate data and cyber-security policies, and clearly outline different roles and responsibilities of relevant parties and data users, which should be used throughout the project lifecycle and reviewed periodically to account for regulatory and legislative changes as well as data and cyber-security vulnerabilities.
ER7.1, All CLR(s)	DATA CELLAR should have suitable technical, ethical, legal and organizational procedures, measures and safeguards for data and cyber-security, which are to be applied throughout the project lifecycle and are capable of ensuring the highest level of accuracy, security and resilience of the DATA CELLAR’s dataspace, tools and functionalities as well as to the best of DATA CELLAR’s ability also the physical assets and processes that they will be linked to them.
E7.2, CLR 1.6, CLR 1.8, CLR 2.6, CLR 3.5, CLR 21.9	DATA CELLAR must safeguard the integrity, confidentiality, and availability of data, throughout the duration of the project and in case of various physical, organizational and technical incidents such as overload of operations, data breaches cyber-security attacks and insolvency.
ER7.3, All CLR(s)	DATA CELLAR must guarantee that its cybersecurity risk prevention and response as well as other cyber and data security measures will respect and account for individuals’ privacy and personal information for example by informing its data users about the security and data-related concerns associated with data processing activities and the steps that could be taken or are being implemented to alleviate them.
CLR 4.1, CLR 11.1, CLR 13.1, CLR 19.1, CLR 21.4	DATA CELLAR should have its dataspace, functionalities and tools in accordance with security by design and security by default principle that is being applied in the cyber-security law.
CLR 6.1, CRL 12	DATA CELLAR, where necessary, should obtain relevant certification for its functionalities and tools, digital products, services, and processes.
CLR1.3, CLR2.2, CLR3.1, CLR 10.1, CLR 21.5	DATA CELLAR should have a suitable and effective reporting procedure for data breaches and cyber-security attacks.

⁷⁹ This table follow guidelines from AEPD, 2023, pp. 89–93.

7 Conclusion

This deliverable addresses the key legal and ethical aspects of data processing as well as cyber and data security within the DATA CELLAR project. Firstly, by summarising the key legal and ethical frameworks which apply to the project, this deliverable formulates legal and ethical requirements for the consortium to follow. For the legal aspects of the project, the key legal frameworks include data protection laws, cybersecurity laws, and energy-specific laws, with the resultant requirements focused on data governance, data ownership and control, compliance with the relevant regulatory frameworks and fundamental rights, and data access and sharing. With regard to the ethical aspects, research ethics principles such as beneficence, autonomy and justice were combined with ethical principles pertaining to data ethics and ethical AI specifically, including transparency, fairness, privacy, and non-maleficence. These aspects were enriched based on partner feedback from the T2.6 co-design workshop. Once these requirements were produced, potential risks preventing the fulfilment of these requirements were ideated. These risks relate to data processing as well as cyber and data security within the data energy sharing space and the relevant functionalities which will support it. Next, legal and ethical guidelines to address these risks were produced, addressing the design, stewardship, structure, classification, formatting and accessibility of the databases used within DATA CELLAR. To support the implementation of these guidelines both within the project and on a regulatory level, each of these guidelines are supported by a range of protocols for implementation. These protocols offer best practices as well as policy-based recommendations on how to practically implement the legal and ethical guidelines. Finally, due to the wide range of legal and ethical guidelines needed within the DATA CELLAR project, impact and probability scores were provided for each risk and its corresponding guidelines and protocols. These help the project partners to prioritise between different risks which, in turn, assists project partners with utilising and applying the guidelines in practice. By mapping the project risks and proposing guidelines in this way, this deliverable contributes to the project's commitment to creating a fair, secure, and user-centric federated dataspace.

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9 Annex 1: T2.6 Ethics Workshop Report

Organized on April 28th 2023, the task 2.6 workshop has aimed to engage project partners in more reflective practices that examine ethical aspects of handling data in the collaborative platform created by the consortium. The insights produced by the workshop help to guide the ethical requirements and guidelines proposed within the deliverable. This annex provides a report of the workshop and its findings.

1. Introduction

After having been introduced to the event, participants have been distributed over four discussion rooms that have been run in parallel. Each room has focused on a specific functionality that will be implemented in the DATA CELLAR. Participants have been guided to discuss assigned functionalities through questions that have allowed understanding the situation that drive the ethical implications and their relevance for the main data types at stake.

Functionalities assigned to each room have been the following ones:

- DR1) Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning
- DR2) Decision support system
- DR3) Data Marketplace
- DR4) Digital Twins

Project partners have been distributed over these discussion rooms as detailed in Table 1 below.

Discussion outcomes have consisted of preliminary lists and characterizations of the main ethical issues identified and this information will serve as an input for the guidelines to be developed under task 2.6.

Chapter 2 of this summary report generally describes the main potential ethical issues discussed in each room. Each section of chapter 2 summarises in particular what discussed in each room and associated functionality and is structured in two parts. The first part of each section describes the potential ethical issues as pre-identified and proposed to discussants by discussion coordinators. The second part provides instead a summary of the potential issues as highlighted and described by discussants themselves.

Considering that a series of addressed ethical issues have resulted to be common to several functionalities and discussion rooms, report chapter 3 provides then an overview and summary of these common ethical issues over the four discussion rooms.

2. Main potential ethical issues addressed in the discussion rooms of the workshop

As mentioned above, this chapter lists and briefly describes the main potential ethical issues discussed in each room. Each chapter section refers to one discussion room and associated functionality. While the first part of these sections describes the potential issues as identified and

proposed to discussants by discussion coordinators, their subsections summarize the potential issues as highlighted by discussant themselves.

2.1. Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML)

The following ethical aspects have been initially described and proposed to discussants as potential issues at stake for the artificial intelligence and machine learning functionalities that are being developed in DATA CELLAR.

1. **Human Agency and Oversight:**
 - Deals with the effect of AI systems that are aimed at guiding, influencing or supporting humans in decision-making processes.
2. **Technical Robustness and Safety:**
 - Issues related to the security, safety, accuracy and reliability of AI systems.
3. **Privacy and Data Governance:**
 - Fundamental right linked to the principle of prevention of harm. Deals with the impact of AI systems on privacy and data protection.
4. **Transparency**
 - Traceability (documentation).
 - Explainability: are decisions of AI systems explained to end-users? Communication of AI system's capabilities and limitations to end users.
 - proper communication of limitations of AI systems.
5. **Diversity, Non-discrimination and Fairness:**
 - Aims at avoiding unfair biases and enabling inclusion and diversity all through the lifecycle of AI systems.
6. **Societal and Environmental Well-being:**
 - Deals with the impacts of AI systems on the environment and society (including the work sphere, institutions, democracy and society at large).
7. **Accountability:**
 - Deals with the need of ensuring responsibility for the development, deployment and use of AI systems.

Depending on the datasets used to train the AI algorithms, several concerns can in principle generally be at stake. For example, if information in the datasets is biased, the design of AI functionalities and decisions undertaken thereby could result unfair or inaccurate.

Other potential concerns relate to how data are collected, who has access to them, and to how these data will be used. Notably, data collection and analysis raise then serious questions at a technical and policy level about needed in-home surveillance and how to address consumers' privacy interests. Another potential issue relates then to inequality and heterogenous expertise.

Users representing industrial and commercial organisations have for example experts who work on optimising energy requirements for their organisations. Private citizens, on the other hand, might lack the expertise, drive and flexibility to change their lifestyles according e.g., to dynamic pricing.

2.1.1. Potential issues on AI and ML as discussed in more detail in the related room

Three main potential ethical issues on AI and ML were discussed in more detail during the workshop. These issues are related to *Explainability, Privacy and Transparency*.

Explainability of decisions taken based on AI decisions and recommendations has been indicated as a relevant problem. One of the main characteristics of AI models is indeed that the designer might not be able, at the end, to explain the trained model's decisions (black-box-problem). This potential issue should however be addressed under DATA CELLAR task 5.5 on algorithmic transparency and explainability.

Two mentioned main potential *privacy issue* concern instead 1) how AI models (and Decision Support System tools) can provide fine-tuned recommendations (meaning user-targeted recommendations) if they only get anonymized data as input and 2) how the DATA CELLAR can ensure that anonymized data cannot be traced back to the user while keeping their usefulness. The possibility of using synthesised datasets has been discussed as a potential option and solution in this case. However, it has also been mentioned that this solution is challenging and requires end-users' training and engagement in the provision of synthetic data.

As far as *transparency* issues are concerned, participants in the discussion rooms mentioned that geopolitical tensions might challenge the possibility of having open data transparency of algorithms. This potential issue has been particularly highlighted for energy distribution networks, as they can be military targets. If data/AI software related to their operativity are open, these networks can indeed result more exposed and less protected and negative impacts can also be generated for the whole society relying on them. On the other hand, it has been also highlighted that open data and AI algorithms could produce significant benefits in non-conflicting geopolitical landscapes.

2.2. Decision Support System (DSS)

The ethical aspects listed in Table 1 below have been initially described and proposed to discussants as potential issues at stake for the Decision Support System being developed in DATA CELLAR.

Table 1: Potential ethical issues of the DSS functionality

Personal Data	Information that relates to an identified or identifiable individual.
Data Privacy	- Does the DSS reveal any direct or indirect information which could be used to identify an individual? E.g. from the grid edge services or directly on the dashboard by a consumer, such as name location, IP addresses etc.
Data Security	- Is personal data secure from corruption, theft, unauthorised access throughout its entire lifecycle in the DSS? This covers all elements of the system, e.g. in hardware, software, user devices.
Artificial Intelligence/ Machine Learning	Computer systems perform tasks normally requiring human intelligence, e.g., perception, recognition, translation, decision-making. Systems that learn and adapt by drawing inferences from patterns in data via algorithms/models.
Data Bias	- Is the data representative of all stakeholders? E.g., different socio-economic groups; persons with disabilities etc. - Is the data representative of all energy types? E.g., wind, solar.
Algorithm Transparency	- Is the dataset and the algorithm used to develop the DSS traceable?
Algorithm Explainability	- Will the end-user be able to understand/have context for the outcomes within the DSS? E.g., reasoning, unknowns, probabilities. Is the human oversight and decision-making genuine?
Ownership and Accountability	- Who owns the data processed, the algorithm and its results? - Who is liable for any harm resulting from the DSS?
Social Justice/Energy Justice	Fairness and the eradication of inequality as it manifests out into society
Accessibility	- Is the DSS accessible for different end-users?
Environmental Impacts	- What are the environmental impacts of the DSS? Data consumption/storage impacts.
Inclusive Process/ Just Transition	- How have/will affected communities been/be involved in the development process? Will the benefits of the Data Cellar solution be shared widely among society?

2.1.1. Potential issues on DSS as discussed in more detail in the related room

In relation to *privacy and security of data* employed by the DSS, potential issues might arise with needed *energy consumption profiles* and associated location to be managed through excel files. These files should however not include personal data like email, phone numbers, fiscal/tax number, etc.. Energy consumption data might then not have to be generally considered as personal data, although this might depend on how specific the information of the associated location might be. In principle, this potential issue might nevertheless be overcome by ingesting input values separately, although this approach might not be optimal.

Potential data privacy and security issues might then affect employed *algorithms*. Personal data are indeed generally needed e.g., for forecast tools, including solar radiation forecasts. The employment of city-level data might perhaps allow avoiding this issue.

It has then also to be noted that data employed by the DSS should have already been anonymized by the anonymization tool being developed under CERTH coordination. It is however not yet clear whether this tool will anonymize also personal data employed by algorithms. A main decision to be taken is therefore how specific the location data will have to be.

Data security remains then a bigger general concern and it has to be decided how the DATA CELLAR and the DSS will protect personal data.

Repurposing of personal data is another potential issue in so far as 1) user control of repurposing should be enabled and 2) repurposing requires a new legal basis under the GDPR.

Possible algorithms and data *biases* represent another potentially relevant issue. Some biases might for example arise 1) when an algorithm will have to determine how energy is shared within a local energy community and the coefficient to be used to do this in a fair way, 2) in case of the absence of energy consumption data for some households or lack of detection of situations of energy poverty or 3) when algorithms might be used to support decisions at the household level by relying on calculations based on anonymized data. The relevance of the last issue might however depend on the granularity expected to be achieved by the DSS and on whether it will target the community level or a lower granularity level. These potential biases might in principle be totally or partially overcome by understanding communities and existing inequalities by relying on wider research. The presence of energy poverty areas might for example be detected through data provided by NGOs, Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) and Governments. Biases might then be reduced by using possibly available *larger datasets* or by exploiting *interoperability/clustering advantages* allowing relying on dataspace being developed through other projects (e.g. dataspace on health). Whatever the bias at stake, *transparency* remains however an important component to ensure algorithms outputs reproducibility.

Another relevant ethical aspect to be addressed in the opinion of discussants consists then in ensuring that the DSS is implemented through the most *energy sustainable* approaches and that this system can actually contribute to reducing the environmental impacts of local energy communities.

2.3 Data Marketplace

The ethical aspects listed under Table 2 below have been initially proposed to discussants as potential issues at stake for listed end-users and business cases addressed in the Data Marketplace being developed in DATA CELLAR.

Table 2: Potential ethical issues at stake with the Data Marketplace

No#	Ethical issue	Data analytics developers	electric mobility operators	energy communities	energy consumers and prosumers	flexibility market operators	policy makers	scientific community under the project business cases planned for these users
Data Related								
1.	Data privacy	X	X	X	X		X	X
2.	Data Security	X	X	X	X	X		X
3.	Bias	X		X	X		X	X
4.	Ownership and control	X	X	X	X	X		X
AI Related								
5.	Algorithms Transparency	X		X	X		X	X
6.	Algorithms Explainability	X		X			X	X
Societal Related								
7.	Environmental impact		X	X	X		X	X
8.	Fairness		X	X	X	X	X	X
9.	Energy justice		X	X	X		X	X
10.	Trust	X	X	X	X	X		X

The following main specific aspects and questions related to above mentioned potential issues have then been proposed for discussion

- **Data privacy:** in most of the EU countries, energy consumption data and energy tariffs can be mainly or uniquely handled by the distribution system operators and energy suppliers. How to address this potential issue?
- **Energy justice:** which consumers and energy communities might be excluded from access to the energy marketplace? Which kind of market discrimination might be generated? Which data might have to be gathered to address just energy transition issues? (Geo-localization? Income?) Is data anonymization always a good thing under a just transition perspective?
- **Bias:** which might be some main biases generated in the energy data marketplace? Which end-users might be the most affected? Which misalignment between real assets and digital data may occur in the energy data marketplace?⁸⁰
- **Transparency, reliability and safety** requirements of protocols and smart contracts underpinning crypto-assets. How can a smart contract - i.e., a blockchain-based computer program automatically executing instructions - be made legally binding?
- **Ownership and control:** considering that data will be stored in all nodes of the system, how can data owners and data controllers be defined in the block-chain models to be implemented? Who would be in charge for a data-breach notification if something illicit

⁸⁰ It is worth mentioning that, as data/models available in the marketplace will be used in conjunction with other online Data Cellar Services (e.g., DSS for energy communities, Dashboard/HMI and Digital Twin), some potential biases of the data market place might be the same that might potentially affect these services.

happens in a block-chain system? How could privacy preferences be managed in energy data marketplace?

- **Environmental impact:** how to ensure that energy data market place promotes the employment of renewable energy sources and energy sustainability?
- **Security:** which security measures should be implemented to avoid security and privacy breach in a DLT market infrastructure? Who owns responsibility for what concerns the cybersecurity of a blockchain based service? Which emergency measures and plans might be needed for a DLT market infrastructure?
- **Trust:** how might trust in the data marketplace and the associated block-chain technology be generated? How can full trust on the validators be ensured in the private permissioned applications employed in the block-chain architecture of DATA CELLAR?

Besides above-mentioned points, other questions to be considered concern then stakeholders to be involved to address mentioned potential issues. The following questions have been in particular proposed for discussion:

- a) Which are the **main stakeholders** to be involved to address identified ethical issues? (Governments? Regulatory bodies? Energy companies? Consumers?)
- b) How can governments and regulatory bodies work with companies to **ensure that ethical practices are maintained** in an energy data marketplace?
- c) Which role should consumers play in promoting ethical practices in the energy data market place?
- d) How can the DATA CELLAR consortium possibly **contribute to achieve agreement** between main stakeholders and to define roles to address identified ethical issues?

2.3.1. Potential issues on the Data Marketplace as discussed in more detail in the related room

One point raised by discussants concerns the fact that everything uploaded in the marketplace could in principle be visible to everybody having access to the DATA CELLAR. Avoiding storing (*sensitive*) *personal data* will therefore be key.

Reliability of validators acting in the restricted private permissioned block-chain architecture module that will be implemented in DATA CELLAR is another mentioned key point.

Under this architecture module, data sets and energy data possibly exchanged will not be stored in the DATA CELLAR and the only data actually stored will be those related to the *transactions* made. This approach solves a series of potential ethical issues related to privacy, data retention, data deletion rights, etc. Information about users involved in the transactions and in data sharing will nevertheless anyhow travel across the block-chain. It will therefore be important to achieve a better understanding *how users identity can be managed in the block-chain system* and which potential privacy issues this management might generate.

As the DATA CELLAR will employ households and companies metered data, discussants stressed the need to identify and apply suitable *consent mechanisms* on data sharing.

Other issues stressed by discussants concern:

- *fairness* and the need to ensure that all data providers and users are treated equitably;
- the fact that the marketplace must be *transparent* in relation to its own policy;
- *transparency* on how data will be shared and on how they will be aggregated;
- *biases* and reliability of employed data and of employed AI trained modules;
- the need to identify a *controller* ensuring that users cannot have information about what other users are doing and that users' identity is preserved;
- *inclusiveness* and the fact the disabled people or vulnerable categories might be prevented from data marketplace access.

2.4 Digital twins

The ethical aspects listed under table 3 below have been pre-identified by task 2.6 partners (notably by UBITECH Energy and EDG West) as potentially relevant for the digital twins functionalities that will be developed in DATA CELLAR.

Table 3: Potential ethical issues at stake with Digital Twins

Key	Ethical issue	Data analytics developers	electric mobility operators	energy communities	energy consumers and prosumers	flexibility market operators	policy makers	scientific community under the project business cases planned for those users
1.	Data privacy	X	X	X	X	X		X
2.	Energy justice			X	X		X	
3.	Bias	X					X	X
4.	Ownership and control		X	X		X		
5.	Transparency	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
6.	Environmental impact			X			X	
7.	Fairness			X	X		X	

More specifically, above mentioned partners have pre-identified the following general points of attention:

- The digital twin will rely on data collected from the community, including *data on energy usage and generation*. This can generate concerns about how these data are collected, who has access to it, and how they are being used.
- The use of a digital twin to manage a low energy community project may raise questions about **energy justice**. For example, there may be concerns that certain groups within the community are being excluded or disadvantaged.
- If the data used to create the digital twin is *biased*, this could result in **unfair or inaccurate decisions** being made. For example, if the digital twin assumes that certain types of energy generation are always more efficient than others, this could lead to decisions that favour one type of energy generation over another.
- There may be questions about who **owns** the digital twin and who has the right to **control** it. This could be particularly important if the digital twin is being used to manage a shared energy resource, such as a community solar panel.

- The use of a digital twin to manage a low energy community project may not be **transparent** to all members of the community. It is important to ensure that the digital twin is open and transparent, so that all members of the community can understand how decisions are being made and how data is being used
- The use of a digital twin to manage a low energy community project may have **environmental impacts**, such as increased energy usage or emissions from data centres. It is important to consider the environmental impact of the digital twin and take steps to mitigate any negative effects.
- The use of a digital twin to manage a low energy community project may have implications for **fairness**. For example, there may be concerns that certain members of the community are benefiting more from the project than others.

2.4.1. Potential issues on Digital Twins as discussed in more detail in the related room

Ownership has been considered as the most relevant potential issue in the discussion room on digital twins. An initial and relevant consideration made in this room is that ownership of data processed by DATA CELLAR should be ultimately attributed to homeowners. Neither local communities, nor distribution system operators (DSOs) or other involved stakeholders should indeed probably be considered as the original owners of processed data. For this reason, homeowners should most probably retain and consent to everything that can be possibly done with their data. There are however several circumstances in which same data might have multiple owners. These general considerations have a series of ethical implications and can be at the root of a series of potential ethical issues and concerns.

A first series of potential concerns highlighted in this room relates therefore to *ownership, accountability, responsibility and privacy* issues at stake with Digital Twins. On the one hand, there are indeed owners of data needed to build digital twins. On the other hand, there are users/buyers of digital twins functionalities. And then there are the owners and developers of the services that will be supplied. Defining and handling data ownership, accountability and privacy might therefore be challenging due to this variety of stakeholders involved. To address some of these issues, it might be key to define proper consent clauses and to obtain data owners consent before uploading and employing any kind of data⁸¹. Proper agreements should be established whereby data users and providers make explicit the reasons why they require the data/or the specific reasons why they are opting in to provide the data and this might require the application of multiple privacy policies. It has then to be pointed out that data used should be as much as possible disjointed by identifiers of data owners and of their geographical origin, although data cannot be anonymized and aggregated in all circumstances and specific knowledge of the issues at stake with the various outputs and employment of the digital twin functionality will be needed to establish when this can be possible. For example, distribution system operators (DSOs) can adopt anonymization and enforce suitable limits for access to private data in circumstances where information at the substation or higher level can be sufficient. In other circumstances, DSOs might instead have to decide, possibly through digital twins, whether some energy generation unit has to be shut down and anonymization cannot be pursued. For cases like these, DSOs might however sign specific agreements, although there

⁸¹ It has been pointed out that building on experience and competences developed in previous projects might be very useful to address these aspects.

might in principle be plenty of homeowners not opting in. Freedom left to homeowners to opt in and opt out poses, therefore, a very relevant challenge, in so far as this freedom might cause that data needed are not provided and biases and situations of underrepresentation might be generated.

Accountability and responsibility have been mentioned as key aspects also in relation to cybersecurity and the possibility of security breaches. These aspects are particularly relevant because, as mentioned above, digital twins may be employed to control *physical assets* and may in principle be connected with metering devices and sensors of various kind. Defining responsibility in case something goes wrong is therefore of primary relevance. Certification and validation processes have most probably a key role to play in this case together with offered possibilities to verify the credentials of the operators and of possible controllers. Altogether, this will however require extra legal review.

It has then been pointed out that *security* issues and the generation of non-optimal solutions might be also associated with the fact that people do not always provide correct information.

Copyrights of service developers are then another aspect linked to ownership that will most probably need to be addressed in the opinion of some discussants as service developers somehow enrich employed data.

Another highlighted connected potential issues is *transparency* in so far as data owners should be informed about how their data will be shared, who will access them, who will use them and how.

Trust in and achievement of a sufficient level of employment of digital twins functionality have also been mentioned as a relevant challenge, particularly because people may be reluctant to use the functionality where multiple responsibilities are involved. In this respect, it has been mentioned that DSOs will have a fundamental role in creating trust and ensuring uptake by providing consumers with information about the reliability and trustworthiness of stakeholders using and collecting their data. DSOs might then outsource their data to third parties but responsibility would anyhow remain over them.

Critical for the scientific community, for data analytics developers and policy makers will then be *biased* possibly generated by the fact e.g., that given sectors might be underrepresented and employed energy tariffs might not be correct, all these aspects having potentially negative consequences on incentives and policies that might be conceived by relying on the outputs of DATA CELLAR functionalities. In this respect, it has been highlighted that *validation and machine learning processes* might have a key role to play also in ensuring that sufficient accuracy and levels of security can be achieved. DSOs will however also have responsibility in ensuring this. Also data analytics developers will however have the responsibility to ensure to generate as accurate representations as possible.

Data scalability and replicability have then been mentioned as another relevant aspect to be addressed in order to allow producing large benefits and serve energy consumers and producers. This might however require the adoption of proper *precaution principles* and responsibility principles to be observed by the scientific community to ensure that produced outputs are as reliable as possible.

3. Overview of the main potential ethical issues highlighted by discussants

Table 4 summarises the main potential ethical issues highlighted by discussants for the four functionalities addressed in the workshop.

The fact that discussants have focused on some issues and not mentioned others might clearly be due to a variety of reasons including, for example, the short time made available for discussions during the workshop. There are therefore certainly relevant potential issues that have not been mentioned by discussants in some rooms despite their high relevance. Biases represent for example a potentially very relevant issue for AI and ML functionalities, despite they do not seem to have occupied most of the discussions held in the related room. On the other hand, the fact that some issues have been highlighted in several rooms can nevertheless be considered as an indicator of their relevance and of the priority project partners think should be assigned to them when it comes to decide which are the main ethical aspects to focus on in DATA CELLAR.

Table 4: Main potential ethical issues highlighted by workshop discussants

Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning	Decision Support System	Data Marketplace	Digital Twins
Privacy	Privacy	Privacy, users identity management, consent mechanisms	Privacy, data ownership and intellectual property rights
		Identification of a controller, reliability of validators in the block-chain architecture	Accountability & Responsibility
Transparency	Transparency	Transparency	Transparency
	Security		Security
		Trust	Trust
	Biases	Biases	Biases
Explainability	Repurposing of personal data		
	Energy & environmental sustainability	Fairness & inclusiveness	Scalability and replicability

The text below provides therefore a short summary of how the relevance of potential issues mentioned more times has been described for the different functionalities addressed in the discussion rooms. As said, other potential ethical issues addressed in the paragraphs above need however certainly also careful consideration, despite not being mentioned hereunder.

3.1. Privacy, data ownership and intellectual property rights

In the case of AI and ML functionalities, *privacy* has been indicated as a potential issue in so far as 1) the need to fulfil privacy obligations can impede that fine-tuned and user-targeted recommendations can be produced through these functionalities and 2) suitable aggregation and anonymization approaches have to be identified to avoid that data can be traced back to the owners they represent.

In the case of the DSS, privacy issues have been mentioned in relation to 1) the need to manage energy consumption profiles and associated location and to 2) the necessity of ensuring that privacy obligations do not affect the proper functioning of algorithms to be employed e.g., to forecast energy consumption and production at given locations.

In the discussion room on the data marketplace, it has instead been stressed that a better understanding needs to be achieved in relation to how users' identity can be managed in the block-chain system and associated transactions to prevent the generation of potential privacy issues.

In the discussion room on digital twins, potential privacy and ownership issues have been associated with the presence of a variety of stakeholders who might be entitled of various degrees of data ownership. On the one hand, there are indeed owners of data needed to build digital twins. On the other hand, there are users/buyers of digital twins functionalities. And then there are the owners and developers of the services that will be supplied. It has therefore been mentioned that 1) defining and handling data ownership and privacy might be challenging due to this variety of stakeholders involved and that 2) it might be key to define proper consent clauses and to obtain data owners consent before uploading and employing any kind of data to address these issues. *Copyrights of service developers* are then another aspect linked to ownership that will most probably need to be addressed in the opinion of some discussants as service developers somehow enrich employed data.

3.2. Accountability, responsibility and identification of a controller

Accountability and responsibility have been generally mentioned as key aspects in relation to cybersecurity and the possibility of security breaches. These aspects have been particularly stressed in case of the digital twins functionality, as digital twins may be employed to control *physical assets* and may in principle be connected with metering devices and sensors of various kinds. Defining responsibility in case something goes wrong has therefore been considered of primary relevance in these cases. Certification and validation processes have then been indicated as key solutions to these potential issues together with offered possibilities to verify the credentials of the operators and of possible controllers.

The need for controllers ensuring that users cannot have information about what other users are doing and that users' identity is preserved has been stressed also in the discussion room on the data marketplace. Connected to this aspect is then probably also the need to ensure the reliability of

validators acting in the restricted private permissioned block-chain architecture module that will be implemented in DATA CELLAR.

3.3. Transparency

Transparency has been discussed in all workshop rooms. In the discussion room on AI and ML it has been pointed out that geopolitical tensions might challenge the possibility of having open data transparency of algorithms, notably because DSOs might become military targets in these situations.

Related to the need for transparency is then the necessity of ensuring user control of the repurposing of (personal) data that has been stressed by discussants in the room on DSS.

The need for transparency on how data will be shared, on how they will be aggregated and in relation to who will access them, who will use them and how has been then highlighted in the discussion rooms on the data marketplace and digital twins.

3.4. Security

Data security has been indicated as a main potential issue and big concern in the discussion room on DSS. There, the need to decide how the DATA CELLAR and the DSS will protect personal data has been stressed. Cybersecurity and the possibility of security breaches have then been indicated as the main potential issues in the case of digital twins. As already mentioned above, digital twins may indeed be employed to control *physical assets* and may in principle be connected with metering devices and sensors of various kinds.

3.5. Trust

Trust in the data marketplace and approaches to be considered to foster participation in this market are certain key aspects to be considered in DATA CELLAR. *Trust* in and achievement of a sufficient level of employment of digital twins functionality have also been mentioned as a relevant challenge, particularly because people may be reluctant to use the functionality where multiple responsibilities are involved. In this respect, it has been mentioned that DSOs will have a fundamental role in creating trust and ensuring uptake by providing consumers with information about reliability and trustworthiness of stakeholders using and collecting their data.

3.6. Biases

Biases are another main potential issue that has received a lot of attention during workshop discussions. For example, possible algorithms and data biases have been indicated as a potentially relevant issue in the discussion room on DSS. In that room, the following possible biases have been mentioned and discussed in particular:

- 1) biases generated when an algorithm will have to determine how energy is shared within a local energy community and the coefficient to be used to do this in a fair way;
- 2) biases generated in case of absence of energy consumption data for some households or lack of detection of situations of energy poverty;
- 3) biases generated when algorithms might be used to support decisions at the household level by relying on calculations based on anonymized data.

Biases possibly generated by the fact that e.g., given sectors might be underrepresented and employed energy tariffs might not be correct have been considered as very critical for the scientific

community, for data analytics developers and policy makers that will possibly rely on digital twins. In this respect, it has then been highlighted that validation and ML processes might have a key role to play in ensuring that sufficient accuracy levels can be achieved. It has however also been stressed that DSOs and data analytics developers will have the responsibility to ensure to generate as accurate representations as possible.